

iMPACT HTA

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

An analytical framework outlining the determinants of HTA recommendations across settings based on primary data collection and primary analysis of secondary data

Work Package 7 - Deliverable 7.1 (Task 1)

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List of Abbreviations

ASMR	Amélioration du service médical rendu (France)
CADTH	Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health
DG SANTE	Directorate General for Health and Food Safety
EUnetHTA	European Network for Health Technology Assessment
GBA	Federal Joint Committee (Germany)
HAS	Haute Autorité de Santé (France)
HRQoL	Health-Related Quality of Life
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
ICER	Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio
INESSS	Institut National d'Excellence en Santé et en Services Sociaux (Quebec)
KCE	Belgian Health Care Knowledge Centre
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
PBAC	Pharmaceutical Benefits Advisory Committee ()
QALY	Quality-Adjusted Life Year
SMC	Scottish Medicines Consortium
SMR	Service médical rendu
SVJ	Social Value Judgement
TLV	Dental and Pharmaceutical Benefits Agency (Sweden)
WP	Work Package
WTP	Willingness-to-pay

**PART A - An analytical framework outlining the determinants
of HTA recommendations across settings based on primary
analysis of secondary data**

Background

In the past few decades, countries have been facing an increase pressure on healthcare budgets due to a steady growth in the demand for health products and services together with the rapid development of new expensive technologies [1]. In order to allocate scarce resources efficiently, health policy-makers have become gradually interested in developing and implementing methods of value-based pricing for the assessment of new medical technologies.

The main aim of these tools is to allow policy-makers to perform informed decisions on whether health technologies should be reimbursed by assessing their value in relation to their opportunity costs. To this end, health technology assessment (HTA) has been implemented in a growing number of countries to support decision-makers with choices regarding the services and products to be made routinely available as part of national healthcare systems.

HTA has been developed and evolved in partial response to the uncontrolled spread of costly health technologies and is defined as a “multidisciplinary, dynamic, rapidly evolving process” [1] that is strengthened by various types of assessment while aiming to inform policymakers about the value of health products [1]. The HTA process usually analyses different aspects of a given technology, attempting to capture their value. However, since data are often scarce and incomplete or of low quality, decision-makers have to apply judgements on their value. This set of judgements are commonly identified as value judgements and they could be scientific or societal/social. Whereas the first set of judgements is specifically around the quality and acceptability of clinical and economic evidence (e.g. acceptability of placebo-controlled trials or surrogate outcomes over clinical outcomes) the latter concern all those elements affecting patients, carers, families and society as a whole.

Despite a continuous improvement in the methods and the ways of implementing it, HTA does not come without shortcomings. Two main criticisms have been raised over time. First, HTA is not always implemented in a similar manner across different countries. Studies have identified variations in the evaluation of evidence [2-5], agency structures [6-8], and guidelines for conducting HTA [9, 10]. Although the scientific evidence sustaining the clinical effectiveness may be similar when conducting HTA, the way a technology is evaluated (i.e. how the evaluation is used to arrive at recommendations on its value in the health sector) may vary from country to country. Consequently, decisions taken may differ widely across settings, eventually leading to a different level of access to treatments across countries. A growing number of studies have emphasized the need to homogenize HTA processes across countries [2, 11, 12]. Acknowledging the differences in healthcare organization and provision

across countries, different studies have suggested that there is ground for standardization in clinical and economic evaluation methods in order to align these, while still allowing for adaptation at country level based on need [1, 12-14].

Different initiatives, particularly in Europe, have been set up to promote minimum standard levels for the use of HTA. For instance, the European Network for Health Technology Assessment (EUnetHTA) started with the aim of improving HTA methods and minimising duplication of effort. It has developed an HTA framework (“HTA core model”) that should enable the sharing of information across countries and a greater harmonization of HTA methods across countries [15]. Recently, the Directorate General for Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE) of the European Commission published an impact assessment proposing a new scenario for a closer cooperation on HTA at EU level beyond 2020 when funding for EUnetHTA will come to an end [16], which was subsequently followed by a draft regulation on EU cooperation on HTA.

Second, analyzing the (additional) clinical benefit and the cost-effectiveness of new technologies, including medicines, HTA is attempting to value all the aspects of a new technology or health intervention. However, the real value given by a new technology could be multidimensional and extend beyond what it is commonly understood as part of an assessment of the clinical benefit relative to the cost. Due to the complexity of this multidimensionality, it is still open to debate as to which elements capturing the value of new health technologies (including pharmaceuticals) should be included in clinical and economic evaluations [17-20]. Different studies [6, 21, 22] have highlighted that the elements capturing the broader value of a technology and its impact at societal level, should include dimensions such as severity of the disease, innovation, nature of the intervention, and whether the intervention has an administration advantage in comparison with current treatment, among others. In the context of pharmaceuticals and other health interventions, these elements should have a clear weight when assessing their cost-effectiveness and could be consistently considered in HTA evaluations.

Currently, a large proportion of HTAs examine the clinical and cost-effectiveness of new interventions by considering the incremental (quality-adjusted) therapeutic benefit, in the form of Quality Adjusted Life Years (QALY) gained, relative to their incremental cost. Because of the significant emphasis placed by the HTA agencies on the use QALY gained as a measure of therapeutic benefit and quality of life, the literature has been questioning this metric highlighting its limitation in capturing important factors embedded in the value of new medicines [21, 23, 24].

Overall, and considering the multiplicity of factors that feed into the value of new medical technologies, there is a need for improving available tools and methods for assessing their value, as well as overcome the limitations of the current approaches.

Objectives and methodological approach

Within the European context, although health and social policy remain a responsibility of the Member States, there is an increasing perception that an opportunity exists for improving the effectiveness and efficiency of health technology procurement by implementing cross-country collaboration in a range of activities, including Health Technology Assessment (HTA). This certainly applies to the field of methodological development, but also in that of empirical and applied study. In some cases (e.g. RCTs and other clinical studies) the results of a specific study can be almost directly applied to other settings, but in the case of economic evaluations, a number of aspects must be customized to country-specific circumstances in order to attain external validity. Recent years have also seen significant changes such that data on costs and health outcomes are now available from an increasing range of sources underscoring the need for better data integration and evidence synthesis, as well as the strengthening of data generation processes for economic evaluations and the improvement in methodological quality. Based on these challenges, the overall objectives of TASK 1 of work package 7 (WP7) are:

- To create an analytical framework explaining the determinants of HTA coverage recommendations linking the quality of evidence, social value judgements and other considerations that may be relevant to decision-makers. Methodologically, task 1 selects a sample of approximately 200 drug-indication pairs that have undergone HTA during the 2009 – 2018 period across different jurisdictions and for which HTA reports and recommendations are available. Country/HTA agency selection will be based on different models of HTA as they apply in different jurisdictions. Drug-indication pairs will be selected from across therapeutic classes and based on what HTA agencies have assessed/appraised during the above study period.
- Based on the primary objective, a methodological framework will be created to inform the data collection process, which builds on previous attempts [25, 26] and in order to identify critical variables in the evidence submitted to HTA bodies (both clinical and economic, if the latter only where it is applicable), the interpretation of the evidence from HTA bodies

(including the scientific and the social value judgements made) and seek to identify components of uncertainty as well as elicited and non-elicited other considerations that may have played a role in the assessment/appraisal process for each drug-indication pair. It is envisaged that several variables (between 35-40 per drug-indication pair) will be collected this way, which will then be included, coded and categorized in a spreadsheet in readiness for analysis. Econometric analysis will be used to identify the determinants of HTA recommendations and the role or importance of precise criteria that have been used in each setting to make coverage recommendations and will estimate the effect of different evaluation parameters (e.g. orphan status, unmet need, surrogate endpoints, as well as therapeutic area- or treatment-specific variables). This process will feed into the creation of a draft value framework outlining the importance and relevance of different parameters of value across settings. The sample will be sufficiently large to enable sub-group analysis in which the nuances of different therapeutic areas can be explored and analyzed (e.g. CNS vs. cancer; how orphan indications differ from non-orphan, etc). In a final step, we will use this evidence to triangulate with the HTA agencies or health insurance organizations concerned to discuss and validate our findings as well as collect individual feedback on the thinking and criteria applied in individual cases. This will be done through face-to-face meetings during the first 22 months of the project. Based on these discussions, the analytical framework will contain the outcome of the econometric evaluation with the appropriate variable coefficients, coupled with qualitative evidence explaining their importance and relevance according to setting. The deliverable from this task will be an evidence-based and validated analytical framework outlining the determinants of HTA recommendations, relying on primary analysis of secondary data and primary data collection to validate this analysis (M18).

Methods

The collection and analysis of HTA data across countries was based on a multi-stage framework aiming to capture in a systematic way the key elements of HTA processes. Six steps were followed (Figure 1) in order to select the sample, and collect and analyze the data.

Figure 1 - Flow of data collection process

3.1 Country/HTA Agency Selection

Country selection was made in order to have a representative sample of the different approaches adopted in HTA (e.g. health service, societal), whilst at the same time ensuring data availability and comparability across settings. A number of predefined inclusion criteria were used for country selection: (a) whether they had well-established HTA agencies and processes, (b) whether a range of decision-making criteria (clinical and/or cost-effectiveness) were explicitly used, and (c) whether the HTA reports were publicly available. A total of 7 countries were identified that met the inclusion criteria. The study countries were France, Sweden, Scotland, England, Germany, Canada (at federal and provincial level) and Australia.

In two countries, Canada and Germany, multiple HTA agencies perform assessments which impact coverage decisions. In Canada, the main agency at National level, the Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health (CADTH) and one of the largest agencies at provincial level L'Institut national d'excellence en santé et en services sociaux (INESSS), were included. While, INESSS reports inform reimbursement decisions in one province (Quebec), CADTH informs reimbursement decisions in all other provinces within Canada. Following national HTA, Ontario also elects to perform an HTA evaluation to supplement the CADTH report. Therefore, three agencies meet the inclusion criteria within Canada: CADTH, INESSS, and HQO. INESSS can be considered as a standalone agency as it informs reimbursement decisions for Quebec in isolation of CADTH and HQO. CADTH and HQO will be considered jointly as both factor into reimbursement decisions within Ontario.

In Germany, both the Federal Joint Committee (GBA) and the Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Healthcare (IQWiG) perform HTA. The GBA commissions IQWiG to perform the majority of health technology assessments. The GBA will then review the IQWiG submission and perform its own assessment, where it may change the recommendation provided by IQWiG. In some cases, IQWiG does not assess drugs and GBA performs the only assessment. For Germany, IQWiG and GBA will be considered jointly as both influence final recommendations. However, GBA reports will be only be considered in situations where a change in the recommendation is made or where IQWiG has not performed an assessment. Table 1 provides a list of Health Technology Assessment agencies for the countries included in this study.

Table 1 – Health Technology Assessment Agencies included in database

Country	HTA Agency	Level	Role	Clinical benefit	Cost-effectiveness
Australia	Pharmaceutical Benefits Advisory Committee (PBAC)	National	Advisory	✓	✓
Canada	Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health (CADTH)	National	Advisory	✓	✓
	Institut National d'Excellence en Santé et en Services Sociaux (INESSS)	Provincial	Regulatory	✓	✓
	Health Quality Ontario (HQO)	Provincial	Regulatory	✓	✗
England	The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE)	National	Advisory	✓	✓
France	French National Authority for Health (HAS)	National	Advisory	✓	✗
Germany	Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Healthcare (IQWiG)	National	Advisory	✓	✗
	Federal Joint Committee (GBA)	National	Regulatory	✓	✗
Scotland	Scottish Medicines Consortium (SMC)	National	Advisory	✓	✓
Sweden	The Dental and Pharmaceutical Benefits Agency (TLV)	National	Advisory	✓	✓

3.2 Drug-Indication Pair Selection

In order to select a representative sample of drug-indication pairs that have undergone HTA assessment between 1st January 2009 – and 1st January 2018, across different jurisdictions and for which HTA reports and recommendations are available a two-step approach was adopted: 1) Identification of all drug indication pairs assessed by selected HTA agencies over the study period, and 2) Selection of representative sample of drug-indication pairs.

Upon reflection of the various HTA agencies' scope and prioritization methods, it is clear that only 5 of the 10 agencies will influence the selection process. Therefore, a number of assumptions can be made in order to simplify the selection process: (a) HAS and SMC assess all new EMA-approved products that apply for inclusion in the benefits catalogue in France and Scotland, respectively, and are, therefore, taken as reference in the selection process; (b) Given that IQWiG and GBA will be analysed jointly, IQWiG and GBA are grouped together for selection. The agency is listed as IQWiG+GBA and drug-indication pairs will be screened to see if they have been assessed by either one of the two agencies; (c) Canadian HTA Agencies assess all products receiving marketing authorisation from Health Canada. Therefore, only one agency (CADTH) is needed in order capture potential differences in the marketed drug-indication pair pool between Canada, Europe, and Australia.

First, websites of the selected HTA agencies (TLV, NICE, IQWiG+GBA, CADTH, PBAC), were queried in order to ensure the feasibility of data collection and to ensure that drug-indication pairs that have been commonly assessed by multiple agencies are included in the study. All publicly available reports published between 1st of January 2009 and 1st of January 2018 were retrieved. Data from all HTA reports extracted were compiled in a excel spreadsheet in order to identify common drug-indication pairs across the agencies. The variables recorded were: brand name, molecule name, date of decision, the indication under review, ATC code and web link to access to the report. Each HTA report was entered as a single row within the excel sheet. Entries were then organised according to molecule name. Each molecule was then reviewed and assessments not suitable for analysis were excluded. Key exclusion criteria were:

- Generic medicines
- Biosimilar medicines
- First submission with a subsequent re-submission. When there was a prior decision (usually a rejection), only the latest major submission for a specific indication was included in the

database. Minor submissions and original submissions for a specific indication were excluded, such that there is only a single entry per Agency for a particular drug-indication pair. For drug-indication pairs selected, prior rejections, re-submission or changes in restrictions will be taken into account in data collection in order to capture the entire decision-making process that is relevant for a selected product.

- Medicines assessed by only 1 HTA bodies

Following exclusion of unsuitable assessments, a list of all drug-indication pairs assessed was compiled in order to facilitate selection. In situations where the wording of indication varied slightly across agencies, entries were discussed internally in order to determine whether or not indications could be considered the same, or if they should be listed separately. Agreement was requirement amongst a minimum of two individuals before inclusion in the final list.

Second, a sample of at least 200 drug-indication pairs was selected from the drug-indication pair list. Drug-indication pairs were organized according to: a) total number of agencies that reviewed each drug-indication pair and b) the date in which the assessments took place (from most to least recent). Drug-indication pairs were selected in different rounds until a total of 200 or more drug-indication pairs were selected. If the number of drug-indication pairs exceeds 200, drug-indication pairs with the oldest EMA approval date will be removed until a total of 200 drug-indication pairs remain. Table 2 outlines the selection criteria for each round.

Table 1 - Drug-indication pair selection criteria

Round	Selection Criteria
1	Drug-indication pairs that have been assessed by 5 agencies
2	Drug-indication pairs that have been assessed by 4 agencies
3	Drug-indication pairs that have been assessed by 3 agencies
4	Drug-indication pairs that have been assessed by 2 agencies

Once a sample of 200 drug-indication pairs was selected, the drug-indication pairs were categorized according to ATC-code and compared to the total list of drug-indication pairs in order to screen for any potential biases in therapeutic area. If the sample was not representative or biased in favour of a

particular therapeutic area, drug-indications would be substituted with those assessed by fewer agencies in order to produce a sample that is representative.

3.3 Update to include drugs assessed between 1st January and 1st of June 2018

The timeframe was extended subsequently in order to capture the most recent medicines assessed between the 1st of January 2018 and the 1st of June 2018. In June 2018, all publicly available reports published between these dates were retrieved and added to the main extraction table in order to identify more recent assessments. The same methodology was applied for selection of drug-indication pairs during this period with the aim of selecting an additional 25-30 drug-indication pairs.

3.4 Variables design

In order to capture in detail key elements included in HTA reports, a comprehensive set of variables were extracted from each HTA report and inserted into an excel spreadsheet. The construction of a composite set of variables would enable an understanding of the differences in evidence across HTA bodies and differences in the assessment of medicines across settings. This would allow the identification of key commonalities and differences both, in the evidence per se (and therefore at assessment level), and in their interpretation at appraisal level.

The variables were organized according to 6 macro-level headings (see Table 1): (a) general information, containing all the information regarding the key dates and outcomes of the HTA decision; (b) Clinical evidence, summarizing all the clinical evidence considered by the HTA body; (c) Economic evidence, capturing information on the economic models considered by the HTA body; (d) Risk sharing agreements, capturing all the (financial and non-financial) agreements between pharmaceutical companies and health care systems to mitigate risk; (e) Uncertainties, capturing all the concerns raised by the HTA body around the clinical and economic evidence presented; and (f) Social Value Judgements (SVJs), interpreting key elements related to the impact of the treatment on the patient and the society (e.g. unmet need). Subsequently each one of the variables were coded with specific code-name in order to obtain several categorical and continuous variables for the analysis.

Table 2- Variables captured in the report

GENERAL INFORMATION	
AGENCY	
MOLECULE NAME	
BRAND NAME	
MANUFACTURER	
DISEASE AREA	ATC CODE
INDICATION(S) UNDER REVIEW (EMA WORDING)	
EMA MARKETING AUTHORISATION DATE (TGA-registered PBAC) (NOC date CADTH)	Always keep the date European format
SCHEME OF APPROVAL	1=STANDARD; 2=CONDITIONAL MARKETING AUTHORISATION [CMA]/[EMA]; 3=AUTHORISATION UNDER EXCEPTIONAL CIRCUMSTANCES [AEC]/[EMA]; 4=ACCELERATED ASSESSMENT / [EMA]
ORPHAN DESIGNATION (YES or NO)	
FDA MARKETING AUTHORISATION DATE	Always keep the date European format
SCHEME OF FDA APPROVAL	1=STANDARD; 2=FAST TRACK DESIGNATION; 3=BREAKTHROUGH THERAPY DESIGNATION; 4=ACCELERATED APPROVAL; or 5=PRIORITY REVIEW DESIGNATION
DATE OF DECISION OF HTA RACCOMANDATION	
IS THIS A RE-EVALUATION OR UPDATE? IF YES, INCLUDE BRIEF DETAILS	
DECISION/RECOMMENDATION:	1=L (LIST); 2=LWC (LIST WITH CRITERIA); 3=DNL (DO NOT LIST); 4=NS (NOT SUBMITTED); 5=HAS; 6= IQWIG; 7=DEFERRED; 8=ADVICE OR HEALTH ECONOMIC REPORT
ADDED BENEFIT- SMR/LEVEL OF PROOF	IQWIG: Major / erheblich = Level 1; Significant/beträchtlichen= Level 2; Small/Minor/ geringen= Level 3; Unquantifiable/nicht quantifizierbar = Level 4; None (not proven)/ nicht belegt= Level 5; Lower/ geringer= Level 6
ADDED BENEFIT- ASMR/PROOF OF BENEFIT	IQWIG: proof/Beleg; Hinweis/ Indication; Anhaltspunkt/ Hint
CLINICAL RESTRICTIONS BASED ON HTA AGENCY RECOMMENDATION	Subgroups and clinical pathways; Prescribing status; Therapeutic category
ECONOMIC RESTRICTIONS BASED ON HTA AGENCY RECOMMENDATIONS	Managed Entry Agreements Improvements in the cost-effectiveness ratio; Price reduction was applied; Therapeutic category; Limited reimbursement; Dose/treatment cycle
HTA REPORT REFERENCE (if applicable)	

SOURCE/WEBLINK	
MANAGED ENTRY AGREEMENTS	
Broader type of MEA	financial based, outcomes based, combination
Start/End year of MEA	end date not always available/ ongoing scheme
Tool(s) used to implement MEA	i.e. Pay by Results, PVA, Outcome guarantee, Discount, Cost sharing, Rebate, Study continuation, Free stock, Tiered budget cap, Utilisation cap, Cost capping, Disease management, Coverage with evidence development, Monitoring registry etc.
Objective/Rationale	To address budget impact, Reduce uncertainty concerning cost-effectiveness Evidence regarding decision uncertainty, Ensure compliance to the restricted reimbursement Utilisation in real life etc.
Uncertainties leading to RSA (where available)	i.e. "The PBAC considered that there was some uncertainty in utilisation numbers particularly in the light of patients potentially accessing brentuximab vedotin in more than one line of therapy, and noted the sponsor's willingness to negotiate with the Department on the proposed Risk-Share Arrangement. However, the Committee noted that the per vial cost of brentuximab beyond each Cap as presented in the submission would need to be further reduced, in order to appropriately manage these uncertainties for the Commonwealth.", "The county councils and the company have agreed a side agreement with risk sharing to manage the uncertainties that exist regarding the increased survival after progression."
CLINICAL EVIDENCE	
Trial name	
Pivotal trial? (Yes/No)	Pivotal trial is considered the Trial submitted to the regulatory agency (If it is not stated in the HTA submission it is necessary to check the EPAR report (Europe, Canada and Australia should have the same pivotal trial-in any case we are going to use EMA as reference)
Study Type	1= interventional study; 2= observational study; 3= indirect comparison
Type of observational study	1=Case-crossover, 2=Cross-sectional, 3=Case-control, 4=Retrospective cohort, 5=prospective cohort and 6=not applicable
Allocation	Randomized=1 Non-randomized=2 Not applicable=3
Trial Identifier (usually NCT number from clinicaltrials.gov e.g. NCT01871649)	
Intervention model	1=single group assignment, 2=parallel assignment, 3= cross-over assignment, and 4=factorial assignment
Used to inform Economic Model? (Yes or No)	
Trial Phase	1=Phase III; 2= Phase II 3=Phase IIa; 4= Phase IIb; 5=Multi-stage; 6=Phase IV; 7=Phase I; 8=N/A
Arm	1=Single Arm Trial; 2=Double Arm Trial; 3=Multi-Arm Trial
Masking	1=single blind; 2=double blind; 3=open label or unblinded
Sample size in the trial	
Length of trial	In month
Length of the follow-up	In month
Number of comparators	

Type of comparator	Active, Placebo, No intervention (for non-comparative), Sham.
Name Comparator(s)	
Type of analysis	Mitt (randomized) ITT (randomized) Full Analysis Set (Non-randomized) or evaluable population (Non-randomized)
PRIMARY ENDPOINT OUTCOMES	
Actual Primary endpoint(s)	
Is primary endpoint: 1=Surrogate Endpoint or 2=Clinical Endpoint?	
Results of the primary endpoints	
SECONDARY OUTCOMES	
Actual Secondary Endpoint(s)	
Results of secondary endpoints	
Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQoL) Measurement	
Results of HRQoL	
SAFETY PROFILE	
All Adverse Events of trial in %	%
Serious Adverse Events %	%
Withdrawal Rates due to adverse events and relevant info	%
Death (%)	%
SECONDARY EVIDENCE INCLUDED	
Secondary trial(s)	
Used to inform what?	Safety, clinical effectiveness, economic model
SUBGROUPS	
Is there a sub-group analysis performed that stemmed to a restriction?	yes/no
If yes please state the name of the subgroup	
if yes please state the subgroup analysis results	
ECONOMIC EVIDENCE	
Type of economic analysis	1=cost of illness; 2=cost minimisation; 3=cost effectiveness; 4=cost consequence; 5=cost utility; 6=cost benefit
Model Structure (e.g. partitioned model, Markov etc)	

Model perspective	
Model horizon	
Comparator(s)	
ICER Submitted by the manufacturer	
ICER accepted by payer	
Cost savings	Applicable only for cost-minimization and other cost analysis NOT for cost-utility
Final cost (cost-comparison)	Applicable only for cost-minimization and other cost analysis NOT for cost-utility
Submission price	
Secondary evidence included	Only if they are used only in the economic case
Budget impact performed?	
CLINICAL UNCERTAINTIES	
Clinical benefit	Limited or poor clinical benefit stemming from the clinical evidence. It MAY comprises: 1) Modest or low clinical benefit from trial 2) The response of the pharmaceutical varied from study to study 3) The response of the pharmaceutical is effective only in a subpopulation 4) The response of the pharmaceutical is not statistically significant compared with the comparator
Clinical evidence	It MAY comprises: 1) Lack of comparative clinical data 2) Unsuitable data (SPECIFIC TO IQWiG) 3) Lack of long-term evidence 4) Lack of safety data
Study design	It MAY comprises: 1) Limitation in trial design leading to confounding in the clinical benefit (e.g. cross-over) 2) Study blinding unsuitable 3) Sample size (too small) 4) Use of surrogate endpoints vs clinical endpoints
Indirect comparison	It MAY comprises 1) indirect comparison not well designed 2) population across different studies non-comparable 3) Statistical analysis performed not suitable (e.g. butcher vs Bayesian model)
Comparator	It MAY comprises: 1) comparator not marketed in the country 2) comparator not suitable because not used in the clinical practice 3) comparator is not the standard of care in the country 4) Placebo-controlled trial
Generalizability of population	It MAY comprises: 1) the trial population is not generalizable to the country population due to ethnicity/baseline characteristics and prevalence 2) The trial population is not included/underrepresented the population of the indication under review 3) Only a subgroup of the trial is considered suitable for the indication
Clinical practice	It MAY comprises: 1) differences in the pathway in the clinical practice of the country 2) differences in the administration and dose in comparison with the standard of care 3) When the treatment criteria (e.g. baseline of the patients for starting the treatment) differed between the study and clinical practice 4) A pharmaceutical is thought to have limited used in the study country. (e.g. clinical pathways of PBAC)

Adverse events	It MAY comprises: 1) Substantial number of patients discontinuing the therapies due to adverse events 2) EPAR with too many safety issues in comparison with current treatment used. 3) There are notable adverse events that would lead to specific monitoring
ECONOMIC UNCERTAINTIES	
Modelling	It MAY comprises: 1) the modelling used is not suitable 2) the use of curves is not appropriate 3) extrapolations method is not appropriate 4) misrepresentation of the population under review or of some specific subgroup 5) any computational errors
Model type	It MAY comprises: 1) The use of a certain model (e.g. CMA vs CUA) is not suitable for the analysis
Clinical evidence	It MAY comprises: 1) the clinical evidence used in the economic model is not suitable due to limitations such as sample size, poor trial design etc. 2) there is a lack of evidence following the nature progression of the disease (e.g. lack of long-term evidence) 3) the indirect comparison used to populate the clinical input of the model is poorly design/with an unsuitable design
Comparator	It MAY comprises: 1) comparator used in the economic model is not marketed in the country 2) comparator used in the economic model is not suitable because not used in the clinical practice 3) comparator used in the economic model is not the standard of care in the country
Cost	It MAY comprises: 1) some costs included in the model are too low or too high 2) the model does not include specific cost that would lead to a over-estimation or under-estimation of the cost-effectiveness such as administration cost or wastage
Utilities	It MAY comprises: 1) the utility values used in the model are not suitable leading to over-estimation or under-estimation of the ICER 2) the utility source is not suitable/ or the measured was not appropriate
Cost-effectiveness	It MAY comprises: 1) cost-effectiveness over the threshold 2) ICER too high even after testing with sensitivity analysis or re-evaluation carried out by manufacturer/HTA body/ external reviewers
Sensitivity analysis	It MAY comprises: any issues around the sensitivity analysis performed by the manufacturer or by the HTA body experts
SOCIAL VALUE JUDGEMENTS	
Rarity	In the HTA guidelines is explicitly included a special status for orphan or ultra-orphan drugs.
Severity	Disease severity and its impact on the patients and the caregivers
Unmet need	Unmet need for new treatments was recognised
Innovation	The treatment is innovative or have a new innovative mechanism of action.
Short life expectancy	
Administration advantage	Refers to the route and the frequency of administration of the treatment
Wider impact on society	There is a substantial impact on the organization of care or the wider society.
Impact on QoL	There is a positive or a negative impact on quality of life

Ethic/equality	Considerations if the drug will lead to Inequalities in accessing health care for groups more likely to be in a grater risk (e.g determinants of risk could be sex, race, disability and socioeconomic status). The drug should be fair and consistent allocated across sub-groups.
Safety profile	The safety profile of current treatments is affecting heavily patients that would prefer to be able to have more options with a different Safety profile (It is not limiting to a better safety profile)
Special demographic populations	Some features of the population are considered such as age, pregnant women.
Emotional burden	Refers to the nature of the disease and its impact on the patient and his/her surroundings' quality of lives and the caregivers quality of lives (e.g. anxiety from the disease leading to social stigma).
Functional burden	Refers to the ability of the patients and their families/caregivers to perform in autonomy everyday life activities, the ability of the patients to work and be normal jobs activities
Special considerations	Set of considerations explicitly considered in the HTA country that are consistently used to perform decision. (e.g Human dignity principle or the ensemble of end of life criteria)

Results

In this section we provide a short descriptive analysis of some of the key sample characteristics. The objective is not to showcase results in any meaningful way, but, rather, to describe in brief some of the key features of the sample, a summary of descriptive statistics followed by a more detailed presentation of trends across key macro-areas captured by our variables namely, outcomes, clinical and economic evidence, uncertainties and social value judgements (SVJs). The next stage of our research will include the development of an econometric model based on these macro areas and variables, aiming to capture the dimensions of value with an impact on the HTA outcomes.

4.1. Selected sample

Initially, 2,772 HTA reports were identified and compiled in an Excel spreadsheet for selection. From this sample, 1,568 reports were excluded because they were not fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria and 397 common pharmaceutical-indication pairs were identified. Applying all our exclusion and inclusion criteria and matching the number of marketed medicines per disease area, we obtained a total of 205 drug indication pairs.

Figure 2- First round of selection

In the second round of selection (**Error! Reference source not found.**), 120 additional reports were identified comprising 46 drug indication pairs. Applying all the exclusion and inclusion criteria, we obtained a total of 10 drug indication pairs to add to the sample.

Figure 3 - Second round of selection

In order to maximize the representativeness of our sample, we included the same proportion of medicines approved by EMA by ATC code in our sample. Figure 4 shows the proportion of drugs by ATC code marketed in European Union and the proportion of drugs by ATC code in our sample.

Figure 4 - EMA Marketing authorization by ATC code VS Sample selected by ATC code

Looking at the different regulatory pathways underwent by the medicines included in our sample, 76% of the medicines underwent a standard pathway to grant the Marketing Authorization, 17% were granted an orphan status by EMA whereas 7% underwent special pathways such as conditional marketing authorization (6%) and exceptional circumstance (1%).

Figure 5 - EMA marketing authorization pathways distribution in the sample

4.2. Summary table of descriptive statistics

Table 3 and Table 3 show the descriptive statistics of the variables selected for the model. From these results HAS (France) and IQWIG (Germany) were excluded due to their different criteria in assessing the clinical benefit of medicine.

Table 3– Outcomes across the sample

HTA/funding outcome including not assessed and other outcomes ¹						
Outcome type (L/LWC/DNL)	List	List With Criteria	Do Not List	Not assessed/Not submitted	Other	Total
N (% of total)	137 (9%)	744 (50%)	167 (11%)	408 (27%)	42 (3%)	1498 (100%)

¹ all the results presented are not comprising HAS (France) and IQWIG (Germany) due to a different system of evaluation of the clinical benefit.

Overall, excluding the not assessed and the other type of submission, our results show that the main outcome across the entire sample was Listed with constraint (71%) followed by Do not list (16%) and List (13%). In 21% of the cases the decision were taken after a first rejection, meaning that the access for patients were delayed.

Looking at the quality of evidence, our results show that the preferred type of endpoints on which the decision were relying upon was surrogate (60%, 630).

For uncertainties and social value judgements two index were created. Looking at the index for uncertainties, the decisions were categorized in the ones with more than 10 uncertainties and the ones with less than 10 uncertainties raised by each HTA body. This was based on the assumption that a higher number of uncertainties would be present when lower quality of evidence was submitted, leading, eventually, to negative results. However, our results show that HTA bodies tend to raise less than 10 uncertainties per decision and only in 58 cases a high number of uncertainties were related to a negative outcome whereas most of decision had less than 10 uncertainties. This shows that most likely uncertainties have different weights. (e.g. clinical benefit vs lack of long-term clinical data)

For the social value judgments, the index was created on the number of SVJs mentioned in each report. They were categorized as high presence in the ones with more than seven SVJs and as moderate when there was less than seven SVJs.

Our results show that most of the decisions (716, 68%) were taken with a low number of SVJs involved and there was no clear association between the number of SVJs considered by the HTA body and a certain outcome.

Table 4- Excerpt of sample characteristics

HTA/funding outcome including not assessed and other outcomes				
Outcome type (L/LWC/DNL)	List	List with Criteria	Do Not List	Total
N (% of total)	137 (13%)	744 (71%)	167 (16%)	1048 (100%)
Country (Agency)				
Canada (CADTH)	8 (6%)	157 (21%)	30 (18%)	195 (19%)
England (NICE)	12 (9%)	127 (17%)	9 (5%)	148 (14%)
Australia (PBAC)	1 (1%)	146 (20%)	30 (18%)	177 (17%)
Scotland (SMC)	43 (31%)	132 (18%)	16 (10%)	191 (18%)
Sweden (TLV)	55	82	10	147

	(40%)	(11%)	(6%)	(14%)
Quebec (INESSS)	18 (13%)	89 (12%)	62 (37%)	170 (16%)
Ontario	0 (0%)	11 (1%)	10 (6%)	21 (2%)
Primary endpoint (excluding France and Germany)				
Surrogate	49 (36%)	475 (64%)	105 (63%)	630 (60%)
Clinical	25 (18%)	79 (11%)	34 (20%)	138 (13%)
Both	35 (26%)	43 (6%)	8 (5%)	86 (8%)
Not applicable	28 (20%)	147 (20%)	20 (12%)	195 (19%)
Prior rejection by HTA				
No	127 (93%)	574 (77%)	125 (75%)	826 (79%)
Yes	10 (7%)	170 (23%)	42 (25%)	222 (21%)
Clinical and economic uncertainty				
U_index _{Moderate} ≤ 10	114 (83%)	491 (66%)	109 (65%)	714 (68%)
U_index _{High} ≥ 10	23 (17%)	253 (34%)	58 (35%)	334 (32%)
Social Value Judgement index				
SVJ _{Moderate} ≤ 6	111 (81%)	491 (66%)	114 (68%)	716 (68%)
SVJ _{High} ≥ 7	26 (19%)	253 (34%)	53 (32%)	332 (32%)
Days from MA to HTA/funding decision				
Mean (SD)	638.2 (482.6)	770.6 (665.9)	548.5 (475.1)	726.2 (636.6)
Min	63	24	1	1
Max	1,234	2,763	1,603	2,763

Note: ¹ all the results presented are not comprising HAS (France) and IQWiG (Germany) due to a different system of evaluation of the clinical benefit.

1.3. HTA Outcomes

As shown in Figure 6, most decisions were listed with restrictions (LWC, 50%) followed by rejections (11%) and full listing (L) 9% of the decisions. In 27% of the cases, the drug was either not considered by the HTA body or a dossier was not submitted by the manufacturer. In the remaining 3% of cases,

a different type of evaluation was conducted such as a multiple technology assessment (MTA) or a health economic report.

Figure 6 - Outcomes across the sample (n=1498)

Note: L= listed; LWC: Listed with restrictions; DNL: Do not list; NS: not submitted/not assessed. Excluding IQWIG and HAS due to a different categorization of the outcomes based on level of proof and added benefit.

As shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**, the outcomes at agency level are reflecting the overall trend with most of the agencies recommending the drugs with restrictions. Interestingly, Ontario did not assess or did not receive a manufacturer submission for most of the medicine (183 out of 214 medicine).

Table 5- HTA outcomes by agency

. tab AGENCY DECISIONRECOMMENDATION1LLI

AGENCY	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Total
CADTH/pCODR	16	8	157	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	214
HAS	10	0	0	0	0	204	0	0	0	0	0	214
INESSS	42	18	89	62	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	214
IQWiG	46	0	0	0	0	0	148	0	20	0	0	214
NICE	62	12	127	9	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	214
Ontario	192	0	11	10	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	214
PBAC	37	1	138	30	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	214
SMC	6	43	132	16	16	0	0	0	0	0	1	214
TLV	37	55	82	10	0	0	0	0	27	2	1	214
Total	448	137	736	167	16	204	148	8	48	6	8	1,926

Note: 1=L (LIST); 2=LWC (LIST WITH CRITERIA); 3=DNL (DO NOT LIST); 4=NS (NOT SUBMITTED); 5=HAS; 6= IQWiG; 7=DEFERRED; 8=ADVICE OR HEALTH ECONOMIC REPORT; 9=MTA 10= withdrawn, 0=not assessed).

CADTH: Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health; HAS: Haute Autorité de Santé; IQWiG: Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Healthcare; INESSS: Institute National d'Excellence en Santé et en Services Sociaux, ; NICE: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence; SMC: Scottish Medicines Consortium; pCODR: pan-Canadian Oncology Drug Review; PBAC: Pharmaceutical Benefits Advisory Committee; TLV: (Dental and Pharmaceutical Benefits Agen

1.4. Clinical evidence

Across the entire sample a total of 3528 clinical studies were identified. 85% of these studies were interventional followed by 13% of indirect comparisons and 3% of observational studies. Across the study countries, this trend was confirmed (Figure 7), with most of the agencies considering mostly interventional studies as main studies to evaluate the clinical benefit. Interestingly, the use of indirect comparison varied substantially, with PBAC considering an indirect comparison in 26% of the reports followed by NICE (18%) and IQWiG (16%) and Ontario not considering any.

The use of observational studies has been constantly low across the agencies with only HAS considering in their evaluation 31 observational studies (5% of the entire number of studies considered by HAS).

Figure 7 - Clinical evidence

Note: CADTH: Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health; HAS: Haute Autorité de Santé; IQWiG: Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Healthcare; INESSS: Institute National d'Excellence en Santé et en Services Sociaux, : NICE: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence; SMC: Scottish Medicines Consortium; pCODR: pan-Canadian Oncology Drug Review; PBAC: Pharmaceutical Benefits Advisory Committee; TLV: (Dental and Pharmaceutical Benefits Agency)

Confirming previous studies, most of the interventional studies were phase III (86% n= 2500) followed by studies phase II (11% n=310), Phase I (2% n=50) and Phase IV (1%, n=21).

Looking at quality of the evidence two main features were highlighted by our results. Firstly, the primary endpoints evaluated in the interventional trials, 69% of the cases the main primary endpoint was a surrogate one and only in 31% of the cases the clinical benefit rely on clinical endpoints. Secondly, 54% of the interventional trials used placebo as main comparator and 12% were not comparative.

1.5. Economic evidence

Economic evaluations were conducted by all the countries studied except IQWIG. We identified 974 economic studies across the 8 agencies performing economic evaluations. The most used economic model was cost-utility (69% n= 719 model) followed by cost-minimization (22% n=228) and cost-consequences (2% n=17).

Figure 8 - Economic models

Note: CADTH: Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health; HAS: Haute Autorité de Santé; IQWIG: Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Healthcare; INESSS: Institut National d'Excellence en Santé et en Services Sociaux, : NICE: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence; SMC: Scottish Medicines Consortium; pCODR: pan-Canadian Oncology Drug Review; PBAC: Pharmaceutical Benefits Advisory Committee; TLV: (Dental and Pharmaceutical Benefits Agency).

1.6. Uncertainties

In conducting their appraisals, HTA bodies make scientific value judgements in order to evaluate the quality and acceptability of clinical and economic evidence (e.g. acceptability of placebo-controlled trials or surrogate outcomes over clinical outcomes). The concerns raised and addressed by HTA bodies are commonly called uncertainties.

In total, we identified 8,132 uncertainties, 5,186 (64%) of which were raised around the clinical evidence presented and 2,946 (36%) raised on the economic model submitted by the manufacturer.

In our sample, the most frequently raised group of clinical uncertainties was around clinical benefit (27% of all uncertainties, n= 1,378 cases) followed by concerns on clinical trial design (20% of all uncertainties, n=1,056 cases) and the lack of evidence (15%, n=791)

The most frequently raised group of uncertainties around the economic evidence was related to the modelling technique used by the manufacturer (31%, n= 907), followed by the overall uncertainty in the cost-effectiveness results (21%, n= 625) and the clinical evidence used as input in the economic model (17%, n=513).

To fully comprehend the impact of these scientific value judgements in the final decision, we recorded (a) whether and (b) how often these uncertainties are overcome in HTA submissions, based on how HTA agencies commented on them.

As shown in Figure 9, even if raised, most of the uncertainties were not overcome at HTA level, with only concerns around the type of economic model selected by the manufacturer for the conduct of economic analysis being overcome in the majority of the cases (58%, n= 32 out of 55 cases). In total only 2,585 uncertainties (32%) were openly overcome with different tools such as patient input or the generation of further evidence from the manufacturer, whereas 5,547 (69%) were not clearly overcome or addressed in any way.

Figure 9 – Dealing with clinical and economic uncertainties in the context of HTA

1.7. Social value judgements (SVJs)

During the process of decision-making, HTA bodies perform also other type of judgements that are not strictly scientific but concerns all those elements affecting the patients, the carer and the society as whole. These are called Social value judgments (SVJs).

Social value judgements are the ensemble concepts of fairness and equity that should be included when evaluating the value of new technologies [27, 28]. They can pertain to values underpinning the processes of HTA per se, such as for instance transparency and accountability in conducting HTA assessments, or contents value related to the implications of introducing the treatments for the patients and the whole society[28].

In our sample, we identified 3773 social value judgements made by HTA bodies across the sample. The most social value judgement made was unmet need (21%, n=787) followed by severity of the disease (12%, n=439) and Administration advantage (10%, n= 359).

76% (n= 2876) of the SVJs made by the HTA body had a positive effect on the decision, 17% (n=623) had a negative effect and only 7% (n=274) did not have an effect or their effect was not clear.

Figure 10 shown that this trend was maintained at category level with most of the SVJs having positive effect on the decisions. The only exception can be seen in the judgements made around the wider impact on society that a medicine can have with 30% of the cases with a negative impact and 46% with a positive one.

Figure 10- Effect of SVJs per category

Conclusions

The sample will be analysed with different econometric modelling techniques in order to study the correlations between the different determinants of HTA and the recommendations outcomes. To that end, two manuscripts are appended in the remainder of this report:

- (a) Algorithms and heuristics of health technology assessments: A post hoc analysis of factors associated with funding decisions for new drugs across eight OECD countries; and
- (b) Health Technology Assessment and funding policies for Orphan Medicinal Products: Failing, Flawed or Fair?

PART B – Algorithms and heuristics of health technology assessments: A post hoc analysis of factors associated with funding decisions for new drugs across eight OECD countries

Algorithms and heuristics of Health Technology Assessments: A post hoc analysis of factors associated with funding decisions for new drugs across seven OECD countries

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Funding acknowledgement: The study is undertaken in the context of the IMPACT-HTA project, which has received funding from the European Commission's Horizon 2020 research programme (Grant Agreement Number: 779312). The views presented in the paper are those of the authors and do not reflect the views of the European Commission.

Acknowledgements: We are grateful to comments received by a number of colleagues in earlier versions of the paper: Alistair McGuire, Jaime Caro, Jaime Espin, Joan Rovira, Michael Drummond, Douglas Lundin, Americo Cicchetti, Jean Mossman, Karen Facey, Sean Sullivan, Mackenzie Mills, Olina Efthymiadou, Anwen Zhang, Maia Laynou-Pujolras and Anna-Maria Fontrier. All outstanding errors are our own.

Abstract

Context: The paper analyses the factors shaping market entry of new drugs and explaining coverage decisions and similarities or differences across countries and therapeutic categories; identifies factors influencing time-to-market; and evaluates whether technical efficiency drives funding decisions.

Objective: The paper identifies and analyses the factors influencing time-to-market; and provides a post hoc analysis of factors associated with positive and negative coverage decisions, whether positively or negatively.

Methods: Descriptive and econometric analysis of a sample of 219 drug-indication pairs, across seven OECD countries, resulting in a sample of 1,415 observations over the 2009-2018 period. Econometric analysis was based on a two-stage least square approach, analysing factors associated with time to entry (1st stage) and factors associated with coverage decisions (2nd stage).

Findings: Contrary to conventional belief, we find that time to market always exceeds one year post-licensing due to HTA assessment, while accelerated access pathways slow down access to market instead of accelerating it. Thirteen percent of all drugs are rejected due to uncertainty or inadequate health benefits. Two thirds of HTA decisions have a clinical restriction implying availability to a patient sub-group only. Approximately 50% of new drugs are subject to risk-sharing agreements suggesting that their cost is too high relative to their benefit. Although efficiency is an important predictor of coverage, it is increasingly considered confidentially between HTAs and drug manufacturers. Finally, several value dimensions beyond costs and effects shape (are positively associated with) funding decisions, such as severity, unmet need and ‘innovation advantage’.

Conclusions: Important implications for health and public policy relate to: (a) the relationship between two forms of regulation (drug licensing and HTA;); (b) the criteria used by HTA agencies and their importance for funding decisions; (c) the link between efficiency, affordability and equity; (d) the increasing role of risk mitigation strategies to account for uncertainty; and (e) the broader implications of funding decisions for innovation, industrial policy and economic development.

Keywords: Health Technology Assessment; Health policy; Resource allocation; Innovation; Cost-effectiveness; Affordability; Efficiency; Drug pricing; Uncertainty; Social value judgements; Public policy.

JEL classifications: I10, I11, I15, I18.

Background

The introduction of new and costly pharmaceutical technologies, combined with moderate health gains, has sparked extensive debate on the benefits accruing to patients and health care systems, how these benefits should be assessed and what evaluation criteria should be informing coverage decisions [Cohen 2017; Linley and Hughes, 2013]. This debate has intensified in light of increased pressure on healthcare budgets and fiscal sustainability concerns, fuelled in part by steady growth in the demand for health care and the availability of expensive new technologies [Luce et al, 2010; OECD, 2015]. Although health technology assessment (HTA) has been used extensively over the past fifteen years to assess value of new therapies and inform decision-making, studies have identified variations in HTA agency structures [Hyry et al, 2014; Kaitin 2010; Shihi et al 2013], guidelines for conducting HTA [Chalkidou 2009, Keeney 2013], and the evaluation of evidence [Drummond et al 2009; Nicod and Kanavos, 2016; Annemans et al 2017; Angelis et al 2018].

A growing number of studies have emphasized the need to homogenize HTA processes across countries [Cohen 2017; Prasad, 2015; Naci et al. 2012], including a discussion around outcome metrics, such as the QALY [Davis et al, 2009; Neumann et al, 2018; Logviss et al 2018]. Acknowledging the differences in healthcare organization and provision across countries, different studies have suggested that there is ground for standardization in clinical and economic evaluation methods in order to align these, while still allowing for adaptation at country level based on need [Luce et al 2010, Naci et al. 2012; Halsam et al, 2018; Gyawali, Hay and Kesselheim, 2018; Kanavos et al, 2019; European Commission, 2018].

It is still open to debate as to which elements capturing the value of new pharmaceuticals should be included in clinical and economic evaluations [Annemans et al, 2017; Ferrario et al 2017; Kanavos et al 2017; Bouvy et al, 2018; Neumann et al 2018]. Different studies have highlighted that the elements capturing the broader value of a technology and its impact at societal level, should include

dimensions such as severity of the disease, innovation, nature of the intervention, and whether the intervention has an administration advantage in comparison with current treatment, among others [Hyry et al 2014, Garrison et al, 2017; Neumann et al 2018; Lakdawalla et al, 2018; Angelis and Kanavos, 2019].

Previous research investigated the effect of different factors on HTA coverage decisions in the English [Devlin and Parkin, 2004; Dakin et al, 2006; Dakin et al, 2014; Cerri et al, 2014], Welsh [Linley and Hughes, 2012], Scottish [Mshelia et al, 2013] and Australian [Harris et al, 2008] contexts by means of quantitative analysis. By considering coverage decisions as binary, ‘yes’ or ‘no’ options, this research highlighted the importance of cost-effectiveness as a key driver of HTA decisions together with uncertainty and burden of disease [Devlin and Parkin, 2004], although other factors have been highlighted as being important, notably clinical evidence, technology type, patient group submissions [Dakin et al, 2006], statistical superiority of primary endpoint in clinical trials, the year of appraisal, the number of pharmaceuticals appraised within the same appraisal [Cerri et al, 2014], uncertainty, severity and availability of other therapies [Tappenden, 2007].

Diverging coverage decisions across settings for several new medicines, related to diseases often associated with high morbidity and mortality have also sparked debate on the criteria informing decision-making and the importance of contextual considerations [Clement 2009; Faden 2009; Nicod and Kanavos, 2012; Angelis et al, 2019]. Apart from differences in evidence assessment and interpretation, differences in HTA outcomes may be explained by broader, contextual considerations, known as social value judgements, which have been raised and discussed methodologically and in a series of case studies across therapy areas reflecting stakeholder views [Hofmann et al 2014] or in the context of orphan drugs [Nicod and Kanavos, 2016; Nicod et al, 2017]. However, the likely impact of social value judgements on HTA coverage recommendations has not been tested statistically in the presence of other possible parameters that influence such coverage, except for one case and in the context of severity [Tappenden, 2007]. Part of this research distinguished between HTA outcomes

not as binary, ‘yes’ or ‘no’ decisions, but as categorical, namely, ‘yes’ (unconditional), ‘yes with restrictions’ (conditional) and ‘no’ (rejection) and found significant differences in individual case studies in perceptions of value between unconditional and conditional recommendations. Finally, there is some evidence that regulatory outcomes, such as conditional approval, have an impact on HTA decisions [Lipska et al, 2015; Vreman et al 2019], but this has not been seen in association with other factors influencing coverage.

Overall, a number of studies have analysed HTA coverage decisions [Kleijnen, 2016; Lipska et al, 2015; Nicod & Kanavos, 2012; Nicod & Kanavos, 2016; Nicod & Kanavos, 2016b; Nicod, 2017; Spinner et al, 2013; Allen et al, 2017; Vreman et al, 2019; Akehurst et al 2017; Schmitz et al, 2016], by focusing on specific factors, contexts or time. In this is paper we build on all previous literature to adopt a comparative, quantitative approach to study the factors associated with HTA coverage decisions by analysing whether key regulatory, clinical, economic, product or therapeutic area-specific variables, funding modalities and broader considerations beyond costs and effects, have any influence on the final recommendation across a number of countries implementing HTA, by drawing on a panel of medicines that had received marketing authorisation between 2009 and 2018.

Our study adds to and extends the literature on HTA coverage recommendations and the effect different factors may have on it in three ways: first, we propose a comprehensive analytical approach for the factors that may be associated with positive or restricted HTA recommendations by taking into account dimensions of benefit beyond costs and effects and a number of exogenous parameters; second, we adopt a comparative perspective by analysing HTA coverage recommendations across seven countries with well-established HTA systems and using a large sample of drug-indication pairs and their associated HTA outcomes over a period of time; this enables us to capture similarities and differences across settings as well as incorporate the time dimension in the analysis; and, third, our modelling approach allows us to identify the factors that are associated with positive HTA recommendations and analyse how these may differ from positive but restricted recommendations.

Section 2, proposes a conceptual framework to analyse HTA coverage recommendations; section 3, outlines the methodology that is implemented to analyse these across a number of settings. In section 4, the main results of our analysis are presented, while, section 5 discusses the results and the associated policy implications. Finally, section 6 draws the main conclusions.

2. Conceptual framework

The inclusion of a new medicine in the list of products covered by a health care system is characterized by two distinct phases: first, the market entry and the associated speed with which market entry occurs once regulatory and coverage decision-related requirements have been met; and, second, market penetration, notably the outcome of an assessment by a competent authority in order to assess the new medicine's value in terms of its capacity to deliver (therapeutic) benefit.

Obtaining marketing authorization (MA) from a regulatory authority is a clear pre-requisite for medicinal products to be marketed. Across health care systems, achieving coverage implies a positive outcome following an evaluation by a competent authority, including HTA agencies or reimbursement committees in which a product's benefits (and costs) are deemed acceptable based on an assessment from a health care system perspective. Conceptually, following MA, the speed of market entry, i.e. the time between receiving MA and coverage recommendation by an HTA agency is dependent on a number of criteria: the first is the extent to which a drug fulfils certain pre-conditions which may justify early market entry. Accelerated approval pathways (AAPs), such as conditional marketing authorization, in principle provide a signal to HTA agencies that drugs approved through these pathways may only require expedited appraisal or should be subject to different levels of robustness when assessed. As such, medicines approved via AAPs could receive funding recommendations faster compared with non-AAP medicines. A second criterion relates to

the type of medicine, whether its development has benefited from specific incentives or it has a priority status because of its asserted “therapeutic promise”; for example, orphan designation status, suggests that lower thresholds of evidence may be accepted at licensing level and, in principle, signals to HTA agencies that orphan medicines could be considered more favourably. Similarly, the type of therapy and its purpose, notably curative, preventive or offering symptomatic relief, may carry important coverage implications. A third criterion is the type of funding modality that may be agreed upon following the completion of the assessment process. If significant uncertainties relating to clinical benefit have been identified, the possibility to conclude a risk mitigation strategy may act as a decision modifier and a product can be offered coverage or coverage may occur faster, instead of being rejected. Restrictions of use may shape the nature and extent of coverage, either on clinical (e.g. use in certain sub-populations only, where evidence on benefit is strongest), or financial grounds (e.g. a financial arrangement based on risk-sharing (RSA)), or inclusion into a special funding programme other than RSA (which can be restrictive in terms of the number of patients accessing the drug, such as the Cancer Drugs Fund (CDF) in England [NHSE, 2016], or the Exceptional Access Programme (EAP) in Ontario [OMH, 2020]). Evidence shows that clinical and economic restrictions facilitate and accelerate coverage by limiting budget impact, improving cost-effectiveness, or both [Lakdawalla et al, 2018; Logviss et al, 2018; Davis et al, 2009; Lewis and Warlow, 2004]. A fourth criterion relates to the evidence supporting the HTA submission process, such as, the trial phase, the extent to which a direct comparator has been used and whether a clinical, rather than a surrogate, endpoint supported claims on clinical benefit. Concerns about trial designs, type of comparator and the magnitude of clinical benefit can delay considerably positive funding recommendations and may lead to rejections. Finally, if a submission has received a rejection already, a re-submission is more likely to be delayed in receiving a positive recommendation. The above are captured in equation (1),

$$ME_{ij} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 OD_{ij} + \beta_2 MA_{ij} + \beta_3 FM_{ij} + \beta_4 RESUB_{ij} + \beta_5 EVID_j + \beta_6 Z_{ij} + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

where ME_{ij} is market entry in country i and product j , OD_{ij} is orphan designation, as a proxy for special product characteristics, MA_{ij} is the type of marketing authorization pathway the product has undergone; FM_{ij} is the funding modality, $RESUB_{ij}$ indicate whether a HTA dossier was previously rejected for product j in country i , $EVID_j$ is a vector of variables concerning the evidence that supported the HTA submission (i.e. trial phase, comparator and endpoint), Z_{ij} is a vector of country and time-specific variables and ε_i is the error term.

Market penetration, on the other hand, is contingent on the funding recommendation a new medicine will receive. The funding recommendation is the outcome of a robust assessment by HTA agencies and is shaped by a multiplicity of criteria, most of which are linked to a new medicine's perceived value; among them, are the type of medicine under consideration and how it fits into therapeutic pathways, the clinical and economic evidence and their robustness based on scientific criteria, the restrictions in the new medicine's use, evidence uncertainty, considerations capturing value dimensions beyond costs and effects, and time.

Important criteria shaping market penetration include clinical evidence and value parameters, such as clinical study type and design, which ultimately influence internal and external validity, the evidence on and the performance of the clinical benefit in terms of size, clinical meaningfulness and statistical significance and the extent to which the new drug's demonstration of clinical benefit relies on a clinical or a surrogate endpoint. Economic variables can be critical in the context of value assessment and HTA. The incremental cost effectiveness ratio (ICER), as an indicator of efficiency, underscores the additional investment required to obtain an additional unit of health gain; its acceptability on a case-by-case basis reflects national willingness-to-pay (WTP) thresholds, where they exist. Budget impact, by contrast, is an indicator of affordability. Drugs can be efficient (cost-effective) compared with the standard of care, but may not be affordable; therefore, efficiency may be a necessary but not a sufficient condition for coverage. Uncertainties, both clinical and economic, may also have an

impact on coverage recommendations. Uncertainties capture the concerns of decision-makers on assumptions and baseline characteristics of clinical trials, trial design issues, treatment discontinuation, the economic evidence submitted (e.g. model and modelling, cost and utility data, comparator issues, relationship to current clinical practice), all of which render the results uncertain and non-generalisable and, if not addressed, have a negative effect on coverage recommendations. Crucially, addressing clinical and economic uncertainties forms an important dimension in HTA in order to achieve coverage. A further set of criteria that may influence the direction of coverage recommendations is the extent to which social value judgements (SVJs) are considered; these capture elicited (e.g. human dignity and solidarity principles in Sweden; end-of-life criteria in the UK) and non-elicited considerations (e.g. emotional and financial strain on patients and their families, treatment administration advantages) beyond a new therapy’s costs and effects. SVJs may influence decision-making and factors that have been shown to have some impact, include the explicit recognition of disease severity, unmet need, and administration advantage [Annemans et al, 2017; Jadad et al, 1996; Harris et al, 2008; Dakin et al, 2015].

Consequently, the funding recommendation, F , in country i and product j , can be positive (either unrestricted or with restrictions) or negative and can be expressed as a function of a number of parameters as shown in equation (2):

$$F_{ij} = \gamma_0 + \delta_1 C_{ij} + \delta_2 D_{ij} + \delta_3 U_{ij} + \delta_4 W_{ij} + \delta_5 S_{ij} + \delta_6 Z_{ij} + v_i \quad (2)$$

Where the dependent variable, F_{ij} , is the “HTA funding recommendation” for product i in country j ; C_{ij} is a group of parameters including the drug type, D_{ij} is a vector of parameters relating to the quality of evidence supporting HTA submissions, U_{ij} relates to the impact of clinical uncertainties, W_{ij} refers to the impact of economic uncertainties, while S_{ij} captures the range of social value judgments (SVJs) that may be relevant to the product or the therapeutic indication in question; Z_{ij} is a vector of country- and time-specific variables, while v_i is the error term.

Methods

The collection and analysis of HTA data across countries was based on a multi-stage framework aiming to capture in a systematic way the key elements of HTA processes, their outcomes in terms of coverage recommendations and link these to decisions and funding arrangements. Five steps were followed in order to select the sample, define the variables and collect, validate and analyse the data.

Country selection

Countries were selected in order to include a representative sample of the different approaches adopted in HTA (e.g. health service, societal), whilst at the same time ensuring data availability and comparability across countries. A number of predefined inclusion criteria were used for country selection: (a) whether they had well-established HTA agencies and processes, (b) whether a range of decision-making criteria (clinical and/or cost effectiveness) were explicitly used, and (c) whether the HTA reports and the resulting recommendations were publicly available. A total of 7 countries and their respective HTA agencies were identified that met the inclusion criteria. The study countries were France (HAS), Scotland (SMC), England (NICE), Germany (G-BA), Canada (CADTH/pCODR) operating at federal level), Quebec (INESSS), which is following an independent path in the Canadian context, making its own decisions independently within the province) and Australia (PBAC).

Sample selection

The unit of measurement is the ‘medicine-indication’ pair, notably a product, which is meant for a specific indication. This is so because many products are increasingly used in multiple indications and different coverage arrangements may apply to each indication. We selected a representative sample of medicine-indication pairs that have undergone assessment by HTA agencies across the 7

study countries between January 1st, 2009 and June 15th, 2018. In order to select a representative sample of medicine-indication pairs that have undergone HTA assessment between January 1st, 2009 – and June 15th, 2018, across different jurisdictions and for which HTA reports and recommendations are available a two-step approach was adopted: 1) identification of all drug indication pairs assessed by selected HTA agencies over the study period, and 2) selection of representative sample of drug-indication pairs.

Upon reflection of the various HTA agencies' scope and prioritization methods, it is clear that only 5 of the 7 agencies will influence the selection process. Therefore, a number of assumptions can be made in order to simplify the selection process: (a) HAS and SMC assess all new EMA-approved products that apply for inclusion in the benefits catalogue in France and Scotland, respectively, and are, therefore, taken as reference in the selection process; (b) Canadian HTA Agencies assess all products receiving marketing authorisation from Health Canada. Therefore, only one agency (CADTH) is needed in order capture potential differences in the marketed drug-indication pair pool between Canada, Europe, and Australia.

First, websites of the selected HTA agencies (TLV, NICE, IQWiG, CADTH, PBAC), were queried in order to ensure the feasibility of data collection and to ensure that drug-indication pairs that have been commonly assessed by multiple agencies are included in the study. All publicly available HTA reports published between January 1st, 2009 and June 15th, 2018 were retrieved. Data from all HTA reports extracted were compiled in a excel spreadsheet in order to identify common drug-indication pairs across the agencies. The variables recorded were: brand name, molecule name, date of decision, the indication under review, ATC code and web link to access the report. Each HTA report was entered as a single row within the excel sheet. Entries were then organised according to molecule name. Each molecule was then reviewed and assessments not suitable for analysis were excluded. In order to ensure that there was a single recommendation outcome entry per HTA Agency for a particular drug-indication pair, the following exclusions applied: (a) Original full submissions were

excluded if superseded by a subsequent full submission; (b) In the case of a drug-indication pair recording a submission with a subsequent re-submission, if there was a decision (usually a rejection) for the first submission, followed by a re-submission, only the outcome of the re-submission was included, but the outcome of the first submission was also recorded; (c) minor submissions, consisting in amendments of existing listings that do not alter the population or cost-effectiveness; and (d) any submissions involving generic or biosimilar medicines were excluded.

For all selected drug-indication pairs, prior rejections, re-submissions or changes in restrictions were recorded in data collection in order to capture the entire decision-making process that is relevant for a selected product. Where the wording of an indication varied slightly across countries, entries were discussed internally in order to determine whether or not differences in wording (as well as the associated evidence) related to the same indication or could be different indications. Agreement was required amongst a minimum of two individuals before inclusion in the final list.

Based on the above, a sample of 219 unique drug-indication pairs was identified. The identified sample was representative of and proportional to all drug-indication pairs approved by the European Medicines Agency over the study period based on therapeutic area, captured by the ATC code. Where the sample was not representative or found to be biased in favour of a particular therapeutic area, medicine-indications would be substituted with those assessed by fewer agencies in order to produce a sample that is representative. The total sample size across the 7 study countries was n=1,415 HTA decisions.

Variables

In order to capture key elements from the HTA process, a comprehensive set of variables were extracted from each HTA report and inserted into an excel spreadsheet, enabling an understanding of likely differences in evidence across HTA bodies and differences in the assessment of drugs across

countries and allowing the identification of key commonalities and differences both, in the evidence per se (and therefore at assessment level), and in their interpretation at appraisal level. The variables were organized according to 9 macro-level headings, as follows: (a) coverage decision outcome and time to HTA coverage decision; (b) regulatory variables (regulatory approval type (e.g. standard, accelerated or parallel review) and whether a product has had a previous rejection followed by re-submission); (c) drug- and diagnosis-specific parameters, providing information on whether products have an orphan designation or are related to a cancer diagnosis; (d) economic restrictions (notably funding modalities, including risk sharing agreements or other special funding arrangements), and clinical restrictions (elaborating on population, dosing or both types of restrictions); (e) clinical evidence, summarizing key aspects of clinical evidence considered by HTA agencies, including type of evidence (Phase III vs all other), comparators (direct vs no direct), primary endpoints (whether clinical or surrogate) and quality of evidence. To capture the overall quality of clinical evidence, a composite variable based on specific concerns raised across clinical evidence was constructed, aiming to capture the occurrence of one or multiple issues relating to clinical evidence, namely: the study design, the comparator used in the study and the follow up period [Olivo et al 2008; Jadad, 1996]; (f) economic evidence, capturing information on the ICER and whether this was publicly available or confidential, or indeed other type of analysis was considered; (g) clinical uncertainties, capturing key quality of evidence concerns raised by HTA agencies around the submitted clinical evidence, for example, trial design, comparator(s), follow up period, size of clinical benefit, generalisability, and adverse events; (h) economic uncertainties and, specifically concerns raised around modelling, the model itself and key inputs informing the model such as costs and utilities; and (i) Social Value Judgements (SVJs), interpreting key elements related to the impact of the treatment on patients and society, notably, severity, unmet need, innovation (in terms of new mechanism of action) and administration advantage. The full list of variables, including definition, and type (continuous categorical or binary) is shown on Table 1.

< Table 1 about here >

Descriptive analysis

The descriptive analysis has included a number of endpoints: (a) comparison of HTA outcomes across the study countries, by distinguishing these between positive and unrestricted (denoted as “L” - List), positive but restricted (denoted as “LWC” – List With Criteria) and rejected (denoted as “DNL” – Do Not List), alongside any clinical or/and economic restrictions imposed on new medicines as part of the funding recommendation; (b) time to coverage (from MA to HTA funding recommendation) across countries and types of products and any differences between regulatory schemes; (c) the type of clinical evidence submitted and any effect this had on the HTA funding recommendation; this included phase III vs earlier phase clinical trials, therapeutic benefit in terms of clinical vs surrogate endpoints, and quality of evidence and their respective associations with funding recommendations; (d) the effect of previous rejections on final HTA funding recommendations across settings; (e) the importance of cost-effectiveness evidence in informing HTA funding recommendations; (f) the effect of clinical and economic uncertainties raised and their association with HTA coverage recommendations; and (g) the prevalence of select SVJs and their association with HTA funding recommendations.

Econometric analysis

Based on the conceptual framework our objective was to determine empirically which factors were associated with (a) time to HTA recommendations and (b) HTA coverage recommendations, respectively.

(a) Time to HTA recommendation

To assess factors influencing delay in reaching an HTA recommendation, a linear regression was considered, as shown in (3):

$$E(Y) = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_k X_k \quad (3)$$

Where the expected value of the distribution of the response variable Y , ($E(Y)$), is assumed to be a linear combination of the explanatory variables ($X_1 \dots X_k$).

Building on both equations (1) and (3), the following empirical model where the HTA_TIME_{ij} variable was regressed on regulatory as well as product-specific variables was deployed:

$$\begin{aligned} HTA_TIME_{ij} = & \alpha_0 + \beta_1 COMPARATOR_j + \beta_2 ENDPOINT_j + \beta_3 PHASEIII_j + \beta_4 ORPHAN_j + \\ & \beta_5 APPROVAL_j + \beta_6 FUDNING_{ij} + \beta_7 HTAMODEL_i + \beta_8 AGENTTYPE_i + \beta_9 GDP_i + \\ & \beta_{10} YEARHTA_i \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

Where i and j indicate the country and the product, respectively. Details on the response and explanatory variables can be found in Table 1.

(b) Factors associated with HTA recommendation

To determine what variables impacted on HTA coverage recommendations, we considered a range of options. Due to the ordinal nature of the variable of interest (negative, positive with restrictions and positive coverage recommendation), an ordered multinomial logistic approach was initially considered. However, as the present analysis focuses on how positive recommendations, either with or without restrictions, compare with negative ones, this approach was rejected. A panel data approach was also contemplated, but due to HTA coverage recommendations being unique rather than recurring events over time, this was deemed unfeasible. Finally, multinomial level modelling was explored to assess whether results of the analysis were robust to accounting for intra-agency correlation, but the computational complexities in running a multilevel multinomial unordered regression warranted this to be a robustness check rather than the principal analysis. Based on the above, a multinomial logistic regression was deployed, as shown on (5):

$$\log \left[\frac{P(Y=j)}{P(Y=0)} \right] = \alpha_j + \beta_{j1} X_1 + \beta_{j2} X_2 + \dots + \beta_{jk} X_k \quad (5)$$

Where $\log \left[\frac{P(Y=j)}{P(Y=0)} \right]$ represents the log of the odds of outcome j conditional on explanatory variables $X_1 \dots X_k$.

Following (2) and (5), the empirical model that was considered in our analysis is shown in (6):

$$\begin{aligned}
 HTA_RECOMMEND_{ij} = & \alpha_0 + \beta_1 RESUBMIT_j + \beta_2 ONCOLOGY_j * \beta_3 ORPHAN_j + \\
 & \beta_4 QUALITY_j + \beta_5 HTAMODEL_i + \beta_6 AGENTYPE_i + \beta_7 GDP_i + \beta_8 YEARHTA_i + \\
 & \beta_9 SEVERITY_{ij} + \beta_{10} INNOVATION_{ij} + \beta_{11} ADMINAD_{ij} + \beta_{12} UNEED_{ij} + \beta_{12} CLINBEN_{ij} + \\
 & \beta_{13} GENERAL_{ij} + \beta_{14} MODELLING_j + \beta_{15} INPUT_{ij} \quad (6)
 \end{aligned}$$

Where i and j indicate the country and the product, respectively. Details on the response and explanatory variables can be found in Table 1. The categories of the response variable $HTA_RECOMMEND_{ij}$ are the achievement of positive (L), positive with restrictions (LWC) or negative (DNL) HTA recommendations. No ranking was assumed between the categorical outcomes and DNL was used as the baseline group against which L and LWC were compared. Coefficients were exponentiated to relative risk ratios (RRR) for ease of interpretation. RRR lower/higher than 1 indicate a lower/higher likelihood in observing the outcome of interest versus the base outcome (e.g. LWC vs DNL). Coefficients represent deviations from a negative recommendation and positive recommendations with and without restrictions were not be directly compared. A set of product-specific variables were initially considered in an initial, reduced form model and different permutations were run to investigate whether results were sensitive to the inclusion and exclusion of explanatory variables, namely social value judgements and clinical and economic uncertainties. All variables were then included in a final model, which represents the principal model of this analysis and is shown in (6) above.

A number of interactions were explored. Interactions were tested for those variables whose effect was expected to change depending on the level of another independent variable. For example, the interaction between the type of product (oncology drug or not) and whether a product received an orphan designation was run based on our assumption that an orphan drug for a cancer indication would be more likely to be listed, with or without restrictions.

All analyses controlled for country-specific effects to account for heterogeneities at country level by including country GDP per capita and variables indicating the model of HTA prevailing in each country (clinical and cost-effectiveness vs comparative clinical benefit assessment) and the country practice in terms of topic selection (whether the HTA agency assesses all or some of the new products approved by regulatory agencies); in order to account for product-specific heterogeneities we included oncology and orphan designation as covariates. Finally, the year of the HTA recommendation was also added as a control to account for time effects.

The models in (4) and (6) were run (a) for the full sample comprising all 8 countries and (b) a sub-sample comprising 6 countries based on the HTA model they follow (i.e. clinical and cost-effectiveness), thereby excluding France and Germany (that follow comparative clinical benefit assessment). The latter was undertaken to investigate the effect of incremental cost effectiveness on the HTA recommendation; France and Germany were excluded in (b) because economic evaluation is either not performed as part of the HTA process (Germany) [Vreman, 2020], or plays a minor role in decision-making [CEPS, 2019]. All statistical analyses were performed in Stata Version 16 [StataCorp, 2020].

Descriptive analysis

HTA funding recommendations and restrictions

Not all medicines that are approved by regulatory bodies (e.g. the EMA (in the EU), Health Canada (Canada), Therapeutic Goods Administration (Australia)) are funded by the health care systems of the study countries. Although the original sample of medicine-indication pairs was $n=219$, the number of medicine-indication pairs assessed by each HTA agency ranged from 147 (England) to 200 (France). Despite the majority of medicines assessed by HTA agencies receiving a positive coverage recommendation (L=16%, $n=231$; LWC=71%, $n=1004$), a sizeable proportion (12%, $n=180$) were rejected (Table 2).

Just over 12% of the sample consisted of orphan medicinal products (OMPs) (Pearson $n=163$; $\chi^2=43.6$, $p=0.164$) (Table 2). The proportion of OMPs that received positive or positive but restricted recommendations was slightly higher (90%) compared with the rest of the sample (88%), indicating the importance of OMPs and the slightly different criteria that may apply in their assessment (Kawalec et al, 2016). Thirty six percent of our sample ($n=511$; $\chi^2 = 4.2$ ($p=0.122$)) comprised oncology drugs, of which 70% were listed with restrictions, 15% were listed as applied for, while the remaining 15% were rejected. Oncology drugs represented 47% of all rejections in the sample.

Sixty-five percent of list with restrictions (LWC) recommendations were subject to one or more clinical restrictions (Pearson $\chi^2=495$, $p=0.000$). These related to patient population restrictions (40% of the total), dosing restrictions (14%), or both (11%) (Figure 1A). Population restrictions lead to the narrowing down of the approved indication, to sub-groups of eligible patients who are likely to benefit most. The proportion of clinical restrictions has not changed over time, with population restrictions always being above the 30% of the total LWC decisions and at a higher proportion compared with dosing restrictions.

Considering the high cost of several new drugs as well as the clinical uncertainties associated with their use (e.g. uncertain patient outcome depending on patient type), HTA agencies may recommend or impose funding restrictions in order to mitigate some of the financial risk associated with their

adoption. Thirty one percent (n=439) of all drugs that were approved with restrictions (LWC), were recommended with a risk-sharing agreement (RSA) while 4% (n=53) were linked to other special funding agreements, the latter implying earmarked funds, or funding under data collection conditions. Over time the proportion of RSAs has increased, from only 20% of LWC decisions in 2011 to 69% in 2018 (Figure 1B).

<Figure 1 about here>

Time to coverage and impact of regulatory schemes

Following marketing authorization (MA), drugs take on average >12 months to be recommended for funding; time varies between L, LWC and DNL recommendations and mean time to funding approval stands at 9.68 months (for ‘L’ decisions), 12.1 months (‘LWC’) and 14.85 months (‘DNL’)(Pearson $\chi^2=186.959$, $p=0.036$). Significant variations exist across countries, with Australia showing the lowest average difference between MA and funding recommendation (8 months) and England, Quebec and France showing the highest (18.1, 14.2 and 13.6 months, respectively). Having an accelerated MA does not necessarily correspond to a faster funding decision compared with standard MA (Figure 2). However, the implementation of parallel review in Canada [Health Canada, 2018] and Australia [PBAC, 2018], has an impact on the time to coverage with an average time of 3.7 months in Australia, 6.7 months in Canada and 10.6 months in Quebec, respectively (Figure 2).

Early approval pathways (n=215, 15% of the sample) and parallel reviews (n=145, 10% of the sample) did not seem to have had significant impact on the outcomes of the HTA process. Early approval pathways were more likely to lead to listing with restrictions (LWC=71%) and rejection (DNL=15%) than to unrestricted listing (L=13%). Parallel review showed comparable outcomes (LWC= 79%, L=7% and DNL=14%).

<Insert Figure 2 here>

Type of clinical evidence submitted

Most submissions (86%; n=1,220) presented at least one phase III randomized clinical trial as main evidence supporting claims on clinical benefit. Over time, however, the number of submissions informed by ‘weaker’ or early phase evidence (e.g. Phase II) has increased (Figure 1D). This may reflect the introduction of accelerated approvals to enable promising treatments to come to market faster.

Contrary to the high proportion of phase III clinical trials in HTA submissions, significant issues were identified with regards to comparators and the type of primary endpoints used, such that more than half of the sample drug-indication pairs were either compared to placebo, including best supportive care (47% of all submissions, n=545), or had no comparator and, therefore, relied on single arm trials (8% of all submissions, n=114). The lack of (active) comparator was also correlated with a higher number of rejections (63% of all the rejections).

Most drug-indication pairs (82%, n=1,167) were submitted to HTA agencies with evidence from a surrogate endpoint as their primary source of evidence and only 18% (n=248) had a clinical endpoint as the primary endpoint. At the same time, 77% of all rejections (n=136), had a surrogate as their main evidence endpoint.

In terms of how quality of care impacted HTA funding recommendations, evidence from the sample showed that only 20% of all submissions were informed by good quality of evidence whereas 47% by average quality and 33% by poor quality. Over the time these proportions have been stable showing half of HTA submissions per annum are deemed to be of average quality (Figure 1E).

Resubmissions following a rejection

Twenty four percent (n=388; $\chi^2=28.47$, p=0.000) of all HTA submissions had at least one prior rejection, implying failure to satisfy decision-makers on a number of criteria, including the quality of evidence and clinical benefit, among others (Figure 1C). Of the drug-indication pairs that received a final rejection, 31% (n=56) had at least one previous rejection, which implies that in re-submitting

the product for re-consideration, manufacturers failed to address the concerns of the same agencies from the previous rejection. There was a steady increase over time of re-submission with 11% of the total HTA assessments having undergone at least one re-submission in 2011 to 29% in 2018. This may be related to the introduction of stricter criteria or clearer and re-submission processes by HTA bodies.

Cost-effectiveness evidence

The ICER is significantly associated with the outcome of the HTA process ($\chi^2=33.39$, $p=0.000$), but important variations exist. In 28% of all cases ($n=395$) economic evidence was not submitted, either because the HTA system does not assess evidence on cost effectiveness (France and Germany), or because the clinical benefit was not achieved (Quebec, $n=27$) or because of abbreviated submissions (Scotland, $n=18$). Of the cases where economic evidence was submitted ($n=1,020$), 31% ($n=318$) had no ICER or cost-utility analysis but alternative models – such as cost minimization – were submitted instead; in 16% ($n=165$) of cases the submitted ICER was confidential, pointing to an arrangement between the manufacturer and the health care system around the price of the drug (typically, a risk sharing agreement (RSA)) in order to facilitate coverage, while in the remaining cases an explicit ICER was submitted (53%, $n=537$) (Figure 3).

<Insert Figure 3 here>

Uncertainties and Social Value Judgements (SVJs)

We identified a number of clinical and economic uncertainties raised by HTA agencies when the latter judge the robustness of the submitted evidence. We found that uncertainties relating to the size of the clinical benefit were the most frequently raised (48% of the sample, $n=685$; $\chi^2=8.06$, $p=0.018$), while generalizability issues were raised in 34% of the sample ($n=484$; $\chi^2 = 12.92$, $p=0.002$), followed by adverse events concerns (27%, $n=386$; $\chi^2 = 3.05$ $p=0.218$) (Table 2). The highest

number of economic uncertainties were raised around modelling (33% of the sample, $n=470$; $\chi^2 = 15.45$, $p=0.000$) and included concerns on the actual structure of the model in submissions.

We tested the association between several key social value judgements, such as severity, unmet need, and administration advantage, with their effect on the HTA outcome and whether it was positive, negative, or non-existent. We found that severity had a detectable and measurable effect in 26% of the sample ($n=369$; $\chi^2=0.57$, $p=0.753$); unmet need was present in 43% of the sample ($n=607$; $\chi^2=20.44$, $p=0.000$); administration advantage was present in 22% of the sample ($n=308$; $\chi^2=5.36$, $p=0.069$); finally, innovation was considered only in 14% of the sample ($n=202$; $\chi^2=10.27$, $p=0.006$). No significant changes were detected on the proportion of SVJs considered over time, suggesting a constant approach towards the consideration of SVJs in HTA decisions (Figure 1F). Although we found that there was both a detectable and measurable effect of SVJs, the extent to which they have contributed to a positive decision or reversed a negative decision, can only be examined in multi-variate analysis.

Econometric analysis

A total of $N=1,415$ observations across the eight study countries were considered in the analysis; in the reduced sample, comprising 6 countries, the sample was $N=1,065$ observations.

(a) Time to HTA recommendation

The variables tested were phase, comparator and endpoint of the main trial(s) supporting the HTA submission, re-submission, orphan designation, marketing authorization pathway, regulatory approval type, agency and country-specific characteristics and year of the HTA submission (Table 1). The logarithmic transformation of HTA_TIME_{ij} as well as robust standard errors were deployed to mitigate heteroskedasticity issues previously identified with Breusch-Pagan and Cook-Weisberg tests (*estat hettest* command in STATA).

Having an active comparator (vs placebo or no comparator) was associated with a shorter time to market entry while having clinical endpoint (vs surrogate) was associated to longer time to market entry, though this was not statistically significant. Having a phase III trial supporting the HTA submission was significantly ($p<0.01$) associated with a longer time to market entry, compared to all other trial phases (i.e., phase I, II) or indirect comparisons. This may be explained by the high presence of phase III trials in our sample (84%). Though, exploratory analyses where the trial phase and comparator variables were interacted indicated that drugs supported by phase III trials and an active comparator reached the market faster than those who did not ($p<0.05$). Products with orphan designation were associated with a longer time to funding recommendation ($p<0.01$), confirming evidence on differences in the time to access to orphan drugs based on country policies [Zamora et al, 2019]. Compared with a standard regulatory approval, parallel review was associated with a shorter time lag between marketing authorization to the final HTA coverage recommendation ($p<0.01$), while the accelerated approval pathway was correlated with an increase in the time to coverage but was not statistically significant. Both, unrestricted funding and funding with an RSA were associated with a faster time to coverage compared to decisions not to fund products, but only funding decisions with an RSA were associated with statistically significant and faster time to market ($p<0.05$), highlighting that RSAs despite often being complex to conclude are speeding up access to market. Products approved with special funding were associated with longer time to entry, though this was not statistically significant. All agency and country-specific variables included in the analysis were found to be statistically significant. Countries using clinical and cost effectiveness took longer to reach a funding recommendation than countries using comparative clinical benefit assessment, while countries whose agencies assessed all products coming to market experienced faster time to funding recommendation (respectively $p<0.1$ and $p<0.01$).

Results in the smaller sample were aligned with those in the broad sample equations, but a few differences were observed. Most notably, in the time to access linear regression, orphan designation

was associated with an even longer time to market entry compared to when France and Germany were dropped from the analysis ($p < 0.01$). This might be associated with country-specific features of the French and German reimbursement system that allow a faster reimbursement process for orphans by considering their benefit as given and not subjecting them to detailed HTA scrutiny [Zamora et al, 2019]. Interestingly, a statistically longer time to access ($p < 0.05$) was related to the presence of an accelerated pathway when obtain regulatory approval. This variable was not statistically significant for the full sample. This could be related to the standardized time pathway established in both countries that do not allow shorter assessment time for medicines undergoing accelerated approval at regulatory level. By contrast resubmission were associated with a shorter time to access ($p < 0.01$) when dropping Germany and France.

(b) Factors associated with HTA recommendation

Across all models, the likelihood of a product being listed (L) was negatively correlated with a previously failed submission ($p < 0.01$), meaning that if a product had a re-submission, the less likely it would be that such product would receive a positive and unconditional funding recommendation (Table 4). Despite ratios suggesting the same effect for products listed with criteria (LWC), results were not statistically significant across the board. Orphan products for oncological indications were more likely to be either listed or listed with criteria across all regressions ($p < 0.01$).

The effect of the quality of the evidence submitted to HTA on recommendation was explored across all the models and ‘high quality of evidence’ was found to be positively and significantly associated with both unrestricted listing and listing with restrictions ($p < 0.01$).

Of the four SVJs included in our model (administration advantage, severity, unmet need, and innovation) only severity showed to be not significant. Having the innovation of the treatment explicitly recognized by the HTA agency increased the likelihood of being listed with criteria (ranging from $p < 0.05$ to $p < 0.01$) Similarly, the recognition of administrative advantage and unmet

need by HTA agencies was positively associated with a statistically higher likelihood of being listed with criteria in the core model including all the covariates (respectively $p < 0.1$ and $p < 0.05$).

Finally, the effect of both clinical and economic uncertainties was explored and the presence of uncertainties around the generalizability of clinical studies to the population or the clinical practice in the submission were associated with a statistically significant lower likelihood to getting listed or listed with criteria ($p < 0.05$)

In the model including all the covariates, clinical benefit uncertainties were found to have a negative impact on reimbursement, with a statistically negative likelihood to get reimbursed fully or with criteria (respectively $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.1$). Interestingly, having generalizability uncertainties raised by the HTA agency decreased the likelihood of both being listed and listed with criteria. Results were statistically significant and in one case significant ($p < 0.05$). Economic uncertainties had some effect on HTA recommendations too. Interestingly, uncertainties around the modelling techniques used by the manufacturer in the economic model were associated with a higher likelihood of being listed with criteria ($p < 0.01$); By contrast, uncertainties relating to the clinical and cost inputs included in the economic models were associated with a lower likelihood of being listed with criteria only in one model ($p < 0.1$, all covariates model).

The country practice in terms of topic selection was also found to be statistically significant across all models ($p < 0.01$) and the likelihood of drugs to be listed without restrictions was inversely correlated to the year of HTA assessment ($p < 0.01$). Finally, GDP was not found to be associated with coverage decisions.

Table 5 presents the results for the sub-sample that excluded France and Germany from the main sample of countries, in order to investigate the effect of economic evaluation on funding recommendations. For the HTA recommendation analysis, results were consistent among both samples, with some minor differences in terms of significance and magnitude of effects. Compared

to a confidential ICER, products with an explicit ICER were more likely to be listed both with or without restrictions ($p < 0.05$). This is likely to reflect that drugs without an RSA generally have a price low enough to meet the required threshold and therefore are more easily reimbursed. Having other economic models (e.g. cost minimization) supporting the HTA increased the likelihood of being listed, but not listed with restrictions ($p < 0.05$).

Robustness analysis

In order to test whether the multinomial logistic regression presented above adequately captured country-specific heterogeneities, we deployed as a robustness check a mixed-effects multilevel logistic approach where our sample of drug-indication pairs were clustered at the agency level. A mixed-effects model was chosen as it considers random effects to model intraclass correlation as well as fixed effects, analogously to standard regression analysis.

As a STATA built-in option for multilevel multinomial regressions was not available, two separate logistic regressions with DNL as base category were ran (DNL vs LWC, DNL vs L).

Results appeared robust to different model specifications, suggesting that a multinomial logistic approach with agency-specific dummies did adequately explain heterogeneities at the country level. Though, a few differences in magnitude of effects are worth noting, notably, administration advantage is not significantly associated with being listed with criteria, while in previous regression it was significant at the 10% level. Also, in the sub-sample excluding Germany and France, ICER does not appear to be significantly associated with being listed with or without criteria, while it was previously significant ($p < 0.05$). Results of the robustness analysis are presented in Appendix Table X.

Discussion

In this study we undertook an analysis of factors associated with HTA coverage recommendations across 7 OECD countries with well-established and transparent HTA systems. A number of new findings have emerged from this study. First, whereas an overwhelming majority of our sample drug-indication pairs (87.3%) have been recommended for funding, our findings suggest that most coverage recommendations are associated with significant clinical restrictions in new drug use or/and financial agreements in order to mitigate uncertainty and optimise on cost. Despite these restrictions, by admitting new and expensive products into reimbursement, it seems that decision-makers are mindful of the impact current and future innovation can have both on public health improvement as well as economic growth and accept new products with marginal improvements in clinical effect, while rejecting those where the clinical effect is least quantifiable and highly uncertain [Akehurst, 2017; Nicod & Kanavos, 2012; Spinner et al 2013].

Second, our study has shown that there is a significant time gap between regulatory approval and HTA recommendation. Interestingly, negative HTA recommendations take longer to arrive at compared with unrestricted or restricted coverage recommendations. Although this may appear counter intuitive, it may be associated with the high level of scrutiny promoted by HTA bodies before a final decision has been reached and the significant proportion of original rejections, followed by a re-submission.

Third, our results showed a clear relationship between a delay in coverage when negotiation of an RSA is taking place. While RSAs ultimately facilitate access and it appears that positive recommendations are closely associated with the presence of RSAs, the time to coverage recommendation seems to be shorter compared with drugs that are not covered by an RSA, supporting the argument that RSAs altogether facilitate access to new therapies the results of earlier analysis that time to recommendation for oncology drugs was 84 days while drugs without RSA took

significantly longer to obtain a positive recommendation (343 days) [Espin, 2011]. As well, decision-making via inclusion into special coverage schemes (e.g. Cancer Drugs Fund in England, or the Exceptional Access Programme in the Canadian province of Ontario) showed a faster time to coverage was achieved.

Fourth, time to coverage recommendations was longer for products approved via an early approval pathway and for orphan drugs than for products approved through standard MA in line with earlier findings, which nevertheless limit these findings to orphan drugs [Kawalec et al 2016; Nicod et al 2020], despite a significant proportion of both being recommended with an RSA (31% (n=68 out of 215) of drug-indication pairs approved with accelerated pathways and 33% (n=55 out of 163) of orphan drugs were recommended with an RSA). This can be explained by the fact that orphan products and products eligible for early approval pathways often enter negotiations with weak clinical evidence and HTA may request further evidence in order to arrive at a coverage recommendation. While early approval pathways were associated with longer time to a coverage decision, parallel review processes were shown to lead to shorten the time to coverage recommendation [Tafari et al 2018; Allen et al 2017]. This may show an alignment between regulatory and HTA requirements and allows funding decisions and market entry to be made faster. For instance, the extension to 6 months by CADTH of the parallel review system with Health Canada [Health Canada 2018] resulted in speeding up the process by removing the requirements for a separate priority review and allowing the submission to take place at the same time to both the regulator and the HTA agency. Similar arrangements exist in Australia [PBAC, 2018]. Overall, our results show when alignment between regulatory and reimbursement evidence requirements is achieved, new products have a faster entry to market. This could be an important message for the conduct of HTA at EU level, particularly in the context of the EU draft regulation on HTA, which elevates one aspect of HTA (relative effectiveness assessment at EU level)[European Commission, 2019].

Fifth, cost-effectiveness estimates play an important role in coverage recommendations and adhering to a certain threshold is often a watershed in decision-making [Jönsson, 2015; Schwarzer et al 2015; Griffiths et al, 2015]. Having confirmed this, we also demonstrated that, where required, the submission of cost-effectiveness evidence was characterised by several nuances: one of them was associated with the confidentiality of ICERs, while the other related to alternatives to submitting an ICER. With regards to confidentiality, in 12% of the sample the ICER was kept confidential and was associated with the presence of a risk sharing agreement, which, in the majority of cases had as an objective the improvement in the ICER and, ultimately, to achieve coverage. With regards to ICER alternatives, our results showed that conducting a model different from cost-utility is more likely to lead to a positive outcome; this was strictly related to the type of product assessed and, ultimately, the unmet need in the respective therapeutic areas. When several treatment options were available and the clinical benefit was perceived to be identical or similar to an already reimbursed treatment, listing through a cost-minimization would probably suffice to enable coverage, but might also raise questions on considering SVJs and other dimensions of benefit (e.g. administration advantage) to establish which treatment should be prioritised.

Sixth, our results confirmed that phase III trials were the main clinical evidence used in HTA submissions as shown elsewhere [Clement, 2009; Nicod & Kanavos, 2012] and that having a direct comparator shorten the time of a product gaining acceptance, highlighting the importance of the role of appropriate comparators in HTA decision-making, despite 47% of the sample submissions being informed by RCTs with placebo or no comparator, in line with earlier evidence [Akehurst et al, 2016]. Our results showed that this was particularly the case of orphan drugs: out of 163 orphan drug submissions, 109 were supported by only a placebo comparator (66% of the submissions), while in 28% of cases (n=45) there was no comparator supporting the submission. For instance, in the case of avelumab for the treatment of Metastatic Merkel cell carcinoma or daratumumab for the treatment of relapsed and refractory multiple myeloma the only available evidence came from single arm trials

[Usmani et al, 2020; Kaufman et al 2016]. In both cases the medicines underwent a type of accelerated regulatory scheme and were orphan products.

Seventh supporting our results shown that the consideration by HTA committee of scientific concerns (uncertainties) around the clinical and economic evidence shown to be proven statistically significant.

This remarks that the robustness of evidence is still the key drivers in HTA decisions. Interestingly, the raise of concerns is not always led to negative decisions but can just prompt manufacturer to refine or complement the evidence submitted. For instance, uncertainties raised around the modelling techniques used for the economic evidence are often raised but they have way less impact than others because often HTA bodies allow companies to redesign their model. By contrast, issues around clinical evidence such as the magnitude of the clinical benefits and the generalizability of the trial results to the population and the clinical practice of the country are less addressable and negatively impact the reimbursement decision.

Eighth, positive coverage recommendations may have relied, at least in part, on ‘other considerations’ such as unmet need, lack of therapeutic alternatives or severity, in certain therapeutic areas (e.g. oncology and rare diseases). The statistical significance of these considerations suggests that these play a role in decision-making, despite the fact that clarity or explicit guidance on the likely impact of these parameters of benefit is missing, perhaps with the exception of few cases [NICE, 2008, Littlejohns, 2019; TLV, 2020]. Other studies found that in oncology, HTA agencies developed a set of criteria modifying the WTP ratio in certain settings [Simoens & Dooms, 2011]; however, these are not consistently developed neither across countries, nor therapeutic areas. Even though there has been an attempt to incorporate additional dimensions of benefit through ad hoc considerations of certain elements pertaining to some categories of drugs, such as end-of-life (EOL) criteria and the Highly Specialized Technologies (HST) in England [NICE, 2017], the principle of human dignity and solidarity in Sweden [TLV, 2019] and the “modifiers” by Scottish Medicines Consortium (SMC)

[SMC, 2012], these are still applicable mainly to treatments displaying certain characteristics (e.g. orphan or ultra-orphan drugs, end-of-life therapies).

Whereas many have argued in favour of broadening the set of criteria contributing to the value of new medical technologies [Hyry et al 2014, Garrison et al, 2017; Neumann et al 2018; Lakdawalla et al, 2018; Angelis and Kanavos, 2019], these criteria should have a clear weight when considered in HTA evaluations.

Ninth, by constructing a quality of evidence indicator, our study demonstrated the statistical association between high quality of clinical evidence and HTA recommendation is average, but that high quality evidence is an important predictor of HTA coverage recommendations. Few studies have explored similar indicators and our results might imply that HTA bodies will accept imperfect evidence if other factors (e.g. a low cost or high severity) are relevant. [Dakin et al, 2015; Dakin et al 2006].

Tenth, the explicit recognition of special considerations or social value judgements, such as novel mechanism of action or overall level of innovativeness of the technology, increased the likelihood of products receiving a positive coverage recommendation, suggesting that a number of social value judgements constitute important considerations in finalising drug coverage [Franken et al 2015; Akehurst et al, 2016]. Recent reviews of HTA processes and value dimensions [Angelis et al, 2018] suggest that, with the exception of France and Germany, where it informs the added clinical benefit assessment, the recognition of severity as key factor is still not captured as a clear metric and its inclusion in the appraisal stage varies quite widely across countries. This suggests that certain parameters of benefit are considered as part of the decision-making process, but their consideration remains on an ad hoc basis [Angelis et al 2017; Angelis et al 2017b; Rawlins et al, 2013]. The contribution of some SVJs to the outcome of the HTA process highlights their importance as intrinsic dimensions of benefit and as decision modifiers and, perhaps, points to a need for a more

homogeneous approach recognising them as parameters of value; nevertheless, their precise contribution cannot be quantified in more general terms, as many of these parameters of benefit are purely contextual. This can only take place through the implementation of alternative methodologies that capture these broader dimensions of benefit in a more systematic way [Angelis et al, 2020; Angelis et al 2017; Angelis et al 2017b].

Finally, heterogeneity in assessment practices or factors relating to national priorities may influence the direction of HTA recommendations or the time to coverage across settings. One such heterogeneity relates to how HTA agencies deal with a poor submission, followed by a rejection and a subsequent re-submission. In some cases a submission is kept open and a final decision is deferred pending the completion of evidence by the sponsor (Australia), whereas elsewhere, a rejection can take place and the process of assessment and appraisal and re-start with a fresh submission (Scotland), or a rejection can become final once an appeal has been launched and discussed (England). Quebec seems to adopt a stepwise process whereby economic model submissions are not accepted if the clinical benefit is deemed inadequate. Germany commonly does not accept surrogate endpoints as the main evidence on clinical benefit leading to lower rating of certain medicines.

Limitations

Our study is not without limitations; one such limitation relates to the data collection include: (a) the retrieval of data only from publicly available sources limiting the access to the discussion of HTA committees (especially for France and Sweden) and, therefore, some elements of appraisals may be missing; and (b) the translation of French and German decisions into the nomenclature we have adopted for the rest of the countries may be subjective, as the value assessment system prevailing in both France and Germany differs from the traditional clinical and cost effectiveness model followed

elsewhere. Still, the translation into L, LWC and DNL, follows widely accepted norms. Another limitation was that it was not possible to include metric that would summarise clinical benefit and its performance across all countries and therapeutic indications did; nevertheless, we have proxied this with the inclusion of relevant variables, such as type of comparator, clinical or surrogate endpoint, and uncertainties raised by HTA agencies with regards to the clinical benefit. Finally, as the data collection went on until June 2018, we are not in a position to know whether some of the originally rejected drug-indication pairs were re-submitted later on and, if so, what the outcome of the re-submission was. Nevertheless, a re-submission would most likely amount to the submission of new evidence, therefore, it would constitute a new submission altogether. In Germany, IQWiG or G-BA rating does not constitute final appraisal but the final negotiation of the reimbursement level is done by the German public insurers.

Conclusions

In this paper we have shown how two forms of regulation (drug licensing and HTA) relate to each other and the length of time it takes between licensing and HTA coverage decisions; we have researched the criteria used by HTA agencies, their importance for funding decisions and shown the statistical relationship between a wide range of criteria and HTA coverage decisions; explored the link between efficiency, affordability and equity; discussed the increasing role of risk mitigation strategies to account for uncertainty; and outlined the broader implications of funding decisions for innovation, industrial policy and economic development.

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Source: The authors based on information extracted from publicly available HTA reports.

Figure 2 - Time to funding recommendation

Source: The authors based on information extracted from publicly available HTA reports.

Figure 3 - Type of economic evidence submitted, including ICER submissions, 2011-2018^{1,2}

Note: ¹ “Other models” do not necessarily relate to cost-effectiveness or cost-utility analysis, but could be cost-minimisation or cost analysis.

² Excluding France and Germany, where economic evidence does not constitute an essential part of the assessment process.

Source: The authors based on information extracted from publicly available HTA reports.

Table 6 - Variables deployed in the analysis

Variable	Type	Variable abbreviation	Definition/Explanation
Coverage decision outcome & Timelines			
Final coverage decision ¹	Categorical	HTA_RECOMMEND	1 = L (List; IQWIG /HAS: Level 1/2); 2 = LWC (List with Criteria; IQWIG/HAS: level 3/4/5); 3 = DNL (Do Not List; G-BA= Level 6; SMR=insufficient);
Time to HTA coverage decision	Continuous	HTA_TIME	Time between Marketing Authorisation and final HTA/coverage decision in months
Regulatory variables			
Regulatory approval type	Categorical	APPROVAL	1 = Standard (EMA, Health Canada, TGA) 2 = Accelerated Approval Pathway 3 = Parallel Review
Re-submission	Binary	RESUBMIT	1= Drug has had at least one prior rejection on an earlier submission; 0= no prior rejection
Drug- and diagnosis-specific parameters			
Orphan drug	Binary	ORPHAN	1= Drug has orphan status/designation; 0= no orphan status/designation
Oncology drug	Binary	ONCOLOGY	1= Drug has an oncology indication; 0= no oncology indication
Economic (funding) and clinical restrictions			
Funding restrictions	Categorical	FUNDING	0= Not applicable/not funded; 1 = Unrestricted funding; 2 = Risk sharing agreement; 3 = Special funding arrangement [non-risk-sharing] (e.g. CDF, new drug funding programme, etc)
Clinical restrictions	Categorical	-	0 = No restrictions; 1 = Population restriction; 2 = Dosing restriction; 3 = both
Clinical evidence considerations			
Type of evidence	Binary	PHASEIII	1 = Phase III RCT; 2 = All other types of clinical trial
Comparator ²	Binary	COMPARATOR	1= At least one direct comparator informing the decision; 0= No direct comparator
Primary endpoint	Binary	ENDPOINT	1 = Clinical endpoint as primary endpoint; 0 = Surrogate endpoint as primary endpoint
Quality of evidence	Categorical	QUALITY	1= High quality of evidence (no issues with study design, comparator used in study and follow up period); 2= Average quality of data (there are issues in one of the categories); 3= Poor quality of data (there are issues in more than one category).
Follow up quality of data	Binary	FOLLOWUP	1= If there are no issues explicitly expressed by the HTA body around the follow-up and the long-term data, the quality of evidence is considered 'high QoE'; 0= Otherwise the quality of evidence is considered 'low QoE'.
Economic evidence considerations			
ICER	Categorical	ICER	1= ICER submitted and publicly available; 2= confidential ICER; 3= Other analysis submitted; 4= No ICER submitted.
Clinical uncertainties			
Size of clinical benefit ³	Binary	CLINBEN	1= At least one uncertainty around the size of clinical benefit extrapolated from the evidence submitted; 0= No uncertainties.
Generalisability ⁴	Binary	GENERAL	1= At least an uncertainty related to generalisability to the country's population or local clinical practice; 0= No uncertainties.
Economic uncertainty			
Modelling ⁶	Binary	MODELLING	1= At least an uncertainty around the modelling approach; 0= No uncertainties.
Input ⁸	Binary	MODEL	1= At least an uncertainty around the inputs (cost and utilities) used by the manufacturer in the economic model presented; 0= No uncertainties.
Social value judgements			
Severity	Binary	SEVERITY	1= Severity of the disease explicitly recognised by HTA agency; 0 = Severity not recognised.
Administration route/frequency	Binary	ADMINAD	1= Route and the frequency of administration of the treatment explicitly recognised by HTA agency as offering advantage; 0 = Not recognised as offering advantage.
Unmet need	Binary	UNEED	1= Unmet need for the new treatment (e.g. few or no alternatives exist, need for additional treatments, high BoD) explicitly recognised by HTA agency; 0 = Unmet need not recognised.

Innovation	Binary	INNOVATION	1= Novel mechanism of action and overall innovativeness of the treatment explicitly recognised by HTA agency; 0 = Not recognised.
Country-specific variables			
GDP per capita	Continuous	Ln_GDP	Log of Country GDP per capita
Model of HTA	Binary	HTAMODEL	1= Clinical and cost-effectiveness; 0 = Comparative clinical benefit assessment
Type of HTA agency	Binary	AGENTYPE	1=All products approved by regulatory agencies are assessed by the HTA agency; 0 = Not all products approved by regulatory agencies are assessed by the HTA agency
Time-specific variables			
Year of HTA approval	Continuous	YEARHTA	Year of HTA approval

- Notes:**
- ¹ France and Germany follow a different approach to the other countries in the sample that follow the incremental cost effectiveness model. As such, the classification is not explicitly the same as 'List', 'List with Criteria' and 'Do not List', but subscribes to a specific ranking order, as follows: in France, there is the improvement in the therapeutic benefit (amelioration du service medical rendu – ASMR) that includes 5 scales ranging from major (ASMR=1) to no improvement (ASMR=5); at the same time, the total clinical benefit (service medical rendu) is an indicator of whether a technology is considered beneficial, ranging between SMR=1 (important) and SMR=4 (insufficient), the latter implying an outright rejection, as a drug with SMR=4 will not be included in France's positive list. In the case of Germany, a comparable rating is followed, with the added (clinical) benefit ranging between 1 (major) – 6 (below what is currently available). Ratings between 1-4 imply that drugs enter a price negotiation the rating they receive influences the final price premium over comparator, while if a rating of 5 or 6 is given, the drug is included in the reference pricing categories. Based on the above and in order to ensure comparability across our sample countries with regards to the coverage recommendations received for the same medicine-indication pair across countries, the following was undertaken: Levels 1 and 2 in the French and the German incremental benefit rating were considered as 'List', while Levels between 3 and 5 in both countries' systems were considered as 'List with Criteria'; Level 6 in the German rating and SMR=4 in the French system were considered rejections, i.e. 'Do not List'.
 - ² When an indirect comparison informs the submission as main clinical evidence, it is considered that a direct comparator is not present and therefore categorizes the evidence as 'low'.
 - ³ Concerns raised around the magnitude of clinical benefit (e.g. is too little or confounded by other factors that are not related to the clinical design) may comprise but are not limited to: (1) Modest or low clinical benefit from trial; (2) The response of the pharmaceutical varied from study to study; (3) The response of the pharmaceutical is effective only in a sub-population; (4) The response of the pharmaceutical is not statistically significant compared with the comparator.
 - ⁴ Concerns raised around the **generalizability of the population** used in the clinical evidence to the country of the HTA body may comprise but are not limited to: (1) the trial population is not generalizable to the country population due to ethnicity/ baseline characteristics and prevalence; (2) The trial population is not included/underrepresented the population of the indication under review; (3) Only a subgroup of the trial is considered suitable for the indication. Concerns raised around **generalizability of the clinical practice** of the clinical trials submitted by the manufacturer (e.g. administration route or pre- and concomitant medication or a different use of the resource of the health system) may comprise but are not limited to: (1) differences in the pathway in the clinical practice of the country; (2) differences in the administration and dose in comparison with the standard of care; (3) When the treatment criteria (e.g. baseline of the patients for starting the treatment) differed between the study and clinical practice; (4) A pharmaceutical may have limited use in the study country (e.g. PBAC clinical pathways).
 - ⁵ Concerns around the safety profile of the medicine under evaluation stemmed from the clinical benefit evidence or the EPAR. It may comprise but is not limited to: (1) Substantial number of patients discontinuing the therapies due to adverse events; (2) EPAR with too many safety issues in comparison with current treatment used; and (3) There are notable adverse events that would lead to specific monitoring.
 - ⁶ Concerns around the modelling used (e.g. in Markov/ partitioned survival model), or the extrapolation technique used for the clinical data may comprise but is not limited to: (1) the modelling used is not suitable; (2) the use of curves is not appropriate; (3) extrapolations method is not appropriate; (4) misrepresentation of the population under review or of some specific subgroup; (5) any computational errors.
 - ⁷ Concerns around the use of a certain model (cost-minimization or cost-utility etc) in that may not suitable for the analysis.
 - ⁸ Concerns around the **cost data** used to build the model leading to over- or under-estimation of the ICER may comprise but is not limited to: (1) some costs included in the model are too low or too high; (2) the model does not include specific cost that would lead to a over-estimation or under-estimation of the cost-effectiveness such as administration cost or wastage. Concerns around the **utility data** used to build the model leading to over- or under-estimation of the ICER may comprise but are not limited to: (1) the utility values used in the model are not suitable leading to over-estimation or under-estimation of the ICER; (2) the utility source is not suitable/ or the measured was not appropriate.

Source: The authors.

Table 7 - Descriptive statistics

HTA/funding outcome				
Outcome type (DNL/LWC/L) N (% of total)	Do Not List (DNL) N=180 (13%)	List With Criteria (LWC) N=1,004 (71%)	List (L) N=231 (16%)	Total N=1,415 (100%)
Country (Agency) $\chi^2 = 253.395 (0.000)$				
Canada (CADTH)	29 (16%)	160 (16%)	9 (4%)	198 (14%)
France (HAS)	10 (6%)	156 (16%)	34 (15%)	200 (14%)
Canada (INESS)	65 (36%)	91 (9%)	24 (10%)	180 (13%)
Germany (IQWiG)	1 (1%)	107 (11%)	42 (18%)	150 (11%)
England (NICE)	11 (6%)	123 (12%)	13 (6%)	147 (10%)
Australia (PBAC)	36 (20%)	149 (15%)	5 (2%)	190 (13%)
Scotland (SMC)	18 (10%)	133 (13%)	45 (19%)	196 (14%)
Sweden (TLV)	10 (6%)	85 (8%)	59 (26%)	154 (11%)
Orphan status¹ $\chi^2 = 3.610 (0.164)$				
No	164 (91%)	891 (89%)	197 (85%)	1,252 (88%)
Yes	16 (9%)	113 (11%)	34 (15%)	163 (12%)
Therapeutic area $\chi^2 = 4.203 (0.122)$				
Non-oncology	103 (57%)	648 (65%)	153 (66%)	904 (64%)
Oncology	77 (43%)	356 (35%)	78 (34%)	511 (36%)
Funding mechanism p-value = 0.000, Fisher's exact test				
No funding	180 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	180 (13%)
Unrestricted funding	0 (0%)	512 (51%)	231 (100%)	743 (53%)
Risk sharing	0 (0%)	439 (44%)	0 (0%)	439 (31%)
Special funding agreement	0 (0%)	53 (5%)	0 (0%)	53 (4%)
Prior rejection by HTA $\chi^2 = 28.469 (0.000)$				
No	124 (69%)	747 (74%)	206 (89%)	1,077 (76%)
Yes	56 (31%)	257 (26%)	25 (11%)	338 (24%)
Endpoint $\chi^2 = 9.657 (0.000)$				
No clinical endpoint	138 (77%)	848 (84%)	181 (78%)	1,167 (82%)
At least one clinical endpoint	42 (23%)	156 (16%)	50 (22%)	248 (18%)
Scheme of approval $\chi^2 = 13.150 (0.011)$				
Standard	127 (71%)	736 (73%)	191 (83%)	1,054 (74%)
Early approval	33 (18%)	153 (15%)	29 (13%)	215 (15%)
Parallel review	20 (11%)	115 (11%)	11 (5%)	146 (10%)
Comparator $\chi^2 = 23.961 (0.000)$				
No active comparator	113 (63%)	454 (45%)	92 (40%)	659 (47%)
At least one active comparator	67 (37%)	550 (55%)	139 (60%)	756 (53%)
Trial phase $\chi^2 = 2.203 (0.332)$				
No phase III trial	35 (19%)	155 (15%)	41 (18%)	231 (16%)
At least one phase III trial	145 (81%)	849 (85%)	190 (82%)	1,184 (84%)
Clinical restrictions $\chi^2 = 494.980 (0.000)$				
No restrictions	180 (100%)	352 (35%)	231 (100%)	763 (54%)
Population restrictions	0 (0%)	400 (40%)	0 (0%)	400 (28%)
Dosing restrictions	0 (0%)	142 (14%)	0 (0%)	142 (10%)

Population and dosing restrictions	0 (0%)	110 (11%)	0 (0%)	110 (8%)
Quality of evidence (QoE) $\chi^2 = 25.160$ (0.000)				
Good quality	20 (11%)	201 (20%)	69 (30%)	290 (20%)
Average quality	88 (49%)	483 (48%)	88 (38%)	659 (47%)
Poor quality	72 (40%)	320 (32%)	74 (32%)	466 (33%)
ICER (categorical) $\chi^2 = 33.386$ (0.000)				
Cost utility & explicit ICER	68 (38%)	396 (39%)	73 (32%)	537 (38%)
Cost utility & confidential ICER	37 (21%)	114 (11%)	14 (6%)	165 (12%)
Other models ²	38 (21%)	222 (22%)	58 (25%)	318 (22%)
Economic evaluation not conducted ³	37 (21%)	272 (27%)	86 (37%)	395 (28%)
Social value judgments				
Severity $\chi^2 = 0.568$ (0.753)				
Not considered	134 (74%)	737 (73%)	175 (76%)	1,046 (74%)
Considered	46 (26%)	267 (27%)	56 (24%)	369 (26%)
Unmet need $\chi^2 = 20.443$ (0.000)				
Not considered	99 (55%)	546 (54%)	163 (71%)	808 (57%)
Considered	81 (45%)	458 (46%)	68 (29%)	607 (43%)
Administrative advantage $\chi^2 = 5.361$ (0.069)				
Not considered	139 (77%)	774 (77%)	194 (84%)	1,107 (78%)
Considered	41 (23%)	230 (23%)	37 (16%)	308 (22%)
Innovation $\chi^2 = 10.268$ (0.006)				
Not considered	160 (89%)	842 (84%)	211 (91%)	1,213 (86%)
Considered	20 (11%)	162 (16%)	20 (9%)	202 (14%)
Clinical uncertainties				
Clinical benefit $\chi^2 = 8.057$ (0.018)				
No uncertainty	80 (44%)	515 (51%)	135 (58%)	730 (52%)
At least one uncertainty	100 (56%)	489 (49%)	96 (42%)	685 (48%)
Adverse events $\chi^2 = 3.048$ (0.218)				
No uncertainty	122 (68%)	733 (73%)	174 (75%)	1,029 (73%)
At least one uncertainty	58 (32%)	271 (27%)	57 (25%)	386 (27%)
Generalizability $\chi^2 = 12.917$ (0.002)				
No uncertainty	102 (57%)	659 (66%)	170 (74%)	931 (66%)
At least one uncertainty	78 (43%)	345 (34%)	61 (26%)	484 (34%)
Economic uncertainties				
Modelling $\chi^2 = 15.452$ (0.000)				
No uncertainty	117 (65%)	648 (65%)	180 (78%)	945 (67%)
At least one uncertainty	63 (35%)	356 (35%)	51 (22%)	470 (33%)
Model inputs $\chi^2 = 12.745$ (0.002)				
No uncertainty	115 (64%)	714 (71%)	184 (80%)	1,013 (72%)
At least one uncertainty	65 (36%)	290 (29%)	47 (20%)	402 (28%)
HTA model $\chi^2 = 42.959$ (0.000)				
Clinical benefit assessment	11 (6%)	263 (26%)	76 (33%)	350 (25%)
Clinical & cost-effectiveness	169 (94%)	741 (74%)	155 (67%)	1,065 (75%)
HTA Agency type $\chi^2 = 16.364$ (0.000)				
Not all molecules evaluated	122 (68%)	540 (54%)	112 (48%)	774 (55%)
All molecules evaluated	58 (32%)	464 (46%)	119 (52%)	641 (45%)

Months from MA to HTA/funding decision $\chi^2 = 187.891$ (0.033)				
Mean (SD)	14.85 (15.19)	12.10 (13.99)	9.68 (12.37)	12.05 (13.96)
Min ⁴	0	0	0	0
Max	115	113	82	115
HTA/funding decision year $\chi^2 = 48.946$ (0.000)				
Mean (SD)	2015 (2)	2015 (2)	2014 (2)	2015 (2)
Min	2009	2009	2008	2008
Max	2018	2018	2018	2018
GDP ⁵ $\chi^2 = 295.756$ (0.000)				
Mean (SD)	46,913 (3,619)	46,020 (3,812)	45,884 (4,504)	46,112 (3,919)
Min	37,154	34,712	34,712	34,712
Max	56,689	56,689	56,689	56,689

Note: ¹ No orphan status designation is present in Canada.

² Other models include cost minimization, cost comparison and cost consequence analyses.

³ Economic evaluation may be required in France, but it is not a key decision criterion and is not required in Germany. In the Canadian province of Quebec, cost-effectiveness analysis is not conducted if clinical benefit is deemed to be insufficient.

⁴ Zero months from MA to HTA/funding decision are recorded in Australia, where the parallel review process allows PBAC to approve pharmaceutical products concurrently before their marketing authorization.

⁵ OECD (2021), Gross domestic product (GDP) (indicator). doi: 10.1787/dc2f7aec-en (Accessed on 17 February 2021).

Source: The authors.

Table 8 – Results of linear regression for Time to HTA recommendation analysis

Variables (base)	All Countries	Excluding France and Germany
ACTIVE COMPARATOR (NO ACTIVE COMPARATOR)	-0.201* (0.121)	-0.260* (0.154)
CLINICAL ENDPOINT (NO CLINICAL ENDPOINT)	0.0373 (0.136)	0.0201 (0.177)
PHASE III RCT (OTHER PHASE/INDIRECT COMPARISON)	0.740*** (0.207)	0.953*** (0.255)
RESUBMIT (NO RESUBMIT)	0.842*** (0.146)	0.871*** (0.186)
ORPHAN DESIGNATION (NON-OPRHAN)	0.431*** (0.153)	0.763*** (0.183)
ACCELERATED APPROVAL (STANDARD APPROVAL)	0.0502 (0.147)	0.0918 (0.187)
PARALLEL REVIEW (STANDARD APPROVAL)	-2.521*** (0.380)	-2.330*** (0.372)
UNRESTRICTED FUNDING (NO FUNDING)	-0.116 (0.174)	0.0179 (0.194)
RISK SHARING AGREEMENT (RSA) (NO FUNDING)	-0.758*** (0.188)	-0.784*** (0.195)
SPECIAL FUNDING (NO FUNDING)	0.383 (0.292)	0.310 (0.297)
HTA MODEL (CLINICAL EFFECTIVENESS)	0.240* (0.126)	
HTA AGENCY TYPE (NOT ALL MEDICINES ASSESSED)	-0.362*** (0.124)	-0.530*** (0.137)
ln_GDP	-6.028*** (1.062)	-9.889*** (1.508)
HTA YEAR	0.397*** (0.0571)	0.552*** (0.0756)
Constant	-734.4*** (105.8)	-1,004*** (138.6)
Observations	1,415	1,065
R-squared	0.233	0.250

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 9 – Factors associated with HTA coverage recommendations: Results of multinomial regression for core variables (full sample of 8 countries)

Variables	Initial model		Initial model with SVJs		Initial model with uncertainties		Full model	
	LWC	L	LWC	L	LWC	L	LWC	L
	RRR (SE)	RRR (SE)	RRR (SE)	RRR (SE)	RRR (SE)	RRR (SE)	RRR (SE)	RRR (SE)
DNL base case								
RESUBMIT	0.774	0.277***	0.817	0.285***	0.773	0.276***	0.833	0.295***
(NO RESUBMIT)	(0.144)	(0.0758)	(0.152)	(0.0778)	(0.146)	(0.0755)	(0.160)	(0.0810)
ONCOLOGY	0.757	0.817	0.597***	0.776	0.699*	0.892	0.580***	0.799
(no ONCOLOGY)	(0.141)	(0.197)	(0.116)	(0.195)	(0.140)	(0.230)	(0.118)	(0.208)
ORPHAN DESIGNATION	0.598	0.790	0.529	0.731	0.555	0.737	0.469*	0.637
(NON-OPRHAN)	(0.234)	(0.375)	(0.216)	(0.351)	(0.219)	(0.350)	(0.193)	(0.309)
ONCOLOGY#ORPHAN	3.221**	4.050**	3.335**	4.055**	3.455**	4.248**	3.765**	4.579**
(Interaction)	(1.914)	(2.792)	(2.016)	(2.822)	(2.069)	(2.948)	(2.288)	(3.207)
HIGH QoE	2.116***	3.593***	2.381***	3.627***	1.994**	3.178***	2.168***	3.278***
(LOW QoE)	(0.591)	(1.167)	(0.696)	(1.224)	(0.562)	(1.049)	(0.633)	(1.111)
AVERAGE QoE	1.189	1.048	1.325	1.075	1.205	0.995	1.297	1.033
(LOW QoE)	(0.221)	(0.251)	(0.250)	(0.262)	(0.227)	(0.244)	(0.246)	(0.255)
HTA MODEL	0.211***	0.132***	0.159***	0.122***	0.156***	0.123***	0.122***	0.104***
(CLINICAL EFFECTIVENESS)	(0.0671)	(0.0459)	(0.0518)	(0.0436)	(0.0513)	(0.0451)	(0.0409)	(0.0390)
HTA AGENCY TYPE	2.374***	2.100***	2.571***	2.056***	2.366***	2.122***	2.785***	2.271***
(NOT ALL MEDICINES ASSESSED)	(0.520)	(0.539)	(0.603)	(0.569)	(0.526)	(0.560)	(0.677)	(0.648)
ln_GDP	0.0224*	2.588	0.163	3.975	0.0176*	0.855	0.0932	1.942
	(0.0446)	(6.118)	(0.340)	(9.886)	(0.0363)	(2.097)	(0.200)	(4.930)
HTA YEAR	0.991	0.754***	0.924	0.744***	0.979	0.766***	0.909	0.736***
	(0.0752)	(0.0644)	(0.0738)	(0.0672)	(0.0763)	(0.0675)	(0.0739)	(0.0676)
SEVERITY RECORDED			1.048	1.276			1.160	1.451
(SEVERITY NOT RECORDED)			(0.231)	(0.351)			(0.261)	(0.404)
INNOVATION RECORDED			2.083**	1.366			2.292***	1.675
(INNOVATION NOT RECORDED)								

IMPACT HTA

			(0.599)	(0.514)			(0.682)	(0.645)
ADMIN ADVANTAGE RECOR. (ADMIN ADVANTAGE NOT RECOR.)			1.395 (0.319)	1.211 (0.358)			1.563* (0.368)	1.439 (0.437)
UNMET NEED RECORDED (UNMET NEED NOT RECORDED)			1.341 (0.267)	0.700 (0.181)			1.552** (0.332)	0.864 (0.236)
CLINICAL BENEFIT RECORDED. (CLIN BENEFIT NOT RECORDED)					0.747 (0.154)	0.694 (0.177)	0.618** (0.139)	0.623* (0.169)
GENERALISABILITY RECORDED (GEN/BILITY NOT RECORDED)					0.662** (0.134)	0.581** (0.148)	0.561*** (0.117)	0.533** (0.138)
MODELLING RECORDED (MODELLING NOT RECORDED)					2.494*** (0.526)	1.543 (0.437)	2.229*** (0.483)	1.506 (0.438)
INPUT RECORDED (INPUT NOT RECORDED)					0.793 (0.161)	0.730 (0.199)	0.682* (0.142)	0.684 (0.188)
Constant	1.157e+27 (1.592e+29)	7.161e+243 *** (1.106e+246)	9.393e+78 (1.354e+81)	1.559e+253 *** (2.533e+255)	1.081e+39 (1.526e+41)	3.283e+234 *** (5.211e+236)	1.418e+96 (2.081e+98)	3.525e+26 5*** (5.815e+267)
Observations					1,415			
Pseudo R-squared	0.0747			0.0883		0.0882		0.102
Chi2	144.7			178.8		190.5		217.5
Prob > chi2	0			0		0		0

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 10- Factors associated with HTA coverage recommendations: Results of multinomial regression for core variables (sample of 6 countries, excluding France and Germany)

Variables	<i>Initial model</i>		<i>Initial model with SVJs</i>		<i>Initial model with uncertainties</i>		<i>Full model</i>	
	LWC RRR (SE)	L RRR (SE)	LWC RRR (SE)	L RRR (SE)	LWC RRR (SE)	L RRR (SE)	LWC RRR (SE)	L RRR (SE)
<i>DNL base case</i>								
RESUBMIT (NO RESUBMIT)	0.817 (0.157)	0.214*** (0.0748)	0.847 (0.163)	0.213*** (0.0735)	0.811 (0.159)	0.215*** (0.0741)	0.861 (0.171)	0.220*** (0.0757)
ONCOLOGY (no ONCOLOGY)	0.769 (0.154)	0.360*** (0.113)	0.621** (0.131)	0.387*** (0.129)	0.728 (0.154)	0.408*** (0.136)	0.614** (0.133)	0.394*** (0.133)
ORPHAN DESIGNATION (NON-OPRHAN)	0.610 (0.263)	0.480 (0.279)	0.551 (0.247)	0.476 (0.281)	0.576 (0.247)	0.461 (0.268)	0.500 (0.224)	0.416 (0.248)
ONCOLOGY#ORPHAN (Interaction)	3.378* (2.272)	10.11*** (8.671)	3.501* (2.394)	9.535*** (8.278)	3.619* (2.459)	10.88*** (9.424)	3.929** (2.708)	11.29*** (9.914)
HIGH QoE (LOW QoE)	1.855** (0.533)	4.126*** (1.451)	2.043** (0.615)	3.914*** (1.422)	1.807** (0.523)	3.722*** (1.325)	1.939** (0.583)	3.704*** (1.351)
AVERAGE QoE (LOW QoE)	1.202 (0.233)	1.237 (0.348)	1.318 (0.261)	1.215 (0.345)	1.242 (0.244)	1.171 (0.337)	1.326 (0.264)	1.198 (0.345)
EXPLICIT ICER (CONFIDENTIAL ICER)	2.150*** (0.548)	2.759*** (1.081)	2.011*** (0.519)	2.825*** (1.120)	2.062*** (0.532)	2.883*** (1.138)	1.926** (0.499)	2.774** (1.102)
OTHER ECONOMIC MODELS (CONFIDENTIAL ICER)	1.296 (0.327)	2.268** (0.873)	1.283 (0.329)	2.274** (0.887)	1.370 (0.347)	2.336** (0.911)	1.338 (0.347)	2.309** (0.912)
HTA AGENCY TYPE (NOT ALL MEDICINES ASSESSED)	2.433*** (0.566)	2.232*** (0.621)	2.605*** (0.643)	2.248*** (0.663)	2.455*** (0.576)	2.245*** (0.638)	2.829*** (0.717)	2.470*** (0.748)
ln_GDP	0.0538 (0.122)	1.695 (5.060)	0.322 (0.769)	2.634 (8.006)	0.0380 (0.0881)	0.296 (0.889)	0.156 (0.379)	0.626 (1.926)
HTA YEAR	0.962 (0.0784)	0.777** (0.0765)	0.904 (0.0775)	0.773** (0.0790)	0.957 (0.0793)	0.806** (0.0808)	0.896 (0.0776)	0.782** (0.0809)

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SEVERITY RECORDED	1.000	1.086			1.096	1.245		
(SEVERITY NOT RECORDED)	(0.235)	(0.355)			(0.261)	(0.409)		
INNOVATION RECORDED	1.875**	1.148			2.069**	1.423		
(INNOVATION NOT RECORDED)	(0.550)	(0.488)			(0.631)	(0.625)		
ADMIN ADVANTAGE RECOR.	1.347	1.362			1.497*	1.653		
(ADMIN ADVANTAGE NOT RECOR.)	(0.312)	(0.429)			(0.356)	(0.536)		
UNMET NEED RECORDED	1.355	0.627			1.547**	0.797		
(UNMET NEED NOT RECORDED)	(0.272)	(0.181)			(0.334)	(0.242)		
CLINICAL BENEFIT RECORD.				0.778	0.780	0.659*	0.736	
(CLIN BENEFIT NOT RECORDED)				(0.167)	(0.226)	(0.152)	(0.225)	
GENERALISABILITY RECORDED				0.744	0.463***	0.630**	0.433***	
(GEN/BILITY NOT RECORDED)				(0.155)	(0.138)	(0.137)	(0.132)	
MODELLING RECORDED				2.247***	1.423	2.054***	1.425	
(MODELLING NOT RECORDED)				(0.480)	(0.435)	(0.449)	(0.444)	
INPUT RECORDED				0.737	0.703	0.645**	0.658	
(INPUT NOT RECORDED)				(0.149)	(0.206)	(0.135)	(0.194)	
Constant	4.173e+47	2.568e+2	1.341e+94	4.118e+2	1.033e+54	2.172e+1	5.010e+1	1.043e+217
		17***		20***		94**	04	***
	(6.102e+49	(4.491e+2	(2.054e+96	(7.472e+2	(1.533e+56	(3.868e+1	(7.743e+1	(1.915e+21
)	19))	22))	96)	06)	9)
Observations					1,065			
Pseudo R-squared	0.0798		0.0952		0.0954		0.110	
Chi2	113.4		144.8		150.6		176.2	
Prob > chi2	0		0		0		0	

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Appendix Table 11 - Results of multilevel mixed-effects logistic regressions for all covariates

Variables	All Countries		Excluding France and Germany	
	LWC	L	LWC	L
<i>DNL base case</i>	OR (SE)	OR (SE)	OR (SE)	OD (SE)
RESUBMIT (NO RESUBMIT)	1.076 (0.219)	0.236*** (0.0937)	1.056 (0.222)	0.183*** (0.0845)
ONCOLOGY (no ONCOLOGY)	0.674* (0.146)	0.423** (0.176)	0.681* (0.156)	0.327** (0.160)
ORPHAN DESIGNATION (NON-OPRHAN)	0.394** (0.169)	0.133*** (0.0871)	0.393** (0.182)	0.0618*** (0.0530)
ONCOLOGY#ORPHAN (Interaction)	3.151* (1.893)	8.078** (6.608)	3.890** (2.619)	17.66*** (18.58)
HIGH QoE (LOW QoE)	2.514*** (0.781)	5.384*** (2.525)	2.337*** (0.740)	6.622*** (3.445)
AVERAGE QoE (LOW QoE)	1.363 (0.274)	1.225 (0.422)	1.427* (0.301)	1.792 (0.749)
SEVERITY RECORDED (SEVERITY NOT RECORDED)	1.205 (0.290)	1.073 (0.473)	1.096 (0.278)	0.658 (0.343)
INNOVATION RECORDED (INNOVATION NOT RECORDED)	2.219*** (0.677)	1.493 (0.766)	2.147** (0.661)	1.410 (0.852)
ADMIN ADVANTAGE RECOR. (ADMIN ADVANTAGE NOT RECOR.)	1.160 (0.275)	1.039 (0.432)	1.161 (0.281)	1.077 (0.487)
UNMET NEED RECORDED (UNMET NEED NOT RECORDED)	1.615** (0.357)	1.244 (0.486)	1.550* (0.356)	0.969 (0.413)
CLINICAL BENEFIT RECORD. (CLIN BENEFIT NOT RECORDED)	0.660* (0.152)	0.494* (0.190)	0.705 (0.168)	0.653 (0.287)
GENERALISABILITY RECORDED (GEN/BILITY NOT RECORDED)	0.576** (0.127)	0.487* (0.186)	0.616** (0.144)	0.604 (0.269)
MODELLING RECORDED (MODELLING NOT RECORDED)	2.269*** (0.539)	3.056** (1.332)	2.246*** (0.549)	2.730** (1.300)
INPUT RECORDED (INPUT NOT RECORDED)	0.645* (0.146)	0.378** (0.162)	0.634** (0.145)	0.379** (0.179)
HTA AGENCY TYPE (NOT ALL MEDICINES ASSESSED)	2.309 (1.186)	2.493 (2.647)	1.986 (1.094)	1.706 (2.390)
HTA MODEL (CLINICAL EFFECTIVENESS)	0.0955*** (0.0622)	0.0177*** (0.0220)		
ln_GDP	12.97 (42.69)	172.2 (856.9)	21.87 (80.72)	6,386 (37,907)
HTA YEAR	0.799** (0.0854)	0.646*** (0.109)	0.797* (0.0924)	0.621** (0.120)
EXPLICIT ICER (CONFIDENTIAL ICER)			1.401 (0.413)	1.349 (0.766)
OTHER ECONOMIC MODELS (CONFIDENTIAL ICER)			1.378 (0.376)	1.802 (0.987)
Constant	9.027e+185**	***	4.818e+18	***

(1.668e+188) 4**
(9.567e+186)

Observations	1,184	411	910	324
Number of groups	8	8	6	6
Chi2	60.60	65.88	45.93	61.02
Prob > chi2	0	0	0	0

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

**PART C - Health Technology Assessment and funding policies
for Orphan Medicinal Products: Failing, Flawed or Fair?**

Abstract

Context: Orphan medicinal products (OMPs) comprise an ever-increasing part of drug costs and their high cost makes their clinical and economic evaluation and budget impact relevant to health technology assessment (HTA).

Objectives: We discuss the process of value assessment of OMPs, the time gap between marketing authorisation (MA) and coverage decision, the HTA policies and the value considerations that inform these across four different settings. We analyse how clinical and economic evidence feed into the decision-making processes and discuss how uncertainties are addressed in different contexts. Finally, we seek to understand the role of social value judgements (SVJs) as decision modifiers in HTA recommendations.

Methods: We identified 42 compound-indication pairs, which were subjected to HTA in four countries (Australia, Canada, England, Scotland) between 2008 and 2018, resulting in a sample of N=168 compound-indication-country pairings. HTA recommendation and funding decision data were collected from HTA reports available through national online databases. Qualitative and quantitative analysis was deployed to identify key parameters associated with HTA outcomes and funding recommendations.

Findings: A total of 151 HTA reports (Canada=36, England=42, Australia=36, Scotland=37) were identified. The average time between MA and coverage decision is lowest in Canada (12.1 months), followed by Australia (19.4 months), Scotland (23.5 months) and England (32 months). In 50 cases (33%), the respective therapies had at least one prior rejection, which partly explains the length of time between MA and HTA recommendation/funding decision. Coverage decisions were largely positive and often linked to a patient access scheme; NICE issued the maximum percentage of positive recommendations (LWC with PAS= 97%, L=3%), followed by SMC (LWC=70%, L=11%), CADTH (LWC=67%, L=14%), and PBAC (LWC=64%, L=8%). PBAC issued the highest number of negative HTA recommendations with 25%, pursued by both SMC and CADTH, 19% and 20%, respectively. Disease related SVJs (e.g. rarity of disease or limited life expectancy) were given high importance across all HTA reports (CADTH=65%, NICE=57%, PBAC=67%, SMC=66%), whereas treatment-related SVJs (improvements in QoL or first drug in class) were also acknowledged but to a lesser extent (CADTH=35%, NICE=43%, PBAC=33%, SMC=34%).

Conclusions: OMPs are subjected to the same value assessment processes as non-OMPs. Despite the favourable regulatory framework and supportive incentives for R&D purposes, value assessment through HTA remains the same for OMPs as they do for non-OMPs. SVJs provide an enhanced scope for OMPs to receive coverage based on value dimensions beyond costs and effects. Uncertainties,

gaps in (clinical) evidence and high unit costs, which often stretch well beyond willingness to pay (WTP) thresholds, mean that HTA processes take long to recommend some OMPs for coverage.

Background

At a time when budgetary concerns are affecting health care systems globally, the role of health technology assessment (HTA) in promoting efficiency in resource allocation is of particular significance [6, 29-31]. As part of that drive, new drugs must not only have proven safety and efficacy, but also show demonstrable 'value', both clinical and economic, despite criticisms on the methods used to establish 'value' including the differences in perspectives around societal preferences in a variety of settings and for different products [6, 29, 32-34]

Orphan medicinal products (OMPs) are not exempt from standard value assessment rules, although different countries apply a number of modifiers in that context [35]. Beyond value assessment, the development OMPs is encouraged, among others, through flexible regulatory frameworks for orphan designated products and incentives to developers in the USA [36], the European Union [37-40], Australia [41], Japan [42] and elsewhere [43]. Beyond orphan designation, which is based on prevalence, and carries small differences across jurisdictions [32, 36, 42, 44]; key incentives at regulatory level include periods of exclusive marketing rights [25, 44] (, fee reduction for regulatory activities and the provision of scientific advice by drug regulatory bodies (Table 12).

The availability of incentives for the development of OMPs is not coincidental. OMPs are likely to face difficulties in meeting the requirements put forward by HTA agencies and potentially carry a greater risk of rejection [45]. Beyond the possibility of creating an unfavorable platform for investment [44], small patient populations make recruitment of subjects for large scale randomized trials problematic, therefore, establishing efficacy is often challenging despite the significant unmet medical need characterizing the majority of rare diseases [29, 35]. The same applies to the demonstration of cost effectiveness [46], which is a decision criterion for inclusion of new treatments into benefits packages. As a result of the small patient populations and the challenges associated with clinical development, the lack of appropriate comparators or clinically relevant endpoints, OMPs are often characterized by considerable clinical and economic uncertainty, the remedy for which has often been 'conditional reimbursement' or 'coverage with evidence development' by HTA bodies[34] .

Despite the proliferation of these measures, HTA agencies have, on occasion, rejected OMP submissions on the grounds of poor cost-effectiveness [44] or arrive at coverage decisions late and with a significant delay after an OMP has obtained MA, resulting in a considerable access gap. Doubts have also been raised with regards to the adequacy of HTA as a mechanism of value assessment when evaluating drugs for rare diseases, as, at present, organisations may not consider the wider social value of orphan drugs. Similarly, concerns have been raised about the extent to which society should value rarity [47].

In light of the above, the objectives of this study, and its contribution to the literature, are threefold: first, to review and analyze the individual value drivers of OMPs and investigate whether the regulatory endpoints, in principle expediting the process of MA have the same traction at HTA level. Second, to understand the factors associated with coverage/funding of OMPs and the extent to which regulatory, clinical, economic, uncertainty and other considerations influence coverage decisions across settings and research drug-specific or country variations. And, third, considering that the vast majority of orphan drugs are characterized by potentially unacceptably high cost-effectiveness ratios, to explore the role and importance of considerations beyond costs and effects (known as social value judgements) that may contribute to coverage recommendations and prioritization. Section 2 outlines the analytical framework underpinning our analysis; section 3 discusses the methodology, section 4 presents the results, section 5 places the results in the context of the literature, while section 6 draws the main conclusions.

Table 12- Orphan drug policies in key OECD countries

	USA ¹	European Union ²	Australia ³	Japan	Canada ⁴
Orphan Drug Framework	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Date of introduction	1993	2000	1990	1993	N/A
Prevalence threshold (per 10,000 individuals)	5.6	5	1	4	5 ⁵
Population threshold	<200,000 ⁶	<251,250	<2,000	<50,000	<3,300 ⁵
Market Exclusivity (years)	7	10 + 2 ⁷	N/A	10	8
Ratio of drug approval/designation⁸	15.2%	7%	26.8%	64.3%	N/A
Regulatory Assistance	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Fee Reductions	100% ⁹	40%; 100% ¹⁰	100%	Yes ¹¹	Yes ¹²
(Other) key incentives provided	(a) 50% tax credit for clinical research; (b) Accelerated process for marketing authorisation review	(a) Accelerated process for Marketing Authorisation; (b) Administrative and procedural assistance for SMEs (c) Protocol assistance, i.e. scientific advice fee reduction for designated medicines (d) EU Research Framework Programme to provide funds for research. ¹³	(a) flexible prevalence threshold and required evidence for OD designation; (b) treat conditions for which no therapeutic goods are registered (c) fast track approval process (d) regulatory assistance (e) free scientific advice	(a) Financial subsidies (50% of expenses); (b) tax credits (15%); (c) corporate tax cut (14%); (d) drugs for conditions with no therapeutic alternatives can be designated as orphan	N/A

Notes:

¹ Based on the Orphan Drug Act of 1983^[36]

² The European Regulation (EC141/2000)^[39] and a resolution (847/2000)^[40] constitute the main framework for orphan drug definition (for a condition that is “life-threatening or chronically debilitating”), orphan designation and regulatory approval process.

³ The Australian Government and the Therapeutic Goods Administration (TGA), adopted the Therapeutic Goods Act in 1989 and amended it shortly thereafter, reaching a comprehensive orphan drug policy legislation in 1997^[41]. The process of designation considers, when possible, the decision adopted by EMA (Europe), FDA (USA) MHRA (UK), MPA (Sweden), MEB (Netherlands) and Health Canada^[48]. In July 2017, the Therapeutic Goods Regulations were updated, introducing some amendments to the original 1990 act^[41]. The main ones are (a) retain the 100% fee waiver for sponsors who would not find a financially viable way to market the drug; (b) prevalence threshold of 5/10,000 can be maxed out if a drug listed in the TGA register would not be supplied to more than 5 in 10,000 individuals each year; (c) redefine the orphan condition status as seriously debilitating or life threatening and additional criteria that aim to bring orphan products to market that treat conditions for which no therapeutic goods are registered, or that can provide significant benefit over registered therapeutic goods; (e) require the orphan indication to be medically plausible (generally a distinct disease or condition), subgroups would only be considered appropriate where the product would be ineffective in the remaining population; (f) introduce a new pathway with separate eligibility criteria to seek orphan designation for new dosage form medicines; and (g) the validity of the orphan designation lapsing after six months with possibility of six months extension in certain circumstances to ensure that the fee waiver of a related registration application is based on information that is reasonably current.

⁴ Canada represents a particular case since does not have a specific OMP framework^[49]. Formally, an OMP application follows the same process as for all other drugs. The absence of a specific orphan drug framework has often been justified by the access to the OMPs approved by the US FDA, even after a debate around a proposal of introducing a specific OMP framework in 1997^[48]. The absence of specific policies for OMPs means that incentives (e.g. grant programmes, market exclusivity, OMP designation) that apply elsewhere to encourage the development and marketing of OMPs do not exist in Canada. However, priority reviews (accelerated approval), scientific advice and fees reduction are available for companies researching on OMPs^[50]. Furthermore, an Emergency Drug Release Program has been set up to allow access to unapproved drugs^[51]. A recent proposal of OMP framework defined a prevalence threshold of ca 5/10,000 individuals.^[52]

⁵ Proposal only.

⁶ Diseases affecting more than 200,000 individuals are also included if the developing drug will not reasonably recover the costs of developing and marketing

⁷ Applicants receive a further 2 years of market exclusivity if drug complies with the paediatric investigation plan (PIP).^[53]

⁸ The ratio between drugs with approval (that obtained the authorisation to bring the product to the market) versus the designed drugs, which have been granted orphan status.^[54]

⁹ Reductions related to the review of the pre-market approval dossier, i.e. 'user fees'.

¹⁰ 40% fee reduction; free of charge for SMEs and for paediatric products.

¹¹ Varying levels of reductions.

¹² Fee reductions for regulatory activities through mitigation or deferral. Mitigation or deferral would be to reduce the potential negative impact of paying the associated fee. Fees can be deferred for a year or two if the company has not completed their first full fiscal or calendar year of operations. Fees can also be capped at a percentage of product sales.

¹³ Grants and financial incentives are managed at Member State level; for the incentives on development, France provides tax exemptions provided by the Sickness Insurance and the national regulator (AFSSAPS)^[55]; with regards to the reimbursement, two cases can be found in England, with the Cancer Drugs Fund^[56], issued by the NHS to enhance patient access, and in Sweden, where there is free of charge access to ODs if their total price exceeds 4,300 SEK^[57].

N/A: not applicable.

Source: The authors from the literature

Analytical framework

The coverage and funding recommendation for new medicines, is the outcome of a robust assessment process by HTAs. Funding recommendations are shaped by multiple factors, most of which are linked to the perceived value of the medicine. The regulatory environment and the provisions made by it, the type of medicine under consideration and how it fits in therapeutic pathways, the clinical and economic evidence and their robustness based on scientific criteria, the restrictions in new medicines' use, evidence uncertainty, social value judgements (SVJs), capturing value dimensions beyond costs and effects, and time, should be predictors of funding recommendations. Consequently, the funding recommendation, F , in country i and product j , can be positive (either unrestricted or with restrictions) or negative and can be expressed as a function of a number of parameters as shown in (1):

$$F_{ij} = f(R_{ij}, D_{ij}, C_{ij}, E_{ij}, R_{ij}, U_{ij}, S_{ij}, T_{ij}) \quad (1)$$

where R_{ij} , relates to the regulatory parameters that may influence funding recommendations by HTA. Policies related to OMPs, such as the authorisation under exceptional circumstances (AEC) enabling faster approval for compounds that are unlikely to be able to deliver phase III clinical studies [58], and, therefore should be treated differently from HTAs, is one such example. Similarly, accelerated approval pathways (AAPs) provide a signal to HTA agencies that medicines approved through these pathways may deserve expedited assessment/appraisal and/or should be subject to different levels of robustness in assessment. D_{ij} , is a group of parameters related to the medicine type or the diagnosis in question, which may be linked to national coverage priorities (e.g. reduction in the burden of disease or disease eradication), special types of medicines that are prioritised over others (e.g. oncology medicines or OMPs) and, therefore, may carry important coverage implications. C_{ij} , accounts for clinical value parameters, including clinical study type and design, which ultimately influence internal validity, the evidence on and the performance of the clinical benefit in terms of size, clinical meaningfulness and statistical significance and the extent to which the clinical benefit relies on a clinical or a surrogate endpoint. E_{ij} , outlines economic variables, which can be critical in the context of value assessment and HTA. Incremental cost effectiveness ratios (ICER) underscore the additional investment required to obtain an additional unit of benefit, and can be deemed acceptable if they fall within a certain willingness to pay threshold, which is determined nationally. ICERs can inform pricing decisions and are indicators of efficiency. Budget impact, by contrast, is an indicator of affordability. Medicines can be efficient (cost-effective) compared with the standard of care, but may not be

affordable; therefore, efficiency may be a necessary but not a sufficient condition for coverage. R_{ij} , refers to restrictions of use, which may shape the nature and extent of coverage, either on clinical (e.g. use in certain sub-populations only, where evidence on benefit is strongest), or financial grounds (e.g. a financial arrangement based on risk-sharing (RSA)), or inclusion into a special funding programme other than RSA (which can be restrictive in terms of the number of patients accessing the medicine, such as the Cancer Drugs Fund (CDF) in England, or the Exceptional Access Programme (EAP) in Ontario). Evidence shows that clinical and economic restrictions facilitate and accelerate coverage by limiting budget impact, improving cost-effectiveness, or both [59-62]. U_{ij} , relates to the impact of uncertainty, both clinical and economic, and whether these uncertainties have any impact on coverage recommendations. It captures the concerns of decision-makers on assumptions and baseline characteristics of clinical trials, design issues, treatment discontinuation, the economic evidence submitted (e.g. model and modelling, cost and utility data, comparator issues, relationship to current clinical practice) all of which render the results uncertain and non-generalisable and, if not addressed, have a negative effect on coverage recommendations. S_{ij} , refers to social value judgments (SVJs), capturing elicited (e.g. human dignity and solidarity principles in Sweden; end-of-life criteria in the UK) and not-elicited considerations (e.g. emotional and financial strain on patients and their families, treatment administration advantages) beyond a new therapy's costs and effects. SVJs may shape decision-making; these include disease severity, unmet need, innovation, and impact on family or caring, among others [6, 25, 63, 64]. Finally, T_{ij} , reflects the time element and endeavours to capture dynamic efficiency effects, which are linked to the pace of innovation in health care markets, for example, the range of choice for consumers and the performance, reliability, diffusion and quality of products available [65]. Table 13 summarises the dimensions of value outlined in (1).

Table 13 - Analytical Framework relating to value assessment of orphan drugs by HTA agencies

Parameters	Definition/Explanation
Final recommendation or funding decision	Listing decision (CADTH, NICE, PBAC, SMC); decisions classified as: L (List), LWC (List with Criteria), DNL (Do Not List); NA (not assessed), D (defer)
Regulatory robustness	
Regulatory approval type	Whether therapy has benefitted or not from an accelerated access pathway (e.g. conditional marketing authorisation (CMA) or authorisation under exceptional circumstances (AEC) by EMA; or breakthrough designation or priority review by FDA; Notice of Compliance/conditional by Health Canada)
Time to HTA/funding decision	Date of HTA recommendation/funding decision and distance from the date of Marketing Authorisation (MA)
Re-submission	Drug has had at least one prior rejection on an earlier submission to the HTA body concerned
Drug- and diagnosis-specific parameters	
Orphan drug	Relates to whether drug has orphan status/designation or not
Type of drug	Relates to whether one or more of these considerations apply (a) drug is in a priority disease area (e.g. oncology); (b) drug is the first-in-class; (c) drug is the first in disease
Financial/clinical restrictions in use	
Financial restrictions of use	Type of funding decision by competent authority and whether there is (a) some kind of risk sharing agreement (RSA), (b) inclusion into a special funding programme or budget/fund other than RSA
Clinical restrictions of use	Restrictions which may relate to the use of the medicine in patient sub-populations that are likely to benefit most
Clinical evidence considerations	
Clinical/safety parameters & evidence	Extraction of key clinical parameters that inform the performance of the new therapy: (a) Clinical pertinence/relevance of the main criteria; (b) The evidence on and performance of the clinical benefit, esp. the primary endpoint; (c) the size of the effect and its clinical significance; (d) significant safety considerations affecting performance of the drug

Trial design	Trial design may influence internal validity: (a) Pivotal/non-pivotal; (b) Type of design (randomized, non-randomized, observational, etc); (c) Phase (I/II/III/IV); (d) Blinding (double blind/open-label/Single arm trial (SAT)); (e) Comparator (active, placebo, no comparator);
Primary endpoint	Relates to whether the primary endpoint is a clinical or a surrogate endpoint
Economic evidence considerations	
ICER	Whether the ICER is above or below a notional threshold or not reported
Budget impact	Whether the budget impact is increasing, neutral/leading to savings, or it is not submitted/considered
Clinical uncertainty	
Study design	All concerns raised across trial design (blinding, phase, type of endpoint, trial length and follow up period, sample size, comparator).
Data quality	All concerns raised around the lack of long-term data or data for specific population subgroups.
Size of clinical benefit	All concerns raised around the magnitude of clinical benefit (e.g. is too little or confounded by other factors that are not related to the clinical design) the safety information, and the HRQoL data.
Relationship to current clinical practice	The clinical trials included do not reflect the current clinical practice (e.g. administration route or pre- and concomitant medication or a different use of the resource of the health system)
Population generalisability	All concerns raised around the generalizability of the population used in the clinical evidence to the country of the HTA body
Economic uncertainty	
Model & modelling	Concerns around the use of a certain model (cost-minimization or cost-utility etc.) or the modelling used (Markov/ partitioned survival model), or the extrapolation technique used for the clinical data.
Comparator	Concerns around the comparator used in the economic analysis.
Cost and utility data concerns	Concerns around the data used to build the model (e.g. costs & utility values) leading to over- or under-estimation of the ICER.
Clinical evidence used in economic model	Concerns around the suitability of the trial used to populate the clinical input in the economic model, the magnitude of the clinical benefit captured and the population included.

Clinical assumptions	Concerns around the clinical assumptions used in constructing the economic model (e.g. natural progression of disease time)
Relationship to current clinical practice	The assumptions around frequency of dosage, resource used by the health system and the concomitant medications used.
Social value judgements¹	
Chronic/Incurable/Onset in young age	The duration of the disease and the age at onset.
Small population/Rare disease	Cases when the rarity of the disease or the orphan status of the drug were recognised.
Administration route/ frequency	The route and the frequency of administration of the treatment.
Unmet need	Recognition of the unmet need for the new treatment (e.g. few or no alternatives exist, need for additional treatments, high BoD).
Social life	The ability of patients and their families/caregivers to have a normal social life, including leisure activities.
Financial burden	Financial burden created by the disease to patients or families.
Emotional burden	Emotional burden created by the disease to patients or families.
Impact on care organization	The wider impact on the health care system (e.g. administration in hospital setting or provision of specific testing)
Ethical/equality issues	Possible inequalities arising from the reimbursement of the treatment including those associated with gender, age, race, disability and/or socioeconomic status and the need to subscribe to solidarity and human dignity
Stigma	The nature of disease and its impact on patient (and their surroundings) QoL (e.g. anxiety from the disease leading to social stigma).
Productivity	Indirect benefits from the treatment, (e.g. being able to return to work, improving functional capacities) for patients and carers
Aim of the drug	Valuations may differ depending on aim of drug in context: (a) preventive, (b) offering symptomatic relief, or (c) curative
Disabling nature	Disabling nature of the disease as well as the capacity of the treatment to reduce the disability/slow the progression of the disability
Impact in terms of public health	Refers to the health impact of the new therapy at the community level (e.g. broader or diffusion effects at population level)
End of life	Refers to a treatment for a condition towards the end of life and the benefit of a treatment at the end of life is valued more highly

Innovation	Innovative nature compound (e.g. new substance(s)/indication(s) in R&D or in the process of MA, new formulation(s), new treatment method(s))
Other considerations	Any consideration beyond the drug or its direct/indirect effects on society (e.g. market forecasts for other drugs & price reductions)

Source: The authors based on enhancement of the conceptual framework in Angelis, Lange & Kanavos (2018), Nicod & Kanavos (2012) and Nicod & Kanavos (2016).

Methods

Based on the analytical framework outlined in (2) and in order to address the study objectives, we define the country settings, the sample and the analysis, both descriptive and quantitative.

1.1 Country selection

Four countries and their HTA bodies (Australia (PBAC), Canada (CADTH/pCODR), England (NICE) and Scotland (SMC)) were selected based on the following criteria: (a) existence of a long-standing HTA agency and process; (b) practice of clinical and cost-effectiveness/cost-utility analysis; (c) consideration of different approaches to HTA (societal in England, Scotland and health system-related in Australia and, at federal level, Canada); (d) variability in terms of a regulatory framework in operation, which determines whether products can be designated as OMPs and provides incentives for OMP development (this exists in England, Scotland and Australia, but does not exist in Canada) and in terms of eligibility for OMP designation based on prevalence, which means that while a product can be designated as OMP in one setting, it may not in another; to that end, the prevalence thresholds differ between Europe [39, 40] (which guides developments in England and Scotland) and Australia [41]; and (e) public availability of HTA reports and their recommendations.

While HTA recommendations in England, Scotland and Australia also indicate funding recommendations at national level, CADTH/pCODR's recommendations do not amount to funding recommendations as these are taken at provincial level [66, 67]; In order to include funding recommendations from the Canadian setting we included the coverage offered by Ontario, the largest province, accounting for 39% of Canada's population, through its Public Drug Programs.

4.2 Sample selection

We studied compound-indication pairs receiving MA as OMPs by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) [67, 68]; between January 2008 and December 2017 and searched the equivalent regulatory agencies in Canada (Health Canada) and Australia (Therapeutic Goods Administration – TGA) over the same period to ascertain whether they had received MA in those jurisdictions. We subsequently looked at national HTA agencies and included all the EMA-approved OMPs that were evaluated by at least three out of four HTA agencies in the study countries CADTH (Canada), NICE (England), PBAC (Australia) and SMC (Scotland). Of interest was the extent to which the selected sample of EMA OMP-designated products, carried an OMP designation in Australia, while Canada does not have an OMP policy.

This resulted in a sample of 42 compound-indication pairs¹, 20 of which were oncology-related, the remainder non-oncology-related, across a total of 27 indications. The most recent publicly available HTA recommendations in the four countries, as well as all prior rejections and the associated rationale, were obtained through the online databases of the respective HTA agencies. HTA data was collected and analyzed based on the analytical framework outlined in the previous section, which was designed to pick up all relevant information; this in turn, would enable the identification of determinants of HTA/coverage recommendations beyond cost, effectiveness and safety considerations [25]. In 2017, 11 of the 28 drugs authorized by the EU were approved for oncology indications, five of which were designated orphan [69]. Although our starting point to select drugs designated as orphan at EU level could not be carried through in other jurisdictions because of national differences surrounding OMP policies or orphan status/designation, this provided a useful distinction to study how OMP status may influence HTA recommendations.

4.3 Analysis

The analysis comprised a descriptive and a quantitative component. The descriptive analysis focused on a number of endpoints: (a) comparison of HTA outcomes across the study countries, by distinguishing these between unrestricted (denoted as “L” - list), restricted (denoted as “LWC” – list with criteria), deferred (denoted as “D”) or rejected (denoted as “DNL” – do not list), also taking into account their status (OMP or not); (b) time from MA to HTA/funding recommendation across countries and types of products; (c) similarities and differences between countries in the way clinical and evidence is assessed for the same technology; (d) assessment of therapeutic benefit and the extent to which this relies on clinical or surrogate endpoints from pivotal clinical trials; (e) the uncertainties raised and their role in decision-making; and (f) the role of SVJs in prioritisation and decision-making.

Based on the analytical framework outlined in (1) and In order to analyse whether any of the factors discussed therein had any significant effect on HTA/funding recommendations, we deployed a panel data model, where the dependent variable was the achievement of positive (i.e. L, LWC) versus a negative (DNL) HTA recommendation. A Fixed Effects model was used to control for all time-invariant differences between the 4 study countries assuring that the estimated coefficients are not biased due to omitted time-invariant characteristics. Following on from (1), the model was:

¹ From 2008 onwards, a total of 98 designated orphan drugs received MA in Europe, of which 40% were for oncology indications

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + x_{it}^T \beta + v_{it}, \quad (2)$$

with $i = 1, \dots, N$ and $t = 1, \dots, T$ representing products and agencies, respectively and where the dependent variable, y_{it} is categorical (positive/negative funding decision). The vector x_{it} contains Z strictly exogenous variables, while the random variable α_i represents agency-specific effects, possibly correlated with x_{it} ; v_{it} is an observation-specific error term. Based on (2), the dependent variable was $DECISION_{ij}$. A number of independent variables were also included: first, $ORPHAN_{ij}$ tests whether OMP designation. Second, $TYPE_{ij}$ tests the hypothesis that medicine types (oncology vs non-oncology) determine the direction of HTA recommendations. Third, two variables were included related to the clinical performance of the study compounds: $ENDPOINT_{ij}$ tested whether the type of endpoint (clinical or surrogate) had an influence on the direction of HTA recommendations; considering that clinical endpoints are preferred [70, 71], although surrogate endpoints can proxy clinical endpoints [72] and can be considered by decision-makers under the condition that they are justified”[73]. $QUALITY_{ij}$ captured the quality and strength of clinical evidence, synthesizing key concerns from clinical variables, based on whether these concerns were addressed by the submission and, if not, the possibility for bias increases [74, 75]. We operationalised this variable by considering three critical elements: concerns with trial design, concerns with the comparator, and concerns with endpoint type. The quality is high if all three types of concerns are addressed by the HTA submission, medium if two of the three concerns are addressed and low if one of the three types of concerns are addressed. Fourth, restrictions of use were proxied through the $FUNDING_{ij}$ variable, which captures the availability or not of risk-sharing agreements or other funding modalities, which are thought to be positively associated with coverage compared with no agreement. Fifth, SVJ_{ij} is defined as the intensity of social value judgements (SVJs) that have informed the final recommendation and may have played a role in decision-making. The reported SVJs were aggregated in each compound-indication pair case and an index was produced indicating potentially high or potentially low impact. The variable SVJ_{ij} is a composite index of all SVJs and assumes equal weight for each, which does not enable inferences to be made about certain important considerations in this space. The SVJ index was the numeric sum of all social value judgements recognised by HTA agencies in their recommendation rationale and ranged between moderate and high ($SVJ_{Moderate} \leq 6$; and $SVJ_{High} \geq 7$). Sixth, independently of the SVJ index, we considered the effect of disease severity and unmet need by operationalising $SEVERITY_{ij}$ and $NEED_{ij}$ respectively as binary variables, the hypothesis being that disease severity or unmet medical need might have a positive effect on coverage recommendations even in the presence of incomplete or immature clinical data. In some settings, high quality of clinical evidence combined with the treatment

of a severe disease, are pre-conditions for a new therapy to be perceived as a breakthrough, which carries implications for both coverage and price [76]. Seventh, by creating the variable $ORPHAN_{ij}$ we tested whether rarity, captured by orphan designation, independently of other considerations, had an impact on HTA/funding recommendations. The underlying hypothesis is that orphan designation does have a positive impact on coverage and funding recommendations. Eighth, we created an uncertainty index (U_index_{ij}), as the numeric sum of (clinical and economic) concerns raised for each compound-indication pair, including an assessment of the quality and strength of clinical evidence [74, 75], based on how HTAs perceived this evidence; the index was binary and classified into moderate and high ($U_index_{Moderate} \leq 8$; and $U_index_{High} \geq 9$). The hypothesis was that the higher the uncertainty index score, the higher the probability of negative coverage. Finally, we accounted for a number of other effects in the model, which we thought they could influence the direction of HTA recommendations, such as ICER values ($ICER_{ij}$), budget impact ($BUDGET_{ij}$), prior rejection by the HTA agency ($RESUBMIT_{ij}$), the number of days between MA and coverage decision ($DAYS_{ij}$), and dynamic effects, captured by the year of MA ($YEAR_{ij}$).

To test the robustness of the model, the results of the main equation were compared with the ones obtained after including and excluding other explanatory variables as well with the results obtained with a standard OLS regression analysis. If the results were similar to those from the main FE equation, they would confirm the effect of the above identified variables on the final HTA reimbursement decision. The variables deployed in quantitative analysis, alongside the hypotheses they are testing, are shown on Table 14.

Table 14 - Variable definition, coding and justification

Variable name	Hypothesis	Type
DECISION _{ij}	Positive (unrestricted & restricted) vs. negative (rejections) coverage recommendations	Binary: 1=List and List with Criteria; 2=Do not List
TYPE _{ij}	The H ₀ is that oncology indications are less likely to reach approval and funding relative to non-oncology indications, based on significant uncertainties	Binary: 1 = oncology product; 2 = non-oncology product
TIME _{ij}	The H ₀ is that time may be associated with positive recommendation and funding decision	Continuous: time (days between MA and coverage)
TIME _{ij} ²	The H ₀ is that time sq may be associated with positive recommendation and funding decision	Continuous: time squared (days bet MA and coverage)
ENDPOINT _{ij}	The H ₀ is that a clinical endpoint is more likely to lead to a positive recommendation and a surrogate endpoint is more likely to lead to a negative recommendation	Binary: 1=clinical endpoint; 2=surrogate endpoint
FUNDING _{ij}	The H ₀ is that an RSA is more likely to be positively associated with coverage compared with a special funding arrangement, or no agreement related to risk sharing on special funding	Categorical: 1 = RSA; 2 = special funding arrangement (SFA) (not RSA); 3 = none, implying no RSA or SFA; 4 = not funded
ICER _{ij}	The H ₀ is that a high ICER is associated with negative coverage	Categorical: 1=no ICER submitted; 2=ICER<£100,000; 3=ICER>£100,000
RESUBMIT _{ij}	The H ₀ is that a resubmission following a rejection is positively associated with coverage	Binary: 1 = at least one prior rejection; 2 = no prior rejection
UNCERTAINTY _{ij}	The H ₀ is that the higher the uncertainty index score, the higher the probability that it will be associated with negative coverage	Binary: 1 = low (1-8 clinical/economic uncertainties); and 2 = high (>8 clinical/economic uncertainties)
SVJ _{ij}	Assuming that all SVJs carry equal weight, the H ₀ is that the higher the index, the more likely that the compound-indication pair will achieve positive coverage and vice versa for a low index	Binary: 1 = low impact (1-6 SVJs) and 2 = high impact (7-12 SVJs)
BUDGET _{ij}	The H ₀ is that a positive budget impact, leading to more resources required to fund the new therapy is likely to be associated with negative coverage (rejection)	Categorical: 1 = positive budget impact (leading to higher spend); 2 = budget impact neutral or leading to savings; and 3 = no budget impact suggested/ unknown or uncertain.

ORPHAN _{ij}	The H ₀ is that an orphan-designated drug carries a higher probability of a positive coverage recommendation ¹	Binary: 1=yes; 2=no
SEVERITY _{ij}	The H ₀ is that severity should be positively associated with a positive coverage decision.	Binary: 1=yes; 2=no
NEED _{ij}	The H ₀ is that this variable should be positively associated with a positive coverage decision.	Binary: 1=yes; 2=no
QUALITY _{ij}	The H ₀ is that high quality and strength of clinical evidence should be positively associated with a coverage decision;	Categorisation is based on the opinion of HTA committees on the quality and strength of the available evidence, which is explicitly mentioned in the final HTA report.
YEAR	The H ₀ is that longer time is positively associated with a coverage decision;	Continuous: year in sample (1, 2, ..., 10)

Notes: ¹ These are 2 non-cancer drug indication pairs (pirferidone, nintedanib both for cystic fibrosis) and 9 cancer drug-indication pairs (cabozantinib (thyroid cancer); carfilzomib (multiple myeloma); daratumumab (multiple myeloma); ibrutinib (3 indications: chronic lymphocytic leukaemia, mantle cell lymphoma and Waldemstrom's Macroglobulinaemia); obinutumab (2 indications: chronic lymphocytic leukaemia and Follicular Lymphoma); and ofatumumab (chronic lymphoblastic lymphoma) not given OMP status in Australia.

Source: The authors.

Results

5.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 15 summarises the key sample characteristics, while Appendix Table 1 summarises these at compound-indication pair level, including the relevant indication. In terms of orphan status, none of the sample compound-indication pairs were classed as orphan in Canada, due to the lack of an OMP policy including orphan designation. As rarity was benchmarked against the EMA classification, all sample compound-indication pairs assessed in England and Scotland carried that designation. In Australia, 58% of the sample compound-indication pairs were designated as orphan. In total, 151 HTA reports (Canada=36, England=42, Australia=36, Scotland=37) were identified for the 42 compound-indication pairs across the study countries, resulting in 151 HTA recommendations and funding decisions. Most submissions (84%) received either a positive (L=9%) or a positive but restricted recommendation (LWC=75%), while the remainder received a negative recommendation (DNL=16%). England issued the highest proportion of positive recommendations (LWC = 97%, L=3%), followed by Scotland (LWC= 70%, L= 11%), Canada at federal level (LWC=67%, L=14%) and Australia (LWC=64%, L= 8%). On the other hand, Australia had the highest number of negative HTA recommendations (DNL=28%), followed by Scotland and Canada at federal level (19% each). In Canada, a positive recommendation at federal level (by CADTH) leads to negotiation on coverage at provincial level under each province’s drug benefit programme(s) [52]. However, even medicines (e.g. plerixafor and romiplostim) that have received negative recommendations at federal level can be funded at regional level. Overall, of the 36 drug-indication pairs that were submitted for assessment, Ontario funded 20 products through the Exceptional Access Program (EAP), 7 were funded by Cancer Care Ontario’s New Drug Funding Programme (CCO NDFP) and one was on limited use (tobramycin oral for cystic fibrosis).

Table 15 - Sample characteristics & qualitative assessment

HTA/funding outcome				
Outcome type (L/LWC/DNL)	List 13 (9%)	List With Criteria 114 (75%)	Do Not List 24 (16%)	Total 151 (100%)
N (% of total)				
Country (Agency)				
Canada (CADTH)	5 (38%)	24 (21%)	7 (29%)	36 (24%)
England (NICE/NHSE)	1 (8%)	41 (36%)	0 (0%)	42 (28%)

Australia (PBAC)	3 (23%)	23 (20%)	10 (42%)	36 (24%)
Scotland (SMC)	4 (31%)	26 (23%)	7 (29%)	37 (24%)
Orphan status¹				
No	7 (54%)	29 (25%)	10 (42%)	46 (30%)
Yes	6 (46%)	85 (75%)	14 (58%)	105 (70%)
Type of medicine				
Oncology	5 (38%)	62 (54%)	13 (54%)	80 (53%)
Non-oncology	8 (62%)	52 (46%)	11 (46%)	71 (47%)
Primary endpoint				
Surrogate	9 (69%)	98 (86%)	22 (92%)	129 (85%)
Clinical	4 (31%)	16 (14%)	2 (8%)	22 (15%)
Funding mechanism				
Risk sharing	0 (0%)	51 (45%)	0 (0%)	51 (34%)
Special funding agreement	5 (38%)	18 (16%)	4 (17%)	27 (18%)
No risk sharing	8 (62%)	38 (33%)	7 (29%)	53 (35%)
Not funded	0 (0%)	7 (6%)	13 (54%)	20 (13%)
Prior rejection by HTA				
No	9 (69%)	80 (70%)	14 (58%)	103 (68%)
Yes	4 (31%)	34 (30%)	10 (42%)	48 (32%)
Clinical and economic uncertainty				
U_index _{Moderate} ≤ 8	2 (15%)	7 (6%)	3 (13%)	12 (8%)
U_index _{High} ≥ 9	11 (85%)	107 (94%)	21 (77%)	139 (92%)
Quality and strength of clinical evidence				
Low	10 (77%)	77 (68%)	15 (62%)	102 (68%)
High	3 (23%)	37 (32%)	9 (38%)	49 (32%)
Social Value Judgement index				

SVJ _{Moderate} ≤6	9 (69%)	53 (46%)	14 (58%)	76 (50%)
SVJ _{High} ≥7	4 (31%)	61 (54%)	10 (42%)	75 (50%)
Severe disease				
No	4 (31%)	38 (33%)	6 (25%)	48 (32%)
Yes	9 (69%)	76 (67%)	18 (75%)	103 (68%)
Unmet need				
No	6 (46%)	38 (33%)	9 (38%)	53 (35%)
Yes	7 (54%)	76 (67%)	15 (62%)	98 (65%)
Budget impact				
Positive BI	3 (23%)	56 (49%)	12 (50%)	71 (47%)
Negative/neutral BI	1 (8%)	7 (6%)	0 (0.0%)	8 (5%)
No BI	9 (69%)	51 (45%)	12 (50%)	72 (48%)
ICER (categorical)				
No ICER reported	1 (8%)	28 (25%)	6 (25%)	35 (23%)
Low ICER (< £ 100,000)	9 (69%)	66 (58%)	9 (37.5%)	84 (56%)
High ICER (> £ 100,000)	3 (23%)	20 (18%)	9 (37.5%)	32 (21%)
Days from MA to HTA/funding decision				
Mean (SD)	638.2 (482.6)	770.6 (665.9)	548.5 (475.1)	726.2 (636.6)
Min	63	24	1	1
Max	1,234	2,763	1,603	2,763
ICER (GBP)²				
Mean (SD)	494,209 (1,466,940)	739,488 (3,338,502)	240,434 (315,2833)	635,781 (2,910,304)
Min	24,546	3,282	17,187	3,282
Max	5,147,217	28,301,471	1,009,276	28,301,471

Note: ¹ No orphan status designation is present in Canada.

² ICER data are missing for a number of drugs reimbursed by NHS England.

Source: The authors.

Twenty of the sample compound-indication pairs were related to an oncology indication, resulting in 80 HTA submissions (53%), while the remainder related to non-oncology indications (47%, n=71). In the vast majority of cases HTA recommendations relied on surrogate (85%, n=129) rather than clinical (15%, n=22) endpoints. The use of surrogate endpoints as primary endpoints resulted in a positive (L=9) or restrictive (LWC=98) recommendation in 83% of cases, while the remainder were rejections (DNL=22, 17%). Of the submissions relying on clinical as the primary endpoint, the vast majority received positive or restricted recommendations (92%, n=20), while rejections were found only in 2 cases (8%).

A significant amount of time lapses between MA and HTA/funding recommendation. Overall, negative HTA recommendations are associated with a lower mean number of months (18.3 months) compared with positive recommendations (L = 21.3; LWC = 25.7 months). However, significant variations exist both at country level and at broad indication level (cancer vs. non-cancer), which are shown on Figure 1. The time from MA to HTA recommendation takes longest in NICE for cancer and PBAC for non-cancer drugs (36.6 and 23.9 months respectively), and the average time from MA to HTA recommendation is shortest in Canada at federal and provincial level for both cancer and non-cancer indication drugs (17.8 and 19.2 months, respectively) and is not incompatible to what has been observed elsewhere [77]. This appears surprising as Canada does not have an OMP regulation in place. For some cancer drug-indication pairs, HTA recommendations were issued before MA in Canada (levatinib) and Australia (azacytidine and cabozantinib), while others may take years to be recommended by HTAs (e.g. teduglutide for short bowel syndrome took 67 months following MA to be recommended in Scotland) and initial rejections followed by resubmission may prolong this time even further (e.g. pirferidone in England and icatibant acetate in Australia took 84 months each).

Figure 11- Months between Regulatory Marketing Authorization and Coverage Recommendations for Cancer vs. Non-Cancer Orphan Medicinal Products in 4 countries

Note: Australia (PBAC), Canada (CADTH), Canada (Ontario) England (NICE), and Scotland (SMC).

Source: The authors from HTA reports, 2019.

All HTA agencies preferred to cover drug-indication pairs either with clinical restrictions or with some form of managed entry agreement (MEA), predominantly of a financial type (e.g. price discounts). Thirty four percent of all recommendations were subject to a risk sharing agreement (n=51), while special funding agreements were available in 18% of all cases (n=27), the latter found in the Canadian province of Ontario. England was the country with the highest percentage of risk sharing agreements as a funding modality (45%), followed by Scotland (41%) and Australia (14%). In Ontario, for drugs that are not listed on the Ontario Drug Benefit (ODB) Formulary, the Exceptional Access Program (EAP) facilitates coverage based on patient eligibility [78], while the Cancer Care Ontario New Drug Funding Program (CCO NDFP), funds novel and high-priced intravenous cancer drugs which are administered in outpatient settings [79, 80] In England, several high cost orphan drugs are directly commissioned and funded by NHS England and are accessed by eligible patients in a small number of hospitals [81]. Some drugs such as teduglutide and macitentan are funded if there exists an individual funding request (IFR) for patients who are believed to have exceptional conditions and cannot benefit from available NHS treatments [67].

All HTA submissions included key evidence from clinical trials and some kind of economic evidence, both of which are summarised in Figure 2. In terms of clinical evidence, phase III studies composed the highest proportion of clinical evidence submitted, (CADTH=55%, NICE=36%, PBAC=23%, SMC=60%) followed by indirect comparisons including network meta-analyses (e.g. retrospective studies, historical studies) (CADTH=2%, NICE=24%, PBAC=36%, SMC=6%) and phase II studies (CADTH=18%, NICE=19%, PBAC=11%, SMC=14%). Phase I and Phase IV studies are referred the least (CADTH=2%, NICE=3%, PBAC=4%, SMC=1%) and (NICE=1%, PBAC=1%), respectively. With regards to economic evidence, cost utility analysis was the most frequently used type across all HTA bodies. Additionally, cost minimisation studies were used widely in Australia, while other types of economic analysis included cost offset analysis and discrete choice analysis.

Figure 12 - Clinical and Economic Evidence Submitted to HTA Agencies

Source: The authors from HTA reports, 2019.

Forty eight of 151 submissions (32%) were previously rejected by HTAs but receiving a prior rejection did not seem to have a significant impact on the final funding recommendation. Re-submissions were mostly made to Australia (52% of the total), followed by Canada (24%), Scotland (20%) and England (4%). Canada had the highest rejection rate following a re-submission (25%), followed by Australia (15%). The Australian PBAC seems to negotiate for MEAs after re-submissions, using the likelihood of negative recommendations as a bargaining tool. Overall, prior rejections increased the odds of a negative final recommendation, compared with medicines that had no prior rejection (21% versus 14%, respectively).

The uncertainty index was very high (92%, n=139) across all compound-indication pairs, while the quality and strength of evidence was also low across the board (68% of cases, n=102). Canada and Scotland reported the highest percentage of high quality and strength of clinical evidence (Canada=47%, Scotland=43%) while England was evidently the lowest (19%). Contrary to what would have been expected, 15% of submissions with a reported moderate uncertainty were rejected versus 25% of those with a high uncertainty. Figure 3 shows the distribution of clinical and economic uncertainties raised in HTA recommendations across all HTA submissions. The total number of clinical uncertainties identified were considerable in number (n= 479), of which lack of data (e.g. biased data, lack of long-term trial results) was the most often raised clinical uncertainty (CADTH=24% of all cases, NICE=26%, PBAC=31%, SMC=29%). Lack of data is a common problem for many clinical trials as the duration of trials may not allow the collection of sufficient data. Trial design and clinical benefit concerns were other important sources of clinical uncertainty, (CADTH=20%, NICE=19%, PBAC=23% SMC=25%) and (CADTH= 17%, NICE=20%, PBAC=17%, SMC=14%), respectively. A significant number of economic uncertainties were identified across the entire dataset. Uncertainties in the efficacy of clinical data led to uncertainties in the economic model. Lack of data input (e.g. utility values, transition probabilities, costs), the clinical evidence uncertainty and its suitability in economic models and modelling were the most common problems for all HTA organisations accounting for the majority of economic uncertainties (CADTH=69% of all cases, NICE=63%, PBAC=62%, SMC=63%). The existence of significant uncertainties can lead to a rejection. For example, PBAC rejected the listing of nusinersen for the treatment spinal muscular atrophy, due to the uncertainty about clinical effectiveness in terms of extent and durability of response despite high unmet need. Contrarywise, significant uncertainties do not always affect coverage recommendations negatively; for example, SMC approved pirferidone for the treatment of IPF despite the uncertainty around clinical practice, the size of benefit and generalisability of patient population to the Scottish population.

Figure 13 - Clinical and Economic Uncertainties Addressed

Source: The authors from HTA reports, 2019.

Half of all compound-indication pairs had a high SVJ index (n=75). Of the individual SVJs, severity was explicitly recognized in 68% (n=103) of all HTA submissions, followed by unmet medical need (65%, n=98). However, nearly the same proportion of pharmaceutical products received a positive recommendation regardless of whether they were indicated to treat severe illnesses (82%) or not (87%). Similarly, 84% of drugs addressing an unmet need were either listed or listed with criteria versus 83% if they did not address any unmet need. The classification of SVJs and variation by country are shown in Figure 4. Overall, 641 SVJs were identified in the HTA reports, which are both disease-

(64%) and treatment-related (36%). Disease related SVJs (e.g. limited life expectancy) are given high importance across all HTA reports (CADTH=65%, NICE=57%, PBAC= 67%, SMC= 66%), whereas treatment related SVJs (improvements in quality of life or drug being first-in-class) are recognised to a lesser extent (CADTH=35%, NICE=43%, PBAC=33%, SMC=34%). Broader considerations, such as equality, were also considered, particularly if not captured by any of the other SVJs or to ensure that appropriate clarification was provided in connection with the rationale for decision-making and national legislation [82, 83].

Figure 14 - Frequently Raised Social Value Judgements across a sample of 42 OMPs and 4 countries

Source: The authors from HTA reports, 2019.

Forty eight percent of all submissions (n=72) did not report a budget impact, 47% (n=71) had a positive budget impact, implying an increase in health care spending in the indication concerned, while only

5% (n=8) reported a negative or neutral budget impact. Scotland had the highest percentage of positive budget impact (32%) followed by Canada (31%), Australia (20%) and England (17%).

The maximum percentage of high ICER values, intended as above or equal to £100,000, was reported in Canada (CADTH = 47%) while the lowest values were reported in England and Australia (NICE and PBAC = 12.5%). Intuitively, NICE and PBAC had the highest proportion of low ICER values, intended as below GBP100,000 (29%). NICE also reported the highest percentage of missing ICER values (40%), followed by SMC (29%), PBAC (23%) and CADTH (9%). It is also important to highlight that 89% of the drugs that received a positive recommendation (L or LWC), reported a low ICER value while only 71% of those reporting a high ICER value were recommended for funding.

5.2 Quantitative analysis

The regression is estimated using a Fixed Effects (or within) estimator, and standard errors are clustered at the HTA agency level. A Fixed Effects model for panel data was chosen after having compared the Fixed Effects and the Random Effect models with the Hausman test ($\chi^2 = 30.05, Prob > \chi^2 = 0.0027$) [84]. The Fixed Effects model was also found superior to the Pooled OLS model by inspecting the F-statistic of the estimated fixed effect model (Table 2, Appendix). A modified Wald test for group-wise heteroskedasticity was also run on equation (A) ($\chi^2 = 9.60, Prob > \chi^2 = 0.0478$). The test was not significant and therefore the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity (or constant variance) could not be rejected. Heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors were therefore not produced in the analysis.

The results are presented in Table 16. In line with the hypothesis, being designated as an orphan drug significantly predicts whether a drug will be listed or listed with criteria across the different HTA agencies ($\beta=0.257, p=0.022$). Moving from a surrogate to a clinical primary endpoint also significantly predicts whether a drug will be listed or listed with criteria, even if at a lower significance level ($\beta=0.135, p=0.051$). Passing from a risk-sharing agreement to any other funding modality impacts negatively the chances of a pharmaceutical product to be recommended for coverage with or without restrictions. Specifically, not having a risk sharing or a special funding agreement is correlated to a sizeable decrease in the probability of a drug to be listed or listed with criteria ($\beta=-0.991, p=0.000$). Finally, compared with a non-oncology medical product, an oncology product is associated with a statistically significant decrease in the probability of a drug to be listed or listed with criteria ($\beta=-0.165, p-value=0.002$).

The within groups, between groups and overall R-squared values for the main equation (equation A in Table 16) are 0.48, 0.22 and 0.20 respectively, meaning that the independent variables respectively explain 48%, 22% and 20% of the variation in the dependent variable final funding decision. The F value is 9.63 ($p=0.000$). This provides a basis to reject the null hypothesis that all first-stage coefficients are equal to zero, or that none of the explanatory variables affect the final HTA reimbursement decision.

To test the robustness of the results presented above, the results of the main equation (A) are compared with the ones obtained after including and excluding explanatory variables (Table 14, equations B, C, D, E and F) as well as with the results obtained with a standard OLS regression analysis (Table 2, Appendix). For the extended equations (B, C, D, E and F) the overall R-squared values range from 0.19 to 0.20. Furthermore, the F values are 16.66, 10.47, 9.57, 9.60 and 4.14 in equations B, C, D, E and F, respectively. In equation F the number of observations drops to 111 from 143 due to the missing values of the variable ICER, now included in the analysis.

Removing (*prior rejection (resubmission), budget impact, clinical and economic uncertainty*) or adding variables (*quality and strength of clinical evidence, severity, unmet need, days to HTA reimbursement decision², HTA funding year*) does not have any significant effect as results remain consistent with the results of the main equation, with *primary endpoint, funding modality, orphan status* remaining statistically significant, even if at different significance levels, across models (A) to (E). Interactions between variables, for example, orphan with need, or orphan with severity have also been tested, but have shown not to be statistically significant.

The analyses show that, regardless of the model run, the variables *prior rejection, budget impact, clinical and economic uncertainty, quality and strength of clinical evidence, severity, unmet need, days to HTA reimbursement decision², HTA funding year* did not significantly predict whether a drug will be funded (with or without restrictions).

Also, in line with hypothesis, running the six regressions with a Pooled OLS controlling for the HTA agency variable does not change the results as the explanatory variables' coefficients and the significance levels remain constant across all models (Appendix Table 2).

Table 16 - Panel data analysis (fixed effects) for HTA final funding recommendation (HTA Agency represents the panels)

	A	B	C	D	E	F
Variables	Coefficients (SE)					
<i>Constant</i>	0.890*** (0.144)	1.015*** (0.093)	1.008*** (0.104)	0.980*** (0.116)	0.909** (0.142)	1.170*** (0.130)
<i>TYPE</i>	-0.165*** (0.052)	-0.144*** (0.047)	-0.169*** (0.057)	-0.172*** (0.057)	-0.164*** (0.053)	-0.189*** (0.068)
<i>DAYS</i>	3.87 e-05 (3.82 e-05)	3.33 e-05 (3.73 e-05)	3.79 e-05 (3.84 e-05)	4 e-05 (3.87 e-05)	3.74 e-05 (3.81 e-05)	-1.33 e-5 (1.32 e-04)
<i>ENDPOINT</i>	0.135* (0.068)	0.134** (0.066)	0.140** (0.068)	0.139** (0.068)	0.134* (0.069)	0.149** (0.072)
<i>FUNDING (risk-sharing base case)</i>						
<i>Special funding agreement</i>	-0.793*** (0.133)	-0.783*** (0.138)	-0.797*** (0.141)	-0.792*** (0.141)	-0.796*** (0.142)	-0.788*** (0.151)
<i>No funding agreement reported</i>	-0.109* (0.063)	-0.094* (0.056)	-0.114* (0.062)	-0.107* (0.063)	-0.115* (0.062)	-0.131* (0.067)
<i>Not funded</i>	-0.991*** (0.098)	-0.973*** (0.095)	-0.991*** (0.098)	-0.989*** (0.099)	-0.992*** (0.099)	-0.988*** (0.107)
<i>ORPHAN</i>	0.257** (0.110)	0.225** (0.106)	0.237** (0.108)	0.242** (0.109)	0.253** (0.110)	

ICER (no ICER base case)

Low ICER (< £100,000)

0.056
(0.068)

High ICER (> £100,000)

0.110
(0.077)

RESUBMIT

0.020
(0.050)

0.027
(0.054)

0.029
(0.054)

0.017
(0.054)

0.008
(0.056)

QUALITY

-0.034
(0.058)

-0.034
(0.058)

-0.040
(0.062)

BUDGET (high budget impact base case)

Low budget impact

-0.012
(0.110)

-0.001
(0.111)

0.004
(0.116)

-0.017
(0.110)

0.007
(0.117)

No budget impact reported

0.057
(0.055)

0.041
(0.052)

0.050
(0.055)

0.051
(0.054)

0.037
(0.054)

UNCERTAINTY

0.077
(0.091)

0.084
(0.091)

SVJ

0.024
(0.054)

0.030
(0.054)

SEVERITY

-0.002
(0.052)

-0.012
(0.056)

NEED

0.009
(0.055)

<i>DAYS SQUARED</i>						2.50 e-08 (5.45 e-08)
<i>YEAR</i>						-0.001 (0.012)
Sample Size	143	143	143	143	143	143
R-squared						
<i>Within</i>	0.4765	0.4691	0.4736	0.4750	0.4757	0.4643
<i>Between</i>	0.2168	0.2050	0.2044	0.2117	0.2118	0.2044
<i>Overall</i>	0.1991	0.2019	0.1985	0.2000	0.1980	0.2602
Rho	0.7372	0.7235	0.7314	0.7313	0.7366	0.5650
F-statistic	9.63	16.66	10.47	9.57	9.60	6.66
Prob (F-statistic)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Notes: Standard errors are reported in parentheses; *, **, *** indicates significance at the 90%, 95%, and 99% level, respectively.

Discussion and policy implications

This study analyses the factors associated with HTA recommendations on OMPs in four countries. While the overall regulatory framework provides a favourable starting point for the approval and market access of OMPs, value assessment, efficiency, budget impact and pricing are important considerations for their reimbursement by health care systems.

First, there are differences across settings on OMP-related regulatory frameworks, which impact orphan designation and the status of individual products as orphan. Of this study's 42 compound-indication pairs, all had an OMP designation in Europe, 58% were designated as OMP in Australia and none in Canada. Where an OMP designation does not exist any benefits that may accrue from the policies related to them, do not apply. Our analysis found that OMP designation significantly more likely predicts whether a drug will be recommended for coverage (with or without restrictions). This is compatible with current practice as HTA agencies recognise the peculiarities of OMPs, may apply different WTP thresholds, accept higher uncertainty, or implement lower evidence thresholds [29, 85, 86]. Despite the overall positive pre-disposition towards OMPs, we found that the type of product did have an effect on the direction of coverage, in that oncology OMPs were associated with a statistically significant decrease in the probability to be recommended for coverage compared with a non-oncology OMP. This finding could be interpreted as an indication of scepticism around the magnitude and importance of benefits accruing from oncology vs non-oncology products.

Second, nearly all sample compounds were associated with significant uncertainties in their clinical and economic evidence. The uncertainty index was found to be very high (92%, n=139) across all compound-indication pairs and countries, while the quality and strength of evidence was also low across the board (68% of cases, n=102), however, neither constituted sufficient grounds for rejection. While it is widely accepted that OMPs are facing difficulties in the procurement of clinical evidence [35, 85] HTAs have highlighted these as part of their assessment processes. Indeed, despite the flexibility in the assessment of OMPs by HTA agencies, we found that a significant number of compounds (32%) had been rejected at least once. Although this percentage is significant, our analysis showed that it did not have a statistically significant effect on the probability of positive recommendations.

Third, time to access was shown to vary across compounds and study countries, and averaged 23 months from the date of MA. While this is similar to what has been reported elsewhere [77, 87, 88], it could be the case that prior rejections could have influenced the length of time to reach a coverage recommendation. Equally, this may be further propagated by the need to conclude risk mitigation

strategies that will enable coverage based on affordable terms by local payers. Surprisingly, in Canada, with no OMP policy in place, time to access was found to be shorter compared with the other study countries. This could be explained in part by Canada being an immediate recipient of FDA marketing authorisations, which may influence its own MA stance. Making coverage recommendations prior to receiving MA was observed in Canada and Australia may sound counter-intuitive, but can be explained by the existence of parallel review processes in these countries enabling simultaneous assessment by both regulatory agencies and HTAs.

Fourth, the vast majority of OMPs have received positive HTA recommendations and have been included in national benefits catalogues, despite relying almost exclusively on evidence from surrogate endpoints. Our analysis showed that moving from a surrogate to a clinical primary endpoint significantly predicted whether a drug would be recommended or recommended with restrictions. Although this seems to be a direct recognition of the challenges related to the procurement of robust clinical evidence from the perspective of sponsors, decision-makers still have valid concerns about the reliance on surrogate endpoints to inform coverage and access.

Fifth, to cope with the uncertainties in clinical or economic evidence, including re-submissions following an initial rejection, health systems consider RSAs to mitigate risk and as options to enable access to OMPs [62]. Most RSAs are financial-based agreements (discounts, price-volume agreements or budget caps). Where poor cost effectiveness was reported, RSAs seemed to have an effect on changing the recommendation from negative to positive by improving the ICER. Based on our analysis, not having an RSA was correlated with a sizeable decrease in the probability of a compound being recommended. Additionally, transitioning from an RSA to other funding modalities impacted negatively the chances of a positive (with or without restrictions) coverage recommendation, highlighting the importance of RSAs in providing viable funding options. These results are consistent with observations elsewhere [2]. In England, the recent regulations regarding the HTA of high technology drugs and budget limit manifest NICE's willingness to balance access to new medications and economic considerations. Since initial impacts of these regulations will be available in 2020 [89, 90] subsequent analysis should be conducted to evaluate impact on access and budget.

Sixth, our analysis showed that the importance of economic evidence was, at best, very low, as neither high ICERs nor positive budget impacts were found to influence negatively coverage recommendations, despite incremental benefits being small and budget impacts being positive (i.e. requiring additional resources). This was hardly surprising and confirms arguments in the literature [32] given the peculiarities of OMPs, the ex-ante knowledge that many of them would address significant unmet needs and some in severe settings. Although poor cost-effectiveness and positive budget impact are, strictly speaking, reasons for rejection in combination with low additional clinical

value, the existence of risk mitigation strategies (which were found to be important predictors of coverage) may reveal health systems' preferences and willingness to pay.

Seventh, SVJs received explicit recognition across the study countries, but their effects, in general, or of specific SVJs in particular, on coverage recommendations were diverse and subject to country-specific, contextual or policy-relevant factors. To exemplify, eliglustat was recommended by NICE on account of its administration advantage compared to already established and effective intravenously administered treatments (velaglucerase alfa and imiglucerase; SMC rejected ivacaftor for the treatment of CF because of insufficient health benefits relative to costs and weak clinical and economic analysis, despite recognising the burden of disease on daily life and meeting SMC's ultra-orphan drug classification. Although variables associated with SVJs were shown to be not statistically significant in influencing the direction of coverage recommendations, it can be argued that their effect is indirectly captured by other variables, which are more explicitly linked to such recommendations, notably OMP status and funding modality (specifically RSAs).

It would be misleading to relate HTA recommendations to any particular component of HTA submissions; rather, HTA recommendations seem to rely on a combination of factors. National priorities, preferences in individual settings, uncertainties, values and tools to evaluate submissions have an impact on HTA recommendations [2], alongside clear preferences for the type of drug, evidence type, OMP status and putting funding arrangements in place. As such, HTA processes are not altogether lowering their standards, but seem to interpret evidence more flexibly by focusing on clinical benefit [13], and mitigating uncertainties and financial risk by resorting to risk sharing to ensure that worthwhile technologies reach patients in need. Overall, while concerns have been raised about the extent to which society should value rarity, [47] and, because of that, raise our willingness to pay thresholds, our findings suggest that HTA agencies, being proxies of societal preferences, do value rarity, but with caution.

Study limitations

The analysis is not without limitations. First, the classification of SVJs and uncertainties into an index is subjective. Although, this does not invalidate our analysis, future research might refine the way that both SVJs and uncertainties are included in the analysis in order to gauge their respective impact. Second, this analysis is based on secondary and publicly available information. HTA reports with latest publication date are included in the analysis. Previous submissions and submissions which are under consideration are not included in the analysis. Third, the calculation of average time from MA to HTA recommendation could be affected by the lack of drug-indication pairs excluded from the

analysis due to the inclusion criteria of involving at least three HTA recommendations. Fourth, on occasion, qualitative information in the reports had been withheld by the submitter therefore there was incomplete information. It is not possible to say whether this information was of value, but it is unlikely the outcomes of this study would be significantly changed by the inclusion of withheld information. Fifth, a key issue with using qualitative evidence is that there is more scope for interpretation. There is some overlap which left interpretation of parameters potentially confounded, for example the distinction between clinical practice generalisability in the clinical or economic setting. A further example is the distinction between a burden on friends and carers and cost impact on friend and carers; some findings such as 'travel to hospital' mentioned in several reports, could be considered burdensome to family in more than one sense due to time taken and cost of travel. Macro coding in such situations was difficult and author had to make decision based on context, but a different author might have interpreted otherwise. Sixth, in econometric analysis, it would have been preferable to analyse L, LWC and DNL decisions rather than DNL and all listing decisions, but it was not possible due to sample size. Future research can account for this. Seventh, while an attempt has been made to focus on funding decisions, we are not in a position to study the implementation or the uptake of these decisions, which could mean that in terms of implementation, there may be a further delay than is already shown. Finally, orphan diseases are often so rare that a physician might observe less than one case per year [86].

Conclusion

To the extent that HTA assesses robustly all submissions, including those of orphan drugs and applies the same criteria cannot be perceived as a failing. There are, however, a number of flaws in the process, as already outlined in the study; but, overall, the process appears to be fair and consistent with the standards set out ex ante. The fairness of the process is further guaranteed based on decisions to fund through RSAs and other enabling modalities.

Regardless of the existence or not of a legislative framework for orphan drugs at regulatory level, and despite some of the recent rhetoric suggesting significant delays in access, medicinal products for small populations, have received overwhelming approval by HTA bodies in the study countries. Equally, despite the differences across countries and the obvious limitations in the assessment of the clinical and economic evidence of OMPs, HTA processes have applied their standards in a robust manner. Notwithstanding the criticism that HTA has received over time across settings in terms of being too costly, time consuming, unable to recognise innovation, leading many to argue that it may be a failing or a flawed process, we find quite the opposite, namely, that it is fair. Importantly, it needs

to be recognised that HTA is a decision support tool rather than a mechanism providing definitive answers about coverage; in recognising that, it should also be recognised that, as such, it is incomplete and may require improvements, such as, for example, the more explicit recognition of value.

The study results point in the direction of and confirm a number of improvements in the way OMPs are assessed by both regulators and HTA agencies; for example, merging the requirements for MA and HTA into trial design could help optimise resource use, maximise health gain and enhance access to OMPs for patients that need them.

Perhaps the provision of earmarked or central funding for a range of rare diseases and the creation of a separate ‘orphan’ protocol could enable policy-makers ensure objective, accurate and timely HTA of OMPs. Manufacturers can maximise their effectiveness and increase the probability of an OMP receiving a positive recommendation by designing trials to provide more comparative data and structuring economic models from both a health and societal perspective, applying the agency-preferred methods for discounting and quality-adjusted utility values. From their perspective, HTA agencies need to recognise that robust modelling and adequate power – however desirable – may not always be possible in the case of OMPs. Finally, streamlining and standardising HTA processes, increasing international HTA collaboration and improving communication between HTA agencies and manufacturers will undoubtedly increase the efficiency and effectiveness of orphan drug appraisal processes. Ensuring that recommendations can be implemented optimally and uniformly, to enhance uptake and ensure geographical equity in access requires additional work and attention by decision-makers.

Appendix

Table 17- Appendix: Orphan Drugs Assessed by HTA Agencies and HTA Recommendations

Active Molecule/ Brand Name	Indication	Canada (CADTH)	Canada (ONTARIO PUBLIC DRUG PROGRAMS)	England (NICE)	Australia (PBAC)	Scotland (SMC)
Ambrisentan (Volibris)	Pulmonary arterial hypertension	L	EAP	LWC** (NHSE)	LWC	LWC
Asfotase alfa (Strensiq)	Hypophosphatasia	LWC	EAP	LWC (PAS)	DNL	n.s
Ataluren (Translarna)	Duchenne muscular dystrophy	Decision not made	Decision not made	LWC (PAS)	n.a	DNL
Azacitidine (Vidaza)	Chronic Myelomonocytic Leukaemia and Acute Myeloid Leukaemia	Decision not made	CCO NDFP	LWC (PAS)	LWC*	LWC* (PAS)
Aztreonam Lysine (Cayston)	Pseudomonas aeruginosa infection in Cystic fibrosis	L	EAP	LWC** (NHSE)	LWC*	LWC* (PAS)
Blinatumomab (Blincyto)	Acute Lymphoblastic Leukaemia	DNL*	CCO NDFP	LWC (PAS)	LWC*	LWC (PAS)
Brentuximab Vedotin (Adcetris)	Anaplastic Large Cell Lymphoma	LWC*	CCO NDFP	LWC (CDF)	LWC*	n.s

Brentuximab Vedotin (Adcetris)	Hodgkin's Lymphoma	LWC	CCO NDFP	LWC (CDF)	LWC*	n.s
Cabozantinib (Cometriq)	Thyroid Cancer	Decision not made	Decision not made	LWC (PAS)	L	DNL
Carfilzomib (Kyprolis)	Multiple Myeloma	LWC*	CCO NDFP	LWC (PAS)	LWC*	LWC (PAS)
Daratumumab (Darzalex)	Multiple Myeloma	DNL*	Not funded	LWC (CDF)	DNL	LWC* (PAS)
Eliglustat (Cerdega)	Gaucher disease	LWC	Decision not made	LWC (PAS)	DNL	LWC (PAS)
Elosulfase Alfa (Vimizim)	Mucopolysaccharidosis IV	LWC*	Not funded	LWC (PAS)	DNL*	DNL
Ibrutinib (Imbruvica)	Chronic Lymphocytic Leukaemia	LWC*	EAP	LWC (PAS)	DNL*	DNL*
Ibrutinib (Imbruvica)	Mantle Cell Lymphoma	LWC	EAP	LWC (PAS)	L*	LWC (PAS)
Ibrutinib (Imbruvica)	Waldemstrom's Macroglobulinaemia	DNL*	Not funded	LWC (CDF)	n.a	n.s
Icatibant Acetate (Firazyr)	Hereditary angioedema	LWC	EAP	LWC** (NHSE)	LWC*	LWC* (PAS)

					(RSA) ²	
Ivacaftor (Kalydeco)	Cystic fibrosis	LWC	EAP	LWC** (NHSE)	LWC*	DNL
Lenvatinib (Lenvima)	Thyroid Cancer	LWC	EAP	LWC***	LWC* (RSA)	LWC (PAS)
Macitentan (Opsumit)	Pulmonary arterial hypertension	LWC	Not funded	LWC** (NHSE)	LWC	LWC (PAS)
Mannitol (Bronchitol)	Cystic fibrosis	Decision not made	Decision not made	LWC	LWC*	LWC*
Mercaptamine (Procysbi)	Cystinosis	LWC	Decision not made	LWC** (NHSE)	n.a	DNL
Mifamurtide (Mepact)	Osteosarcoma	Decision not made	Decision not made	LWC (PAS)	n.a	LWC* (PAS)
Migalastat (Galafold)	Fabry disease	LWC	Decision not made	LWC (PAS)	DNL*	LWC (PAS)
Nintedanib (Ofev)	Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis	LWC	EAP	LWC (PAS)	LWC* (SPA+RSA)	LWC (PAS)
Nusinersen	Spinal muscular atrophy	LWC	EAP	LWC*	DNL	LWC

² The conditions of existing RSA have not been changed in the re-submission.

(Spinraza)				(NHSE/CCP) ³		(PAS)
Obeticholic Acid (Ocaliva)	Primary biliary cirrhosis	LWC	EAP	LWC (PAS)	n.a	LWC (PAS)
Obinutuzumab (Gazyvaro)	Chronic Lymphocytic Leukaemia	L	CCO NDFP	LWC (PAS)	LWC*	L
Obinutuzumab (Gazyvaro)	Follicular Lymphoma	LWC*	Decision not made	LWC (PAS)	D*	DNL*
Ofatumumab (Arzerra)	Chronic Lymphoblastic Leukaemia	DNL*	Not funded	LWC (PAS)	LWC	n.s
Panobinostat (Farydak)	Multiple Myeloma	Decision not made	Decision not made	LWC (PAS)	n.a	LWC (PAS)
Pasireotide (Signifor)	Acromegaly	DNL	Not funded	LWC** (NHSE)	LWC	L
Pirferidone (Esbriet)	Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis	LWC*	EAP	LWC* (PAS)	LWC* (SPA)	LWC* (PAS)
Plerixafor (Mozobil)	Lymphoma and Multiple Myeloma	DNL	CCO NDFP	LWC** (NHSE)	LWC* (RSA)	L
Pomalidomide	Multiple Myeloma	LWC*	EAP	LWC*	LWC*	LWC*

³ Nusinersen (Spinraza) was rejected by NICE in August 2018, but NHS England has decided to reimburse it under the Expanded Access Programme and to eligible children under commercially confidential agreements (CCPs).

(Imnovid)				(PAS)	(SPA)	(PAS)
Ponatinib (Iclusig)	Chronic myeloid leukaemia	LWC*	EAP	LWC (PAS)	L*	L
Riociguat (Adempas)	Pulmonary arterial hypertension	LWC	EAP	LWC** (NHSE)	LWC*	LWC (PAS)
Romiplostim (Nplate)	Chronic idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura	DNL	EAP	LWC (PAS)	LWC*	LWC
Teduglutide (Revestive)	Short bowel syndrome	LWC	EAP	LWC** (NHSE)	DNL	LWC
Thalidomide (Thalidomide Celgene)	Multiple Myeloma	LWC	EAP	L	LWC*	LWC
Tobramycin (Tobi Podhaler)	Cystic Fibrosis	L	LIMITED USE	LWC (PAS)	LWC* (RSA)	LWC (PAS)
Velaglucerase (Vpriv)	Gaucher Disease	L	EAP	LWC** (NHSE)	DNL*	LWC (PAS)

Notes: L= List/Approved, LWC= List with criteria; DNL= Do not list/Rejected; D= Defer, PAS=Patient Access Scheme; RSA= Risk Sharing Agreement; SPA= Special Pricing Agreement; EAP= Exceptional Access Program; CDF= Cancer Drug Fund; CCO NDFP= Cancer Care Ontario's New Drug Funding Program; n.a= Not available; n.s= Not submitted; *= denotes that the drug has been re-submitted and the outcome of the HTA process reflects the outcome of the re-submission; **= denotes drugs not reimbursed through national prices and directly commissioned by NHS England; for these drugs, funding arrangements vary from very restrictive, e.g. through individual funding requests, to restrictive, including pass through payments, made by invoices raised by provider Trusts, PAS, data monitoring and highly specialised criteria only. ***= denotes confidential commercial arrangement between the manufacturer and the competent authority.

Source: The authors from HTA reports, 2019.

Table 18- Appendix Table 2: Clinical and Surrogate Endpoints as Primary Endpoints in HTA Recommendations

Active Molecule (Brand Name) <INDICATION>	Canada (CADTH)		England (NICE)		Australia (PBAC)		Scotland (SMC)	
	Clinical Endpoint	Surrogate Endpoint						
Ambrisentan (Volibris)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Asfotase alfa (Strensiq)	X	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	NS	NS
Ataluren (Translarna)	NA	NA	X	✓	NA	NA	X	✓
Azacitidine (Vidaza)	NA	NA	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X
Aztreonam Lysine (Cayston)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Blinatumomab (Blincyto)	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓
Brentuximab Vedotin (Adcetris) sALCL	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	NS	NS
Brentuximab Vedotin (Adcetris) HL	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	NS	NS
Cabozantinib (Cometriq)	NA	NA	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓
Carfilzomib (Kyprolis)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓

Daratumumab (Darzalex)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Eliglustat (Cerdelga)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Elosulfase Alfa (Vimizim)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Ibrutinib (Imbruvica) CLL	X	✓	✓	X	X	✓	X	✓
Ibrutinib (Imbruvica) MCL	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Ibrutinib (Imbruvica) WM	X	✓	X	✓	NA	NA	NS	NS
Icatibant Acetate (Firazyr)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Ivacaftor (Kalydeco)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Lenvatinib (Lenvima)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Macitentan (Opsumit)	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mannitol (Bronchitol)	NA	NA	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Mercaptamine (Procysbi)	X	✓	X	✓	NA	NA	X	✓

Mifamurtide (Mepact)	NA	NA	✓	X	NA	NA	X	✓
Migalastat (Galafold)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Nintedanib (Ofev)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Nusinersen (Spinraza)	✓	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Obeticholic Acid (Ocaliva)	X	✓	X	✓	NA	NA	X	✓
Obinutuzumab (Gazyvaro) CLL	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	✓	X
Obinutuzumab (Gazyvaro) FL	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	✓	X
Ofatumumab (Arzerra)	X	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	NS	NS
Panobinostat (Farydak)	NA	NA	X	✓	NA	NA	X	✓
Pasireotide (Signifor)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Pirferidone (Esbriet)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Plerixafor (Mozobil)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Pomalidomide (Imnovid)	✓	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓

Ponatinib (Iclusig)	X	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓
Riociguat (Adempas)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Romiplostim (Nplate)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Teduglutide (Revestive)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Thalidomide (Thalidomide Celgene)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Tobramycin (Tobi Podhaler)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓
Velaglucerase (Vpriv)	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓

Notes: NS=not submitted; NA=not available; sALCL= Anaplastic large cell lymphoma; HL= Hodgkin's lymphoma; CLL=chronic lymphocytic leukaemia; MCL=mantle cell lymphoma; WM=; Waldemstrom's macroglobulinaemia FL=follicular lymphoma.

Source: The authors from HTA Reports, 2018.

Table 19- appendix Standard OLS regression results for HTA final funding recommendation

	A	B	C	D	E	F
Variables	Coefficients (SE)					
<i>Constant</i>	1.567*** (0.161)	1.660*** (0.133)	1.674*** (0.140)	1.647*** (0.148)	1.585*** (0.158)	1.638*** (0.185)
<i>TYPE</i>	-0.165*** (0.052)	-0.144*** (0.047)	-0.169*** (0.057)	-0.172*** (0.057)	-0.164*** (0.053)	-0.189*** (0.068)
<i>DAYS</i>	3.87 e-05 (3.82 e-05)	3.33 e-05 (3.73 e-05)	3.79 e-05 (3.84 e-05)	4 e-05 (3.87 e-05)	3.74 e-05 (3.81 e-05)	-1.33 e-5 (1.32 e-04)
<i>ENDPOINT</i>	0.135* (0.068)	0.134** (0.066)	0.140** (0.068)	0.139** (0.068)	0.134* (0.069)	0.149** (0.072)
<i>FUNDING (risk-sharing base case)</i>						
<i>Special funding agreement</i>	-0.793*** (0.133)	-0.783*** (0.138)	-0.797*** (0.141)	-0.792*** (0.141)	-0.796*** (0.142)	-0.788*** (0.151)
<i>No funding agreement reported</i>	-0.109* (0.063)	-0.094* (0.056)	-0.114* (0.062)	-0.107* (0.063)	-0.115* (0.062)	-0.131* (0.067)
<i>Not funded</i>	-0.991***	-0.973***	-0.991***	-0.989***	-0.992***	-0.988***

	(0.098)	(0.095)	(0.098)	(0.099)	(0.099)	(0.107)
<i>ORPHAN</i>	0.257**	0.225**	0.237**	0.242**	0.253**	
	(0.110)	(0.106)	(0.108)	(0.109)	(0.110)	
<i>ICER (no ICER base case)</i>						
<i>Low ICER (< £100,000)</i>						0.056
						(0.068)
<i>High ICER (> £100,000)</i>						0.110
						(0.077)
<i>HTA agency (CADTH base case)</i>						
<i>NICE</i>	-0.858***	-0.804***	-0.837***	-0.843***	-0.854***	-0.554***
	(0.185)	(0.178)	(0.183)	(0.184)	(0.185)	(0.143)
<i>PBAC</i>	-0.865***	-0.841***	-0.870***	-0.864***	-0.870***	-0.655***
	(0.157)	(0.152)	(0.156)	(0.157)	(0.157)	(0.132)
<i>SMC</i>	-0.941***	-0.895***	-0.916***	-0.922***	-0.937***	-0.641***
	(0.179)	(0.173)	(0.177)	(0.178)	(0.180)	(0.137)
<i>RESUBMIT</i>	0.020		0.027	0.029	0.017	0.008
	(0.050)		(0.054)	(0.054)	(0.054)	(0.056)

<i>QUALITY</i>	-0.034	-0.034	-0.040
	(0.058)	(0.058)	(0.062)
<i>BUDGET (high budget impact base case)</i>			
<i>Low budget impact</i>	-0.012	-0.001	0.007
	(0.110)	(0.111)	(0.117)
<i>No budget impact reported</i>	0.057	0.041	0.037
	(0.055)	(0.052)	(0.054)
<i>UNCERTAINTY</i>	0.077		0.084
	(0.091)		(0.091)
<i>SVJ</i>	0.024	0.030	
	(0.054)	(0.054)	
<i>SEVERITY</i>		-0.002	-0.012
		(0.052)	(0.056)
<i>NEED</i>			0.009
			(0.055)
<i>DAYS (SQUARED)</i>			2.50 e-08
			(5.45 e-08)

<i>YEAR</i>							-0.001 (0.012)
Sample Size	143	143	143	143	143	143	143
R-squared	0.5170	0.5102	0.5143	0.5156	0.5162	0.5057	
Adjusted R-squared	0.4600	0.4731	0.4612	0.4583	0.4591	0.4294	
F-statistic	9.06	13.75	9.68	9.01	9.04	6.62	
Prob (F-statistic)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Standard errors are reported in parentheses.

*, **, *** indicates significance at the 90%, 95%, and 99% level, respectively.

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